

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)

Grant agreement no. 101160684

U2DEMO

Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy Democratization

Deliverable D 2.4 System service provision models based on P2P trading and energy sharing

Document Details

Due date	28-02-2026
Actual delivery date	28-02-2026
Lead Contractor	VITO
Version	1.0
Prepared by	Wicak Ananduta (VITO), Hossein Fani (VITO), Anibal Sanjab (VITO), Salomé Aubri (Artelys), Guillaume Casanova (Artelys), Nicolas Fatras (Artelys), Michaël Gabay (Artelys), Rémi Graffin (Artelys), Rémi Simon (Artelys), Humberto Queiroz (EDP CNET), Francisco Reis (EDP CNET), Victoria Deichmann (INESC ID), Hugo Morais (INESC ID), Diogo Pinto Ferreira (INESC ID), Erik Delarue (KU Leuven), Yucun Lu (KU Leuven), Jelle Meus (KU Leuven), Ângelo Casaleiro (R&D Nester), Gonçalo Glória (R&D Nester), and Inoussa Laouali (R&D Nester)
Reviewed by	Thomas Heylen (Klimaan), Steven Laurijseen (Klimaan), and Gilles Deleuze (EXAION)
Dissemination Level	Public

Project Contractual Details

Project Title	Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy democratization
Project Acronym	U2Demo
Grant Agreement No.	101160684
Project Start Date	01-09-2024
Project End Date	29-02-2028
Duration	42 months

Document History

Version	Date	Contributor(s)	Description
0.1	4 February 2026	W. Ananduta, et. al.	For internal review
0.2	13 February 2026	W. Ananduta, et. al.	Updated version for internal review
0.3	24 February 2026	W. Ananduta, et. al.	For review by the scientific coordinator
0.4	26 February 2026	W. Ananduta, et. al.	Minor revision, for review by the scientific coordinator
1.0	27 February 2026	W. Ananduta, et. al.	For publication

Disclaimer

This document has been produced in the context of the U2Demo project¹. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Acknowledgment

This document is a deliverable of U2Demo project. U2Demo has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement no. 101160684.

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹<https://u2demo.eu/>

Executive Summary

This deliverable assesses how Energy Communities can provide flexibility and contribute to grid and system services at both the distribution and transmission levels, and how such participation can be embedded within local energy sharing and trading arrangements.

The overall objective of the work is to (i) analyze the regulatory context for Energy Community (EC) participation, (ii) identify suitable services and participation mechanisms, (iii) develop and integrate rule-based, tariff-based, and explicit flexibility provision mechanisms into the U2DEMO energy sharing/trading models, and (iv) evaluate technical and economic impacts through quantitative simulation and defined use cases, culminating in actionable conclusions and recommendations.

The report is structured in two parts: a introductory qualitative assessment of regulatory frameworks, implementation practices, and key drivers and barriers for EC participation across Distribution System Operator (DSO) - and Transmission System Operator (TSO) - services; and a core quantitative model-based assessment that integrates flexibility mechanisms into four U2DEMO energy sharing/trading models and evaluates their performance based on numerical simulations.

The qualitative assessment finds that, supported by the existing regulatory framework, community assets can provide reliable explicit flexibility that help manage distribution systems and can contribute to balancing service provision by aggregation with other flexibility resources. However, the uptake remains limited due to regulatory fragmentation, technical requirements, and high enabling costs, in addition to underlying flexibility markets challenges including correct baselining and adequate decentralized control of distributed flexibility assets.

Overall, the quantitative assessment concludes that explicit flexibility provision is consistently economically attractive across energy sharing/trading models. Energy communities can gain benefits from explicit provision regardless of the underlying sharing/trading framework. The four U2DEMO energy sharing/trading models can be extended to compute available aggregated flexibility as well as to dispatch flexibility within the community operations. When energy sharing is centrally determined by a community manager, a profit-oriented dispatch is more economically advantageous than purely maximising delivered flexibility volume, while benefits can be distributed to members via suitable allocation mechanisms, leading to cost reduction for each community member. When energy is traded under an internal pricing mechanism, the pricing design plays a crucial role as it significantly affects the flexibility provision activities. For auction-based local trading and pool-based peer-to-peer trading, flexibility can be provided based on the remaining asset capacity and re-optimising the schedules of all community members in order to maximise the remuneration from this activity. Nevertheless, further research is still needed to address practical challenges, such as baselining and asset control, as well as to improve the robustness of the mechanisms against uncertainties and to understand the impact of this activity on the grid beyond the activation window.

Beyond explicit mechanisms, the models were extended to provide a kW-max service via rule-based or tariff-based approaches. Rule-based schemes can strictly limit community offtake (often at the cost of higher energy costs), while tariff mechanisms can reduce peaks in some models but may not fully enforce the kW-max limit. Therefore, tariff approaches require careful fine-tuning to achieve the intended grid objectives.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
Table of Contents	6
List of Figures	8
List of Tables	9
Keywords, Acronyms	10
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Background and motivation	11
1.2 Scope and Objectives	11
1.3 Relationship with other deliverables	12
1.4 Structure of the deliverable	12
2 Provision of system services by energy communities	14
2.1 Regulatory framework analysis	14
2.2 Flexibility provision mechanisms	17
2.2.1 Market-Based Mechanisms	17
2.2.2 Rule-Based Mechanisms	20
2.2.3 Tariff-Based Mechanisms	21
2.3 Provision for DSO-level services	22
2.3.1 Congestion Management and Voltage Control	22
2.3.2 Drivers and barriers	26
2.4 Provision for TSO-level services	28
2.4.1 Frequency Ancillary services (Balancing)	28
2.4.2 Black Start and System Restoration	35
2.4.3 EC-TSO Operational Validation and Demonstration pilots	40
2.4.4 Challenges & Opportunities for EC/DER Participation in TSO Services	41
2.5 Conclusion	44
3 Modeling focus and quantitative study	46
3.1 Summary of Energy sharing models	46
3.2 Extensions for flexibility provision	46
3.3 Test case description and datasets	48
3.4 Use case datasets	48
4 Provision mechanisms for capacity, energy, and revenue allocation models	54
4.1 Energy management and sharing model	54
4.2 Mechanisms for kW-max Service	55
4.2.1 Rule-based mechanisms	55
4.2.2 Tariffs	55
4.2.3 Numerical Simulation Results	56
4.3 Explicit mechanisms for market-based services	62
4.3.1 Flexibility quantification	63
4.3.2 Flexibility disaggregation	65
4.3.3 Revenue allocation from flexibility provision	66
4.3.4 Numerical Simulation Results	66
4.4 Conclusion	75
5 Provision mechanisms for internal energy pricing models	77
5.1 Mathematical formulation	77
5.1.1 Tariff-based mechanism - Capacity tariff	77
5.1.2 Explicit mechanism	77
5.2 Results and analysis of internal energy pricing models	79

5.2.1	Capacity tariff	79
5.2.2	Explicit flexibility	83
5.3	Conclusion	86
6	Provision mechanisms for auction-based local energy trading models	89
6.1	Mechanism formulation	89
6.1.1	kWmax service	89
6.1.2	Explicit flexibility activation	93
6.2	Results and analysis of auction-based energy trading models	95
6.2.1	kWmax service	96
6.2.2	Explicit flexibility activation	103
6.3	Conclusion	106
7	Provision mechanisms for peer-to-peer energy trading models	108
7.1	Flexibility services and mechanisms modeling	108
7.1.1	Rule-based mechanism for kWmax service	108
7.1.2	Tariff-based mechanisms	109
7.1.3	Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with unknown flexibility activation periods	110
7.1.4	Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with known flexibility activation periods	111
7.2	Results and analysis of peer-to-peer energy trading models	112
7.2.1	Rule-based mechanism for kWmax service	112
7.2.2	Tariff-based mechanisms	117
7.2.3	Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with unknown and known flexibility activation periods	120
7.3	Conclusions	122
8	Conclusion and recommendations	126
8.1	Conclusion	126
8.2	Recommendations	127
9	References	129
	APPENDIX A: Grid limit calculation	134

List of Figures

Figure 2.1	Frequency ancillary services (balancing) according to the system envisaged by ENTSO-E	29
Figure 2.2	Implications of accuracy requirements – simplified control scheme [1]	31
Figure 3.1	Energy sharing and trading models.	47
Figure 3.2	Configuration of the Scheveningen pilot [2].	49
Figure 3.3	Dynamic and constant grid limits for the three cases.	50
Figure 3.4	Flexibility remuneration and retail prices.	52
Figure 3.5	The upward and downward flexibility requests for all cases.	53
Figure 4.1	Flexibility provision mechanisms for the kW-max service.	55
Figure 4.2	Community offtake and injection with and without capacity limit.	57
Figure 4.3	Community offtake and injection with and without capacity tariffs.	59
Figure 4.4	Community offtake and injection with and without ToU tariffs.	60
Figure 4.5	Single-day example of community offtake with and without ToU tariff	61
Figure 4.6	Market-based explicit flexibility provision mechanism.	62
Figure 4.7	Daily maximum available upward and downward flexibility.	67
Figure 4.8	Maximum upward and downward flexibility with retail pricing schemes.	68
Figure 4.9	Different characterisations for maximum upward and downward flexibility.	70
Figure 4.10	Total quantified flexibility for different characterisations.	71
Figure 4.11	Total provided flexibility and cost for flexibility disaggregation.	72
Figure 4.12	Daily provided flexibility and cost for flexibility disaggregation.	74
Figure 5.1	Comparison of daily peak loads with and without the capacity tariff.	80
Figure 5.2	Violations of dynamic grid limits in Case 3 - RTP	82
Figure 5.3	Relative cost change after the implementation of the capacity tariff.	82
Figure 5.4	Comparison of activated flexibility versus requirements under Fixed Rate and real-time pricing (RTP) tariffs across three cases.	84
Figure 5.5	Example of flexibility activation for a single day in Case 3 under the fixed rate contract.	86
Figure 5.6	Decomposition of the total consumer cost under the explicit flexibility mechanism.	87
Figure 6.1	Workflow diagram for explicit flexibility activation valorisation	93
Figure 6.2	Impact of constant rule-based mechanism on community savings	97
Figure 6.3	Impact of constant rule-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes	97
Figure 6.4	Impact of case-dependent CONSTANT kWmax rule-based mechanism on community savings in different scenarios	98
Figure 6.5	Impact of case-dependent CONSTANT kWmax rule-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes	98
Figure 6.6	Impact of DYNAMIC kWmax rule-based mechanism on community savings	99
Figure 6.7	Impact of DYNAMIC kWmax rule-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes	99
Figure 6.8	Impact of energy grid tariff-based mechanism on community savings	100
Figure 6.9	Impact of energy grid tariff-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes	100
Figure 6.10	Grid net position of community for different tariff-based kWmax scenarios	103
Figure 6.11	Comparison of flex activation revenues as a share of community bill after energy sharing.	104
Figure 6.12	Household profile deviations across studied cases with dynamic retail tariffs.	105

Figure 7.1	Net consumption in the baseline case, the computed kWmax limit, and the resulting net consumption with the active kWmax limit of the EC from the retailer in hour 18.	115
Figure 7.2	Net consumption in the baseline case, the computed kWmax limit, and the resulting net consumption with the active kWmax limit of the EC from the retailer in hour 19.	116
Figure 7.3	Peak net consumption for each day for the baseline simulation with and without the capacity tariff.	117
Figure 7.4	Daily repeating Time-of-Use tariff used in the simulation.	118
Figure 7.5	Sum of the battery charging and discharging and net consumption from retailer.	119
Figure A.1	Example of the LDC of community offtake in Case 1.	134

List of Tables

Table 2.1	FFR main characteristics	29
Table 2.2	Summary of FCR product design per country.	31
Table 2.3	Minimum accuracy of frequency measurement [3]	32
Table 2.4	Summary of Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserves (aFRR) product design per country.	33
Table 2.5	Summary of Manual Frequency Restoration Reserves (mFRR) product design per country.	34
Table 2.6	Qualitative assessment of DER participation in black-start processes [4]	38
Table 2.7	Barriers and mitigation measures for DER participation in Balancing services .	42
Table 2.8	Barriers and mitigation measures for DER participation in Black-Start services	43
Table 3.1	Summary of flexibility mechanisms that are developed for different energy sharing models.	48
Table 3.2	Solar PV capacity [kWp] for the three cases.	51
Table 3.3	Battery (dis)charging power [kW] and energy capacity [kWh] for the three cases.	51
Table 4.1	Community total cost (EUR) under baseline, dynamic, and static grid limit scenarios.	58
Table 4.2	Total annual maximum upward and downward flexibility.	67
Table 4.3	Summary of flexibility characterisations considered in the analysis.	69
Table 4.4	The average cost reduction of all community members over all cases by performing flexibility provision	75
Table 6.1	Exchanged volumes (in kW) for each baseline scenario, aggregated over all community members over a year	96
Table 6.2	Total community bill (purchase minus sale, in €) for each baseline scenario, aggregated over all community members over a year	96
Table 7.1	Computation of the kWmax limit.	109
Table 7.2	Total energy bill of the community [€].	112
Table 7.3	Increase of the total energy bill of the community [%].	113
Table 7.4	Comparison between the baseline case, the kWmax limit and the simulation with the active kWmax limit shown in Figure 7.1.	114
Table 7.5	Total bill of the community [€].	120
Table 7.6	Percentual reduction of the annual total bill [%].	120
Table 7.7	Components of the bill in the simulation with flexibility activation [€].	121
Table 7.8	Percentual increase of the annual bill - only the energy part [%].	122

Keywords, Acronym

aFRR	Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserves
API	Application Programming Interface
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BRP	Balance Responsible Parties
BS	Black-Start
BSP	Balancing Service Provider
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CLC	Capacity Limiting Contract
CLC-A	Capacity Limiting Contract on Request
CLC-T	Capacity Limiting Contract with Time
CSP	Congestion Service Provider
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DERMS	Distributed Energy Resource Management System
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EAN	European Article Number
EC	Energy Community
EU	European Union
EV	Electrical Vehicle
FCA	Flexible Connection Agreement
FCR	Frequency Containment Reserves
FFR	Fast Frequency Response
FRP	Frequency Restoration Process
FRR	Frequency Restoration Reserves
FSP	Flexibility Service Provider
HEMS	Home Energy Management System
HP	Heat Pump
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LFC	Load-Frequency Control
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
LV	Low Voltage
mFRR	Manual Frequency Restoration Reserves
MMR	Mid-Market Rate
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MV	Medium Voltage
NC DR	Network Code on Demand Response
NEMO	Nominated Electricity Market Operator
PoD	Point of Delivery
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Communities
RR	Replacement Reserve
RTP	real-time pricing
SDR	Supply-Demand Ratio
SO	System Operator
ToU	Time-of-Use
TSO	Transmission System Operator

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

An Energy Community (EC) can actively participate in explicit flexibility provision by offering their flexible assets, such as batteries, controllable loads, distributed generation, and electric vehicles, in flexibility markets that support system services, including balancing and congestion management. While balancing markets are already mature in many power systems, Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs) at the distribution level are currently being introduced or piloted in a growing number of countries. This development suggests substantial potential for new revenue streams for EC members. In parallel, an energy community can engage in other flexibility mechanisms, such as via reaction to network tariffs and dynamic price signals, in addition to more control-based (also referred to as, rule-based) mechanisms set by the relevant Distribution System Operator (DSO) or Transmission System Operator (TSO), including flexible connection agreements, and imposed dynamic grid connection limits.

In Task 2.4, the U2DEMO project investigates flexibility provision mechanisms that are suitable for energy communities and develops methodologies to embed these mechanisms into the internal energy sharing and trading activities within the community. The mechanisms are evaluated through comprehensive quantitative analyses to assess technical feasibility and economic value. In addition, a complementary qualitative study examines the regulatory framework, key drivers, and challenges for the participation of ECs in the provision of system services both at the distribution and transmission levels, through various mechanisms.

We, here, differentiate between three key dimensions:

1. Flexibility service to be provided to, e.g., a system operator, such as balancing services, congestion management, voltage control, etc.
2. Flexibility instrument, which is the flexibility mechanism employed to procure flexibility from flexibility service providers (including energy communities) and deliver that flexibility service. Such flexibility instruments include explicit flexibility markets, implicit flexibility mechanisms such as network tariffs (volumetric or capacity-based, static or dynamic), and rule-based instruments.
3. Local energy sharing model, which determines how an energy community shares energy internally (these models will be recapped in this document, and were extensively analyzed in U2Demo D2.3 [2]).

Then, the question we investigate here is how different energy sharing models can provide the foundation to support the provision of flexibility by energy communities, ensuring the ability of the energy communities to actually deliver that flexibility through local energy exchange/coordination, while considering different flexibility services and different flexibility instruments.

1.2 Scope and Objectives

This deliverable investigates how ECs can participate in different flexibility mechanisms and deliver grid and system services. We first start with an introductory qualitative assessment of regulatory and implementation aspects. We then follow with a thorough quantitative evaluation based on the U2DEMO energy sharing/trading models. The scope covers flexibility services at both the distribution and transmission levels and considers a range of flexibility provision mechanisms (e.g., market-based, rule-based, and tariff-based arrangements), including their

technical requirements, operational implications, and practical feasibility for ECs.

The overarching objective of this study is to analyze the different forms of flexibility services that ECs, via different flexibility instruments, can deliver and, importantly, to identify how such flexibility can be unlocked and realised within local energy sharing/trading models that can be implemented within energy communities. This is achieved first through a qualitative analyses of the flexibility services and key instruments available to ECs, followed by modeling-based quantitative analyses showcasing how such flexibility mechanisms can be integrated in local energy sharing frameworks in ECs, how such services can then be provided collectively by the EC members, and the impacts thereof (captured by a number of computed Key Performance Indicator (KPI)s). This overarching objective is achieved via a number of sub objectives including:

- To understand the regulatory frameworks and enabling conditions governing flexibility provision by ECs across relevant contexts;
- To identify and analyze suitable distribution- and transmission-level system services for which an EC can provide flexibility;
- To review and assess available flexibility provision mechanisms, including their technical specifications, market/design features, and implementation approaches, and derive the key drivers and barriers affecting participation of ECs;
- To develop and integrate flexibility provision mechanisms within the U2DEMO local energy sharing/trading models, translating participation options into consistent mathematical formulations and tools for the provision and delivery of flexibility collectively via local coordination and energy sharing/exchanges;
- To provide a thorough quantitative evaluation of the developed mechanisms using defined use cases, test cases, and datasets, assessing technical performance and economic impacts for community members;
- To synthesise insights from the qualitative and quantitative work into actionable conclusions and recommendations to support EC participation in flexibility provision.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

This deliverable is closely linked to D2.1, which analyses and establishes common forms of energy sharing and trading. The mathematical models developed here build on the modelling frameworks for energy sharing and trading defined in D2.3, thus mathematical formulations in this deliverable are tightly coupled with those in D2.3. Additionally, individual decision-making processes are supported by the tools developed in D2.2.

Together with D2.3, the outcomes of this deliverable inform the design of energy sharing and trading algorithms to be implemented in the U2DEMO open-source platform, as well as algorithms enabling participation in system-service provision (Tasks 4.1, 4.3, and 4.4). As a result, this deliverable also has implications for the information exchange requirements and design addressed in Task 3.1.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is organised into two main parts, i.e., the qualitative and quantitative studies, and is structured as follows.

Section 2 presents the qualitative study on the provision of grid and system services at both the distribution and transmission levels. It begins with an analysis of the regulatory framework and then assesses three main categories of flexibility mechanisms: market-based, rule-based, and tariff-based mechanisms. Subsequently, the section evaluates DSO-level and TSO-level services across European Union (EU) countries, focusing on drivers and barriers for participation of ECs.

The quantitative study, which represents the largest part of the document, is then presented in Sections 3–7. Section 3 first introduces the four energy sharing/trading models examined in the U2DEMO D2.3 report [2]. It also outlines two system-service provision use cases that form the core focus of the analysis, and describes the test cases as well as common datasets used throughout the study. Then, Sections 4–7 develop the mathematical formulations and present the corresponding analyses of flexibility provision mechanisms for each energy sharing/trading model.

Finally, Section 8 concludes this report and presents recommendations.

2 Provision of system services by energy communities

This section examines how ECs can participate in providing DSO- and TSO-level services. It covers the regulatory framework and its implementation across EU member states—focusing in particular on the U2Demo demonstration countries, along with lessons learned from pilot projects and the key drivers and barriers to participation.

2.1 Regulatory framework analysis

According to Article 22(2) of the Renewable Energy Directive (2018/2001/EU) [5], renewable energy communities Renewable Energy Communities (REC)s are entitled to:

- Produce, consume, store, and sell renewable energy, including through renewable power purchase agreements.
- Share, within the REC, renewable energy that is produced by the production units owned by that REC, subject to the other requirements laid down in this Article and to maintaining the rights and obligations of the renewable energy community members as customers.
- Access all suitable energy markets both directly or through aggregation in a non-discriminatory manner.

Regarding the Electricity Market Directive (2019/944/EU) [6], according to Article 2(11)(c), citizen energy communities Citizen Energy Community (CEC)s are entitled to engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders. Additionally, CECs are entitled to own, establish, purchase, or lease distribution networks and to autonomously manage them (Article 16 (2)(b)), being subjected to the same obligations imposed on DSOs. Furthermore, in Article 16(3)(a), CECs can access all electricity markets, either directly or through aggregation, in a non-discriminatory manner.

Thus, implicit flexibility can be accomplished through the optimisation of the communities' assets (production units, storage systems, and flexible loads), based on price signals or dynamic tariffs. Moreover, explicit flexibility can also be performed by RECs and CECs, since both have the right to access all electricity markets directly or through aggregation, including the provision of flexibility services to system operators and participation in congestion management or re-dispatch mechanisms, particularly at the distribution level, where DSOs are entitled to contract flexibility services from distributed generation, consumers, or storage providers.

Furthermore, the Electricity Balancing Guideline [7] (Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/2195) establishes that all balancing services, including Frequency Containment Reserves Frequency Containment Reserves (FCR), automatic Frequency Restoration Reserves aFRR, and manual Frequency Restoration Reserves mFRR, must be procured through transparent, technology-neutral, and market-based mechanisms. This Regulation explicitly allows the aggregation of generation, demand, and storage resources, enabling RECs and CECs to participate in TSO balancing markets either directly or through aggregators, provided that the applicable technical prequalification requirements are met.

These directives have been transposed to the national legal system of all countries where project pilots are established. In Italy, energy communities may offer ancillary and flexibility services (Article 31(2)(f) of Decreto Legislativo 199/21). Article 31(2)(b) of Decreto Legislativo

199/21 emphasises the relevance of on-site instantaneous self-consumption of energy and energy sharing among community members, thus only surplus energy may be stored and sold.

In Portugal, the operationalisation of these rights is framed by the roles and competences of system operators. The Transmission System Operator (REN - Redes Energéticas Nacionais) is responsible for the security and continuity of electricity supply and for the operation of system services markets, while DSOs, notably E-REDES, are explicitly allowed to contract flexibility services from distributed generation, consumers, and energy storage providers, particularly for congestion management. This establishes a concrete operational pathway for energy communities to provide flexibility services at distribution level, potentially aggregated and coordinated with TSO-level system services. Decree-Law n.15/2022 describes the activities RECs and CECs are entitled to conduct in Portugal. According to this document, energy communities can produce, consume, store, purchase and sell renewable energy with their members or third parties. Besides, energy communities have access to all energy markets, including system services, both directly and through aggregation, while remaining subject to the same rights and obligations applicable to other electricity market participants, including responsibility for deviations under the Network Operation Regulation, which may be transferred to an aggregator or designated representative.

In the Portuguese regulatory framework, particular emphasis is placed on instantaneous self-consumption and internal energy sharing. Energy storage within energy communities is permitted; however, surplus energy storage and commercialisation are subject to regulatory conditions, and energy drawn from the grid for storage purposes is accounted for separately and billed according to applicable tariffs. This reinforces the policy objective of prioritising local consumption over market-oriented energy arbitrage.

In the Flanders region of Belgium, Article 4.8.4. of the Energiedecreet provides details on the activities energy communities may undertake. It is mentioned that energy communities may produce, consume, share, store, and sell energy, plus they can act as a service provider of flexibility or participant in flexibility or aggregation. This energy must be from an installation, directly or indirectly connected via the connection of partners or members of the energy community to an electricity distribution network, the local electricity transmission network, or a closed distribution network.

In the Netherlands, the Energy Act assumes that it should not matter who is engaged in a market activity, but it is the activity itself that determines which rules apply. This classification has the advantage that the question of who performs a market activity (such as a traditional supplier or a party presenting itself as an energy community) is less relevant, and a non-discriminatory framework is established for the various market participants.

Finally, the Emergency and Restoration Network Code [8] (Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/2196) establishes a technology-neutral framework for system defence, restoration, and black-start services. This Regulation defines black-start capability based on functional requirements rather than asset type, allowing distributed generation, storage systems, and aggregated resources (including those owned or operated by energy communities) to participate in system restoration activities, provided they are capable of energising network sections without external supply and supporting coordinated TSO-DSO restoration processes.

Flexibility in Distribution Networks

Article 32 of the Electricity Market Directive (2019/944/EU) establishes a regulatory framework that mandates a shift toward the use of flexibility in distribution networks to enhance system efficiency. Member States are required to ensure that DSOs are both allowed and incentivised to procure flexibility services, such as congestion management, from providers of distributed generation, demand response, or energy storage, and, as an example, national implementation explicitly allows DSOs in Portugal to contract such flexibility services from distributed generation, consumers, or energy storage providers to increase operational efficiency and defer network reinforcements. Crucially, the procurement of these services must be conducted through transparent, non-discriminatory, and market-based procedures as the standard operating model. Deviations from these market-based mechanisms are only permissible if the national regulatory authority explicitly determines that such procurement would be economically inefficient, cause severe market distortions, or lead to higher levels of congestion [6].

To facilitate these market-based interactions, DSOs or national regulatory authorities must engage in a participatory process with system users and TSOs to establish clear specifications for flexibility services and develop standardised market products. This standardisation is designed to ensure that all qualified participants, including those offering renewable energy or aggregation services, can compete effectively and without discrimination. Furthermore, DSOs must coordinate closely with TSOs to ensure the optimal use of resources and the secure operation of the broader electricity system. To support these activities, DSOs are entitled to remuneration that covers their reasonable costs, including those related to the necessary information and communication technology infrastructure required to manage these market interactions [9].

Long-term transparency regarding market needs is provided through mandatory network development plans, which DSOs must publish at least every two years [9]. These plans are essential for signaling upcoming market opportunities, as they must outline medium and long-term flexibility requirements and detail planned investments for the following five to ten years. The Directive emphasises that these plans must explicitly consider demand response, energy efficiency, and energy storage as viable alternatives to traditional system expansion. Before these plans are submitted to national regulatory authorities, DSOs must consult with all relevant system users and TSOs, ensuring that the development of the distribution grid is a transparent process. While these planning requirements are extensive, Member States may choose to exempt integrated electricity undertakings with fewer than 100,000 connected customers or those serving small isolated systems from the obligation to produce these specific plans.

Regulation (EU) 2024/1747 is introduced as an amendment to Regulation (EU) 2019/943. Article 19e establishes a mandatory framework for the assessment of flexibility needs at the national level. Under this article, national regulatory authorities or other designated entities must compile a report every two years that estimates the flexibility requirements of the electricity system for at least the next five to ten years. This report is intended to support the cost-effective achievement of security of supply and the decarbonisation of the system, specifically considering the integration of variable renewable energy sources and the interconnected nature of the electricity market (including interconnection targets and potential availability of cross-border flexibility). These assessments must be consistent with European and national resource adequacy assessments and rely on data provided by transmission and distribution system operators.

These reports must evaluate various types of flexibility on seasonal, daily, and hourly bases to effectively integrate renewable energy, while considering different assumptions for electricity market prices, generation, and demand. These reports are required to assess the potential of

non-fossil flexibility resources, such as demand response, energy storage, aggregation, and interconnection, across both transmission and distribution levels. Furthermore, the assessment must identify existing market barriers to flexibility and propose relevant mitigation measures or incentives, such as removing regulatory hurdles or improving system operation services. The reports must also evaluate the role of digitalisation in electricity networks and consider flexibility sources that are anticipated to be available in other Member States. To facilitate this process, the ENTSO-E and the E.DSO entities are required to coordinate the efforts of system operators, defining the necessary data formats and developing a common methodology for the analysis of flexibility needs. This methodology must consider all available sources in a cost-efficient manner and align with the Union's 2030 and 2050 climate and energy targets.

National reports must be published and submitted to the European Commission and the Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER). Then, ACER shall produce a Union-level analysis providing recommendations on cross-border issues and the removal of barriers for non-fossil flexibility resources. Finally, the findings from these national reports must be integrated into the Union-wide network development plan, which shall be considered by system operators when designing their own network development strategies [9].

The current studies and strategies for TSO services and DSO flexibility provision implemented in countries where project pilots are established are explored in later sections.

2.2 Flexibility provision mechanisms

In general, flexibility provision mechanisms for system services can be grouped into three classes, namely market-based, rule-based, and tariff-based (implicit) mechanisms. This section reviews the implementation of these mechanisms.

2.2.1 Market-Based Mechanisms

TSO Level

At the transmission level, flexibility is primarily procured through market-based balancing and ancillary services to maintain system frequency, voltage, and overall security of supply. Within the harmonised European framework, System Operators (SOs) perform a set of critical operational roles, with TSOs most frequently acting as System Operator, Load-Frequency Control (LFC) Operator, and Imbalance Settlement Responsible, as defined in the Harmonised Electricity Market Role Model [10].

TSOs relies on a portfolio of ancillary services to manage real-time system operation under both normal and disturbed conditions. Some services are defined as mandatory capabilities under Network Codes [11], while others are procured through regulated or competitive market mechanisms when needed to preserve reliability and security. Following the unbundling and liberalisation of the electricity sector, services such as frequency and voltage control, previously delivered by vertically integrated utilities, are now increasingly obtained from third-party market participants through transparent, technology-neutral procurement mechanisms [12].

Balancing markets play a central operational role in this context, enabling TSOs to procure active power reserves to ensure system balance, defined as the continuous matching between scheduled and actual electricity production and consumption. These reserves are provided by Balancing Service Providers (BSPs), which may own or aggregate generation units, demand response, storage, or mixed portfolios, and commit their resources exclusively to a control area

for the delivery of services such as Fast Frequency Response (FFR), FCR, aFRR, mFRR, and Replacement Reserve (RR). Participation in these markets is subject to prequalification procedures, which verify compliance with technical and operational requirements related to controllability, communication, availability, and dynamic performance.

In parallel, Balance Responsible Parties (BRP) retain financial responsibility for imbalances between scheduled and actual energy positions, ensuring appropriate settlement and economic accountability. Together, BSP and BRP roles form the backbone of the European balancing framework, linking operational flexibility provision with market-based incentives.

The large-scale integration of variable renewable energy sources and the decline of conventional synchronous generation have increased system variability and reduced inherent inertia. As a result, the European power system is transitioning from a model dominated by large centralised generators toward one increasingly supported by distributed flexibility resources, including demand response, energy storage, and community-level assets. This structural shift opens new opportunities for ECs and aggregators to participate in TSO-level markets, primarily through aggregation of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) [13].

Ancillary services procured by TSOs can be broadly classified into three categories:

- Frequency ancillary services (balancing), which maintain and restore system frequency over different time horizons;
- Voltage control ancillary services, ensuring reactive power balance and stable voltage levels;
- System defence and restoration services, such as black-start and islanded operation, enabling recovery after major disturbances or blackouts.

DSO Level - Local Flexibility Markets

LFMs are market-based procedures that allow DSOs to procure flexibility services from DERs to improve grid efficiency. They are designed to provide a transparent and non-discriminatory alternative to traditional infrastructure expansion. The primary purpose of these markets is to incentivise DSOs to consider flexibility alternatives as the standard operating model instead of traditional network reinforcements. By managing local congestion and voltage problems through market-based procurement, LFMs aim to lower overall system costs and support the achievement of decarbonisation targets in a cost-effective manner. Therefore, LFMs represent another mechanism for explicit flexibility, allowing DERs to respond to flexibility requests for a certain compensation [14].

LFMs are governed by the principle of technological neutrality, which permits a wide array of DERs to participate in grid services. While participation is open to residential, commercial, and industrial users, it is typically facilitated through BSPs or independent aggregators who pool smaller assets [14]. This characteristic enables the participation of energy communities in LFMs, as the community manager undertakes the role of a BSP, managing all the community's flexible assets. Alternatively, an energy community's assets may be eligible for participation through inclusion in a larger aggregator's portfolio [15].

LFMs are structured around diverse temporal designs and payment mechanisms intended to incentivise participation and fairly compensate DERs. Long-term designs often involve auctions held at least one year in advance, where providers commit to capacity availability and receive dual remuneration consisting of fixed availability payments (€/MW/h) and utilisation fees

(€/MWh) for actual energy delivered. While many products allow for voluntary participation whenever it suits the user's operational needs, certain frameworks include mandatory bidding contracts that obligate the provider to submit a bid whenever a request they qualify for is announced. Conversely, short-term or spot markets operate on a day-ahead or intraday basis, typically paying only for the actual delivery of services through a pay-as-bid auction system. Specific products are designed for managing predictable congestion, while others are established for scheduled maintenance or even for grid failures. To streamline these processes, some pilots are implementing blockchain-based smart contracts to ensure automated, transparent settlement and verification [14, 16, 17, 18].

The first European initiatives for LFMs emerged in Great Britain and the Netherlands, which currently represent the most advanced and mature frameworks in Europe. Since December 2018, all six British DSOs have operated under a formal flexibility commitment to use market-based services as an alternative to grid reinforcement, while the Dutch GOPACS platform serves as a fully operational national scheme allowing both the TSO and DSOs to procure flexibility services [14]. These established markets paved the way for EU Directive 2019/944, which now mandates that all Member States provide incentives and regulatory frameworks for DSOs to procure flexibility through transparent, non-discriminatory, and market-based procedures [6]. Following this regulatory push, several other countries have launched initiatives at various stages of development, including France's Enedis, Sweden's Sthlmflex, and, more recently, pilot projects such as Portugal's FIRMe, Slovenia's direct consumer calls, and Italy's EDGE, RomeFlex, and MiND-Flex. Despite these advancements, the overall prevalence of LFMs remains limited. As of 2025, several countries reported that their DSOs have not yet formally assessed local flexibility needs, and most national regulatory authorities do not anticipate that market-based procurement will exclusively satisfy local grid requirements for at least another five to ten years [9].

Technical eligibility is strictly tied to locational constraints, as resources must be connected to specific electrical nodes within designated "Flexibility Perimeters" to effectively resolve local congestion. Minimum bid sizes vary considerably across Europe to accommodate different user groups, ranging from as low as 1 kW up to 50 kW or 100 kW [18, 19, 17]. Furthermore, participants must possess advanced metering infrastructure for baseline estimation and service provision validation, and also ensure their assets are controllable and modifiable to respond to DSO activation signals. Finally, providers must fulfill administrative requirements by registering on independent market platforms (such as Piclo or NODES) and signing contractual agreements that define the legal framework for data exchange, baseline verification, and financial settlement [14].

The widespread adoption of LFMs is primarily hindered by a fragmented regulatory framework that lacks consistent national or EU-level references, creating significant uncertainty for service providers and complicating the scalability of market platforms across different jurisdictions. Low market liquidity remains a universal challenge, where low participation rates result in a lack of competition and bid prices that stay close to maximum price caps, potentially undermining the effectiveness of LFMs [20, 21, 17]. From a technical perspective, the lack of observability and monitoring infrastructure, particularly at the low-voltage level, prevents DSOs from managing flexibility in real-time, while the absence of remote-control automation for small-scale resources creates significant barriers to efficient service activation. Furthermore, economic sustainability is a major concern for providers due to revenue unpredictability and high entry costs for metering and instrumentation. Operational risks are further complicated by locational constraints, where assets are often disqualified because they are electrically connected to nodes unsuitable for resolving a specific congestion, despite their physical proximity to the problem. Additionally,

baseline verification remains an unresolved issue, as historical averages often fail to accurately reflect the behavior of weather-dependent renewables, leading to potential settlement errors and disputes [9, 14].

TSO- DSO Coordination Schemes Observing the development and adoption of LFM, we can expect closer coordination between DSOs and the corresponding TSO in the future. Coordination between TSOs and DSOs when procuring flexibility has been extensively investigated in recent projects, e.g., Coordinet [22], Onenet [23]. A range of coordinated market designs have been proposed [22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28]. Studies have shown that a common market scheme, where system services from different system operators are procured through a single market, can be the most economically efficient option, but it is also the most challenging approach to implement in practice [23, 29, 28]. A more practical approach is to enable forwarding flexibility bids between markets if they are not cleared in the original one, which can improve coordination and overall system efficiency [30, 31]. Such bid forwarding can also facilitate value stacking and increase the likelihood that a Flexibility Service Provider (FSP) is remunerated. In general, the use of distributed flexibility in distribution and transmission-level markets offers a large pool of flexibility resources for TSOs and DSOs and deliver additional revenue streams to end-users. This participation, however, must also consider the grid-safety of the distribution grids from which this flexibility is generated, to ensure that distributed flexibility can be safely activated [32, 33].

2.2.2 Rule-Based Mechanisms

Flexible Connection Agreements (FCAs) are contractual agreements that allow for the connection of DERs to the power grid under conditions that permit system operators to limit or control electricity injection and withdrawal. These agreements are increasingly viewed as a complementary tool to address network congestion and optimise the use of existing infrastructure, reducing the need for reinforcements [34]. Thus, FCAs are classified as an explicit flexibility mechanism. These agreements establish specific conditions under which system operators can limit a user's grid usage, which can be structured as either concrete, predefined schedules or as responses to direct, real-time signals sent by the system operator [15].

The core purpose of these agreements is to serve as a complementary tool for managing network congestion and reducing system peaks, which helps to minimise or postpone the need for traditional infrastructure reinforcements [6]. By allowing for controlled network usage, these agreements accelerate the connection of renewable energy sources and new demand in areas where sufficient firm capacity is not yet available, providing a faster alternative to waiting for full grid buildouts. Furthermore, they often act as a temporary bridge solution, facilitating immediate grid access for users with controllable installations until permanent reinforcements are completed or until more mature, market-based flexibility frameworks are established [17]. While FCAs are mostly offered on a voluntary basis, some countries like Belgium, Czechia, and Germany have mandatory requirements for specific user groups [34].

These agreements are slightly more common for energy injection than for withdrawal, and they are often incentivised through financial benefits. Such incentives include discounts on use-of-network charges or reduced connection fees. In countries where no direct discounts are applied, users still benefit from the ability to connect to the grid significantly earlier than they would under a firm agreement [34, 9]. A critical condition often attached to these contracts is their temporary nature, with regulatory recommendations highlighting the need for a clear process to convert

flexible agreements into firm connections once the relevant grid infrastructure has been reinforced. Furthermore, participants must generally possess the technical capability to respond to system operator signals, which may require specific metering or telecontrol equipment to limit capacity during periods of network stress [15].

Capacity Limiting Contracts (CLCs) are a subset of FCAs, where users operate under rules set by the DSO, serving as an explicit flexibility mechanism that permits system operators to limit or control injection and withdrawal capacity to manage network congestion and avoid costly infrastructure reinforcements. These contractual arrangements are typically structured into two main variants. Static contracts, such as the Capacity Limiting Contract with Time (CLC-T) in the Netherlands, mandate that users commit to reducing consumption or generation at fixed, pre-defined time periods. In opposition, in dynamic contracts, such as the Capacity Limiting Contract on Request (CLC-A) in the Netherlands, limitations are activated with at least a day-ahead notice when congestion is expected. While participants benefit from availability payments and utilisation fees, these contracts also give rise to financial risk, as failing to meet a setpoint can result in severe financial penalties. Certain studies suggest that these capacity limitation services may offer a simpler and more transparent alternative to baseline dependent flexibility products [14].

Regarding regulatory challenges and risks, while FCAs offer significant benefits for grid management, they present several intricacies, such as the potential to hinder the development of market-based flexibility procurement if system operators utilise “free flexibility” through these contracts without offering payment. There is a specific concern that if FCAs are treated as permanent solutions, they could become a barrier to more efficient long-term tools like demand response or independent storage. Furthermore, stakeholders have highlighted that an over-reliance on such agreements might hinder necessary grid investments and shift the focus away from long-term infrastructure solutions [9]. Additionally, the currently fragmented nature of these agreements means that a lack of standardised and clear terms can create uncertainty for participants regarding how their specific network tariffs will be adapted to these non-firm connection conditions [34].

2.2.3 Tariff-Based Mechanisms

Network tariffs are designed with varying rate structures that incentivise customer behavior, supporting DSOs in congestion mitigation and voltage level control in Low Voltage (LV) and Medium Voltage (MV) networks. As users voluntarily choose if they want to adjust their production and/or consumption without receiving any signals from the DSO, this mechanism can be classified as implicit flexibility. DSOs can implement different tariff schemes, depending on time scale, location, national policy frameworks or metering capabilities, to address specific network needs [34].

Time-of-Use (ToU) tariff is the most common tariff scheme, which has fixed time periods with different rates (peak/off-peak price periods, for example). These tariffs are implemented with the goal of shifting consumption from high-demand hours, reducing peak-load congestion and voltage level deviations caused by simultaneous evening loads. Likewise, dynamic tariffs [35] have variable rates but do not establish fixed time periods. Tariff rates and time periods are defined in day-ahead or real time to deal with short-term congestions and fast voltage variations, typically in areas with high Photovoltaic (PV) penetration. Seasonal tariffs are similar to ToU tariffs, but for larger time scales. As ToU tariffs define higher rates for certain hours of the day, seasonal tariffs define higher rates in certain seasons to alleviate, for instance, demand peaks from heating needs in the winter [34].

Unlike the previous examples, capacity tariffs are based on the user's peak consumption instead of energy consumption. These tariffs are implemented for peak shaving, incentivising users to distribute their consumption throughout the day [17]. Tariffs can also be locationally differentiated, with rates varying by geographic zone or network area. They can be embedded in one-off connection charges and/or use-of-network charges, reflecting differences in network cost conditions in different zones.

Particularly, in certain European countries, energy communities and collective self-consumers are subject to a specific tariff regime, which includes [34]:

- Exemption from network charges for costs arising from the use of higher voltage levels for energy sharing (Portugal).
- Reduced use-of-network charges for the quantities not withdrawn from the public grid by the community (Austria).
- Reduced or specific use-of-network charges on shared (self-consumed) electricity within the community or collective of self-consumers (for example, same facility or based on contract and perimeter criteria) (France and Belgium, specifically in Brussels as well as the Walloon region).
- Separate charging of each community member according to its use of the public network (Slovenia, for new energy communities without yearly net metering).
- Net metering (i.e., charging only for the difference between withdrawal and injection by the energy community, not applicable to new users), similar to the regime that applies to individual prosumers (Slovenia, not applicable to new energy communities).
- Quarter-hourly netting of production and consumption at a certain voltage level and within a certain geographical perimeter (Luxembourg).

2.3 Provision for DSO-level services

2.3.1 Congestion Management and Voltage Control

ECs in Portugal, the Netherlands, Italy, and the Flemish region of Belgium (where U2Demo's pilots are located) are increasingly legally empowered to provide critical grid services, such as congestion management and voltage control, to help DSOs maintain network stability [15]. These services are facilitated through three primary mechanisms: the participation in LFMs, the adoption of incentive-based network tariff schemes, and the establishment of FCAs. Through LFMs, DSOs procure explicit flexibility by compensating energy communities for specific adjustments to their electricity injection or withdrawal to resolve localised grid issues. Simultaneously, implicit flexibility is incentivised through power-based and ToU tariffs, which encourage communities to optimise their behavior and reduce grid stress during peak periods. Furthermore, FCAs serve as an additional explicit mechanism, particularly in congested areas, allowing communities faster grid access in exchange for the DSO's right to limit or control network usage during predefined windows or upon a real-time signal. Although there is an emerging interest in reactive power procurement, current operational frameworks in these regions remain primarily focused on active power regulation as the fundamental tool for delivering these essential DSO services [14].

Network Tariff Schemes

Network tariff structures across the studied regions are increasingly shifting toward ToU and capacity-based schemes to provide implicit flexibility signals and manage grid congestion [34]. Unlike traditional energy-based tariffs, capacity tariffs are calculated based on a user's peak consumption rather than total volume, specifically intended to encourage peak shaving and the distribution of loads throughout the day [17].

In the Flemish region, a major 2023 reform introduced power-based capacity tariffs for low and medium voltage users, which phased out traditional day/night energy rates in favor of charges based on the highest monthly quarter-hour peak recorded by digital meters. Under this Flemish model, all users must pay a minimum contribution corresponding to a 2.5 kW peak, a strategy specifically intended to incentivise peak shaving and discourage the simultaneous loading of the grid by rewarding users who distribute their consumption throughout the day. Furthermore, future market-based solutions could include regulated discounts on grid tariffs for users who accept non-guaranteed access, rather than paying activation fees for every event [17].

Portugal incentivises behavioral flexibility through ToU schemes with schedules that vary by geographical area, including three distinct options for the mainland grid. As of late 2024, the Portuguese regulator is performing a preliminary analysis to update these ToU schedules to ensure they reflect modern consumption and renewable generation patterns [14]. Besides, Portugal incentivises community energy sharing through a specific regime that exempts members from network charges related to upper-voltage levels [34].

In the Netherlands, while distribution-level ToU signals currently have limited application, the regulator is planning a national roll-out for all users by 2027 to better manage system peaks. Italy utilises a model that incorporates power-based components into its distribution tariffs and has implemented experimental initiatives allowing low-voltage consumers to access increased technically available capacity during off-peak periods [34].

For ECs, tariff structures are a primary determinant of the economic viability of energy sharing and local optimisation. One of the main expectations of ECs is to improve the efficiency of local networks, thus their tariff schemes should reflect this positive impact, provided it is measured and justified. These evolving tariff structures present ECs with the opportunity to maximise the financial benefits of individual and collective energy optimisation, decreasing overall system costs by aligning their production and consumption with grid conditions.

However, the transition toward complex power-based and granular ToU charges carries the risk of penalising community members who lack the automation or advanced energy management systems needed to shift their loads effectively. This topic also relates to a persistent concern regarding high technical entry costs, as the requirement for advanced metering, monitoring, and control infrastructure can be prohibitive for small-scale community projects [9, 15]. Moreover, regulators must carefully calibrate these schemes to prevent an unbalanced reduction in network tariffs for ECs, which could lead to higher charges for the remaining users, thereby shifting a disproportionate share of system costs onto those without access to community-led renewable resources.

Flexible Connection Agreements

In the four studied regions, FCAs function as a critical acceleration and regulatory transition mechanism, allowing ECs to bypass the physical saturation of distribution grids. Instead of

waiting years for traditional infrastructure reinforcements. ECs utilise FCAs to obtain immediate grid access by agreeing to conditions that limit or control their electricity injection and withdrawal during periods of system stress. In return, DSOs enable the integration of more renewable energy resources and collective self-consumers, increasing local network efficiency and moving towards their sustainability goals, while avoiding or deferring expensive infrastructure upgrades [14].

In Flanders, the DSO utilises the Fall-back Flex mechanism, which acts as a temporary regulatory bridge providing immediate grid access in congested zones in exchange for mandatory power modulation via telecontrol boxes until a permanent legislative framework is finalised [17]. The Netherlands maintains a highly structured framework offering two distinct FCA variants, fully flexible connections where users pay for monthly peaks rather than contracted capacity and timeslot agreements that provide capacity during specific windows, both of which are uniquely integrated with cost-reflective network tariff discounts. Additionally, the previously mentioned CLC-A and CLC-T are available through GOPACS. In Portugal, the implementation reached a significant regulatory milestone on January 21, 2025, with the approval of general conditions that oblige DSOs to offer flexible connections to producers and storage facilities whenever providing firm capacity is not technically feasible. Meanwhile, in Italy, DSOs are deploying these agreements through pilot initiatives like EDGE and RomeFlex, treating them as strategic “no-network solutions” that allow grid operators to potentially halve necessary infrastructure investments by substituting physical upgrades with digitalised software technology and power modulation [14].

For ECs, these agreements provide a strategic opportunity for active asset management, transforming technical flexibility into economic value through anticipated operational revenue or direct discounts on network usage charges. However, FCAs also impose rigorous technological requirements, forcing communities to invest in advanced monitoring infrastructure, such as second-generation (2G) smart meters and telecontrol devices, so that DSOs can verify compliance with power restrictions in real-time.

Local Flexibility Markets

• Existing Markets and Platforms

The implementation of LFMs across these regions reveals a significant disparity in maturity levels, with the Netherlands operating a fully established national framework while Portugal, Italy, and Belgium remain in the pilot and experimental phases. The Netherlands features the most advanced framework through the GOPACS platform, a unique national coordination system collectively owned by the TSO (TenneT) and all DSOs [14]. Unlike early-stage pilots, GOPACS is a fully operational scheme integrated directly with established wholesale intraday trading platforms ETPA and EPEX SPOT. A new cooperation with Nord Pool has been announced; thus, in 2026, all three Nominated Electricity Market Operators (NEMOs) will be connected to GOPACS. LFM initiatives in Portugal, Italy, and Flanders are currently navigating various pilot and experimental stages to test the technical and economic feasibility of utilising DERs for distribution grid support. In Portugal, the DSO E-REDES launched the FIRMe project in 2023, utilising the Piclo Flex platform to conduct auctions across multiple districts [18]. Italy employs a decentralised regulatory sandbox approach through projects such as EDGE, which also utilises Piclo Flex for forward auctions, and the RomeFlex and MiNDFlex initiatives, which operate via a dedicated section of the national GME platform [16]. Meanwhile, the Flanders region of Belgium conducts seasonal market tests via the NODES platform, where the DSO Fluvius fosters the integration of small-scale assets [17].

The operation of LFM across Portugal, the Netherlands, Italy, and Belgium is characterised by a mix of long-term reservation auctions and short-term activation mechanisms, though they largely converge on a pay-as-bid pricing methodology. In Portugal, Italy, and Belgium, the DSO acts as the sole buyer of flexibility, procuring services directly from service providers to resolve local grid issues rather than facilitating a peer-to-peer exchange. These regions frequently employ long-term capacity reservation through forward auctions (ranging from seasonal contracts in Italy's EDGE to two-year bilateral agreements in Portugal), where providers are remunerated for both their standing availability and the actual utilisation of their flexibility [18]. Italy's Rome-Flex and MiNDFlex specifically utilise a hybrid structure that couples these long-term reservation auctions with short-term day-ahead and intraday spot markets to ensure activations are selected in the most cost-effective manner [14, 16]. Similarly, the Flanders pilot tests a tiered product range, covering reservation guarantees and near-real-time volume adjustments [17]. In contrast, the Netherlands (GOPACS) operates with a unique coordination model that focuses on matching buying and selling bids from different market participants across the national grid. When a Dutch system operator identifies a local bottleneck, it issues a "buy order" for flexibility in that area. GOPACS then automatically matches this with a corresponding "sell order" outside the congested zone to maintain overall system balance while resolving the local issue. Compensation is provided by the Dutch grid operators, who pay for the spread between matched bids. Similarly to the other regions, participants are also compensated for capacity reservation, besides activation [14].

• Technical and Product Specifications

Despite the common goal of mitigating congestion and voltage deviations through active power regulation, flexibility products across these regions exhibit significant design heterogeneity. In Portugal, the DSO utilises forward-looking products tailored to specific grid states: Restore (post-failure), Dynamic (planned maintenance), and Secure (expected congestion) [18]. Conversely, Flanders defines products by their temporal horizon: MaxUsage functions as a long-term capacity limit, ShortFlex enables near-real-time volume adjustments, and LongFlex serves as a reservation product to guarantee availability in the ShortFlex market [17]. The Netherlands operates a similarly temporal model through GOPACS, utilising Capacity Limitation for day-ahead planning, Redispatch for intraday needs, and Mandatory Bidding to ensure long-term capacity for Redispatch [9]. Italy utilises a combination of both frameworks to design their products, mostly focused on the temporal aspect, but distinguishing between Standard and Emergency services [14, 16].

In order to quantify the electricity production or consumption shifted by any BSP, a baseline must be established. In the Dutch GOPACS platform, baseline verification is uniquely bypassed because accepted bids are treated as modifications to a market operator's commercial schedule, allowing for validation by comparing actual delivery directly against the updated commercial program [14]. Conversely, the pilot initiatives in Portugal, Italy, and the Flanders region rely on various historical data methodologies, typically requiring advanced metering infrastructure capable of recording 15-minute intervals to establish reference profiles. In particular, Portugal's FIRMe project utilises a "Mean X-in-Y" methodology, averaging similar recent days while excluding extremes, corrected by the power flow measured in the hours immediately preceding activation [18]. Similarly, Italy's EDGE project has recently evolved to offer providers a choice between three methods: historical averages with additive or multiplicative adjustments, or a method based purely on the two hours preceding activation, which is designed to better account for the volatility of weather-dependent renewables [14, 16].

The technical barriers to entry are largely determined by minimum bid quantities and the sophistication of the required monitoring equipment. Technical entry requirements for LFMs vary significantly across Europe. In the Netherlands, the GOPACS system generally maintains a higher threshold with a minimum bid size of 100 kW. Conversely, pilot initiatives in other regions are progressively lowering thresholds to accommodate smaller distributed resources [14]. For instance, Italy's RomeFlex and MiNDFlex projects allow bids as low as 3 kW, while the EDGE pilot has recently reduced its minimum bid quantity from 100 kW to 50 kW for 2026 activities to better integrate smaller aggregated units [21]. Portugal's FIRMe project has standardised a 10 kW aggregated minimum across all voltage levels, while Flanders has avoided strict capacity mandates, encouraging the inclusion of small-scale DERs [14]. Regarding hardware, all four regions require advanced metering infrastructure, specifically 2G smart meters or digital AMR meters capable of recording usage in 15-minute intervals, which is essential for establishing baselines and verifying service delivery. Additionally, all four regions impose rigorous proximity constraints. Assets must be electrically connected to specific nodes within defined "Flexibility Perimeters" to be suitable for resolving local grid stress [15]. For example, in GOPACS, orders are tied to specific grid-connection European Article Number (EAN) codes to ensure that power adjustments occur exactly where the bottleneck is located [14].

The necessity for an aggregator often depends on the user type and the specific market. In Italy, RomeFlex and MiNDFlex projects mandate aggregation for residential users while allowing commercial and industrial entities to participate directly if they meet the required power levels. Whilst, in the Netherlands, representation through a Congestion Service Provider (CSP) is mandatory for all products, except for capacity limitation contracts with time, which are an agreement in which the user commits to reduce consumption or generation at fixed, pre-defined moments [9]. In all other markets and/or products, aggregation is not necessary, but is allowed to fulfill minimum capacity requirements [14].

2.3.2 Drivers and barriers

• Main Drivers for EC participation

After analyzing all available products and requirements, it is clear that being part of an EC increases the opportunity to participate in LFMs, since these initiatives tend to aggregate multiple DERs in a restricted location. This aggregation allows small-scale distributed assets to meet minimum capacity and/or bid requirements set by DSOs, in Portugal, Italy, and the Netherlands.

A significant economic driver is the dual remuneration structure found in both GOPACS and the pilot LFMs, which provides communities with availability payments for reserving capacity in advance and utilisation fees for the energy effectively delivered during grid stress. Furthermore, in certain products designs, where participants are compensated only for activation, ECs have the freedom to accept or decline flexibility requests without penalty, allowing them to balance their grid contributions with their members' needs.

Ultimately, an additional driver for participation on LFMs is related to social and environmental benefits. By definition, the primary objective of ECs is the provision of environmental, economic, or social benefits to its members, partners, or shareholders or to the local areas in which it operates. The participation in LFMs aligns with these goals by maximising the local use of renewable energy and improving overall system efficiency for the local area.

The successful participation of ECs in LFM is strengthened by the integration of certain flexible assets, management systems, and communication protocols. Certain DERs owned by ECs have increased potential for unlocking flexibility, including Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs), Heat Pumps (HPs), and Electrical Vehicles (EVs) charging stations. Incorporating such assets gives ECs the opportunity to guarantee availability for flexibility services, while granting individual optimisation for their members at the same time (leveraging both explicit and implicit flexibility mechanisms) [15]. Effective management of these assets requires advanced control systems, including Model Predictive Control (MPC) strategies. To replace inefficient manual communication methods, there is a documented shift toward Application Programming Interface (API)-based automated activation and the adoption of standardised communication protocols such as MODBUS-TCP and IEC 61850 to ensure reliable, real-time dispatch. These technological layers are integrated via Home Energy Management Systems (HEMSs) and Distributed Energy Resource Management Systems (DERMSs), which leverage Internet of Things (IoT) architectures to coordinate distributed loads while providing DSOs with the necessary grid observability [14].

• Main Barriers for EC participation

The participation of ECs in LFM is fundamentally hindered by topological and locational constraints, as distribution services are inherently locational, requiring resources to be connected to specific electrical nodes, functional to resolving local grid stress. Many community assets are disqualified during preliminary checks due to a lack of Point of Delivery (PoD) correspondence, meaning that while they may be physically located near a congested area, they are electrically unsuitable for resolving the specific network issue. This challenge is compounded by regulatory fragmentation, characterised by a lack of consistent national or EU-level regulatory references, which creates high levels of uncertainty for communities attempting to develop reliable business models [9].

High technical entry costs present another major hurdle, as the requirement to deploy expensive field-level instrumentation, advanced metering systems (such as 2G smart meters), and automated control infrastructure is often prohibitive for small-scale community resources. This technological gap is particularly acute for assets connected to LV grids, where the lack of remote control and communication systems makes real-time observability and dispatching difficult. Closely related to these technical barriers is the complexity and fear of operational disruption, as community members express significant concerns that power modulation might negatively impact their domestic or industrial processes. These operational fears are intensified by the risk of severe financial penalties [14]. In mature markets like the Netherlands, failing to meet a setpoint can result in the loss of an entire month's earnings, a risk level that discourages small-scale community participation.

Baseline and revenue uncertainty further inhibit EC involvement, as existing historical baseline methodologies often fail to accurately reflect the undisturbed load profile of weather-dependent renewables like solar PV or highly variable loads like EV charging [17]. This leads to settlement errors and, combined with the unpredictable frequency of activations, creates a volatile revenue stream that makes it difficult for communities to justify the initial costs of participation.

Unlocking the full potential of ECs in LFM will depend on harmonisation. The forthcoming Network Code on Demand Response (NC DR) aims to establish Union-wide standards for aggregation models, baselining, and TSO-DSO coordination. This is expected to provide the regulatory foundation needed to move from isolated pilots to a scalable, pan-European flexibility

landscape [9].

2.4 Provision for TSO-level services

2.4.1 Frequency Ancillary services (Balancing)

System frequency control operates across multiple temporal layers, each characterised by distinct response times and operational objectives. By modulating active power from controllable resources, the power system maintains frequency within predefined limits following disturbances.

In low-inertia systems, FFR provides the earliest active power response, acting within hundreds of milliseconds to a few seconds after a frequency threshold is breached to arrest rapid frequency deviations. This is followed by FCR, which constitutes the primary stabilising mechanism and responds automatically and locally within seconds. If frequency is not restored within the acceptable range, Frequency Restoration Reserves (FRR) are activated to return frequency to its nominal value of 50 Hz, either automatically (aFRR) or manually (mFRR), with activation typically ranging from tens of seconds to several minutes [3, 36].

Together, FFR, FCR, FRR, and RR form a hierarchical set of frequency-related services that must remain available to TSOs to manage system disturbances and ensure secure operation. While traditionally procured at transmission level, frequency balancing increasingly involves distribution-connected flexibility resources, reflecting the growing role of DERs and ECs in supporting system-wide frequency control in decentralised power systems.

The dynamic sequence of frequency regulation is illustrated conceptually in 2.1, where full restoration typically occurs within 15 minutes following a disturbance [11]. Immediately after an incident, the following sequence is observed [1]:

1. Local primary response: Generating units react autonomously to frequency deviations through their governor systems, initiating FCR activation within seconds;
2. Transition to FRR: Once the primary response stabilises the deviation, aFRR is activated (from 30 seconds onward) to steer frequency back toward 50 Hz, gradually replacing FCR;
3. Manual tertiary activation: If aFRR activation is sustained or insufficient, mFRR is deployed by the responsible TSO. Activation typically begins within 5 minutes and may continue for extended periods depending on market arrangements and the severity of the event.

Next, each of these services is described in detail, focusing on their technical and market characteristics in the U2Demo pilot countries.

FFR

FFR is a balancing service designed to rapidly arrest frequency deviations following large disturbances, particularly in low-inertia power systems. It provides an ultra-fast active power response, typically within a few hundred milliseconds to a few seconds after a predefined frequency threshold is breached, thereby stabilising frequency before conventional FCR is fully activated. Due to their fast controllability and response times, inverter-based resources such as battery energy storage systems and aggregated DER are particularly well suited to provide

Figure 2.1 – Frequency ancillary services (balancing) according to the system envisaged by ENTSO-E [37]

Table 2.1 – FFR main characteristics

Country	Exists	Procurement	Min. Bid Size	Activation Trigger	Full Activation Time	Min. Duration	Typical Eligible Assets
Portugal	X	–	–	–	–	–	–
Belgium	X	–	–	–	–	–	–
Italy	yes (Pilot)	Market-based	5 MW	Proportional to frequency variations and/or triggered by a setpoint	< 1 s	30 s	BESS, Demand Response
Netherlands	X	–	–	–	–	–	–

FFR, compared to traditional synchronous generation. In the following Table 2.1 are presented the main specifications of the FFR service within the pilots' countries in U2Demo.

In Italy, the National Regulatory Authority (ARERA) [38] approved a pilot project for the provision of Fast Reserve in June 2020 (Resolution 200/2020/R/eel). This service complements existing frequency control mechanisms and is defined as a bidirectional reserve, providing both upward and downward regulation. It delivers a continuous and automatic active power response proportional to frequency deviations, with full activation required within one second of the triggering event.

In the Nordic power system, FFR is designed with technical characteristics that strongly facilitate the participation of small-scale and aggregated DERs. The service is upward-only, autonomously triggered at low-frequency thresholds (typically around 49.7 Hz), and requires full activation within approximately 0.7 to 1.3 seconds, depending on the product variant. Activation durations are short (typically 5–30 seconds), minimum bid sizes are low (down to 1 MW with aggregation explicitly allowed), and activation occurs only during rare disturbance events [39]. These features limit energy delivery requirements and make Nordic FFR particularly well suited for batteries, demand response, and energy community assets.

FCR

FCR forms the foundation of the automatic frequency-control hierarchy in the European synchronous areas. Its primary function is to contain frequency deviations immediately after a disturbance, thereby preventing deterioration of system stability. FCR acts locally and automatically, being activated directly by frequency deviations measured at the providing unit, in accordance with a predefined droop characteristic [1]. When a sudden imbalance occurs, such as a generation outage or a rapid demand variation, FCR stabilises the frequency deviation within seconds by proportionally adjusting active power output, providing the time needed for slower reserves (FRR, RR) to activate.

ENTSO-E defines FCR as a mandatory capability for each synchronous area to maintain instantaneous system equilibrium. In accordance with the System Operation Guideline, FCR must be fully activated within 30 seconds, regardless of the disturbance magnitude [1]. Its activation behaviour follows the Frequency Containment Process (FCP), which enforces a monotonic proportional response to frequency deviations, full activation at the maximum steady-state deviation, and progressive relief by Frequency Restoration Reserves as frequency is restored.

From the perspective of Energy Communities and distributed energy resources, several characteristics of FCR are particularly relevant. First, FCR is a continuous availability service, requiring permanent readiness to respond. This creates challenges for energy-constrained technologies such as batteries, especially when frequency deviations persist for extended durations. At the same time, the predictable availability requirements and capacity-based remuneration structure make FCR an attractive service for aggregated DER portfolios capable of coordinating availability across multiple assets.

Second, national procurement frameworks and minimum bid sizes play a decisive role in determining access to FCR markets. Across Europe, procurement structures range from mandatory provision by centralised generators to market-based and hybrid schemes that allow competitive procurement of FCR capacity. In countries applying hybrid or market-based models, aggregation of loads, batteries, and mixed DER portfolios is explicitly permitted, enabling Energy Communities to participate through aggregators. Conversely, higher minimum bid sizes and generator-only eligibility criteria continue to limit participation in some jurisdictions.

Technical performance requirements also influence DER participation. Criteria related to frequency measurement accuracy, deadband, droop settings, and ramping behaviour were historically designed for synchronous generation. While the standard 30-second full activation requirement is generally compatible with most inverter-based resources, tighter accuracy requirements and faster ramping constraints increase compliance complexity for small-scale DERs. Nevertheless, advances in power electronics and digital control increasingly enable aggregated DER portfolios to meet these requirements. The frequency quality defining parameters of the synchronous areas in Central Europe, the UK, and Nordic countries are detailed in Table 2.3, and the control behaviour is depicted in Figure 2.2, which illustrates the relationship between frequency deviation, deadband, droop, and full activation.

Finally, FCR is fundamentally a capacity-based product, with activation energy settled according to national rules, which may result in positive, zero, or negative prices depending on system conditions [11]. Cost allocation mechanisms vary across Member States, with capacity costs borne by grid users, BRPs, or a combination of both[40]. For ECs, this capacity-oriented re-

Figure 2.2 – Implications of accuracy requirements – simplified control scheme [1]

muneration provides predictable revenues but requires careful coordination with other asset uses, such as self-consumption and local flexibility provision. Overall, FCR represents a stable but regulation-dependent entry point for EC participation in TSO-level balancing services, strongly shaped by national market design, aggregation rules, and technical prequalification requirements.

In the Table 2.2 are shown the FCR product design characteristics per pilot country, showing the differences mentioned above.

Table 2.2 – Summary of FCR product design per country.

	Portugal	Belgium	Italy	Netherlands
Procurement schemes for capacity products	Mandatory	Hybrid ⁽¹⁾ [41]	Hybrid	Hybrid ⁽¹⁾
Minimum bid size requirements	1 MW	>1 MW ⁽²⁾	1 MW ⁽³⁾	>1 MW ⁽²⁾
Time-frame (capacity product resolution)	Not applicable (mandatory)	4 hours (daily procurement) [41]	4 hours (daily procurement)	4 hours (daily procurement) [42]
Activation time (from 0 to full activation) [11]	30 s	30 s	30 s [43]	30 s [42]
Capacity Providers	Generators only	Generators, loads, batteries	Generators, loads, batteries	Generators, loads, batteries
Energy Providers	Same as capacity	Same as capacity	Same as capacity	Same as capacity

⁽¹⁾ FCR capacity in Belgium and the Netherlands is procured through competitive markets to fulfil mandatory system requirements, while activation (energy) is automatic and therefore mandatory in all countries.

⁽²⁾ In accordance with SO GL [11](Annex VI "Limits and requirements for the exchange of FCR").

⁽³⁾ Differences between mandatory and voluntary offers.

aFRR

aFRR constitutes the first layer of the Frequency Restoration Process (FRP), acting after the initial frequency containment provided by FCR. Its primary function is to restore the Frequency Restoration Control Error (FRCE) towards zero by continuously adjusting active power output from prequalified units and aggregated portfolios [44]. Activation is automatic, closed-loop, and quasi-continuous, typically updated every few seconds through the TSOs LFC and Automatic Generation Control (AGC) systems.

According to the System Operation Guideline, aFRR is procured as a capacity product and/or an energy product, depending on the national implementation. Procurement arrangements vary across Member States and include mandatory, market-based, and hybrid schemes. These design choices have a direct impact on the accessibility of aFRR markets for Energy Communities and DER aggregators. Table 2.4 summarises the procurement regimes adopted in the several

Table 2.3 – Minimum accuracy of frequency measurement [3]

Minimum accuracy of frequency measurement	Central Europe	UK	Nordic Countries
Δf_{\max}	± 500 mHz	± 200 mHz	± 100 mHz
maximum instantaneous frequency deviation	800 mHz	800 mHz	1000 mHz
maximum steady-state frequency deviation	200 mHz	500 mHz	500 mHz
time to recover frequency	not used	1 min	not used
frequency recovery range	not used	± 500 mHz	not used
time to restore frequency	15 min	15 min	15 min
frequency restoration range	not used	± 200 mHz	± 100 mHz
alert state trigger time	5 min	10 min	5 min

U2Demo pilots countries.

Design parameters are particularly relevant for DER participation. Minimum bid sizes define the smallest controllable reserve block and have been progressively reduced in several Member States, enabling aggregation of smaller DER portfolios. Product time resolution, typically 15 minutes, influences operational flexibility and portfolio optimisation. Activation requirements must comply with ENTSO-E timelines, with national implementations allowing full activation within a few minutes up to the Time to Restore Frequency (15 minutes), favouring fast and controllable assets.

Eligibility rules remain a key barrier in some countries where aFRR provision is restricted to large or synchronous generators. In contrast, jurisdictions that allow loads, batteries, and aggregated mixed portfolios (see Table 2.4) demonstrate more advanced integration of distributed flexibility. Overall, aFRR offers significant potential for EC and DER participation, but its practical accessibility remains highly dependent on national procurement design and aggregation frameworks.

mFRR

mFRR represents the manually activated component of the FRP, used when automatic reserves (aFRR) are insufficient, saturated, or require relief after sustained activation. Unlike aFRR, which is activated continuously via the Load-Frequency Control system, mFRR is typically triggered through explicit TSO dispatch, providing a flexible and dispatchable reserve to restore system balance and release automatic reserves for subsequent disturbances [1], [11].

The primary role of mFRR is to address persistent imbalances and congestion after frequency has been stabilised, and before BRP can rebalance their positions. Activation may occur in response to long-lasting imbalances, anticipated system stress, or scarcity of faster reserves. Although mFRR activation is executed through discrete dispatch orders, successive activations may result in sustained power delivery over extended periods.

In accordance with the System Operation Guideline, mFRR must respect harmonised FRP performance requirements, notably that the FRR Full Activation Time does not exceed the Time to Restore Frequency (15 minutes). Activation is centrally controlled by the TSO, either through direct dispatch or scheduled activation, depending on the national market framework. Many

Table 2.4 – Summary of aFRR product design per country.

	Portugal	Belgium	Italy	Netherlands
Procurement schemes for energy product	Market-based	Hybrid [45]	Market-based	Hybrid
Minimum bid size requirements (capacity)	1 MW [46]	5 MW	1 MW	1 MW
Minimum bid size requirements (energy)	1 MW	1 MW	1 MW [47]	1 MW
Time-frame (capacity product resolution)	15 min	15 min	15 min	15 min
Time-frame (energy product resolution)	15 min	15 min	15 min	15 min
Activation time (from 0 to full activation)	30 s	< 5 min	< 5 min	5 min < x ≤ 15 min ⁽¹⁾
Capacity Providers	Generators only ⁽⁵⁾	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregated (mixed portfolios) ⁽²⁾	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregated (mixed portfolios) ⁽²⁾	Generators, batteries, aggregated (mixed portfolios) ⁽⁵⁾
Energy Providers	Generators, aggregated (storage and controllable loads) ⁽⁶⁾	Same as capacity	Same as capacity	Same as capacity

⁽¹⁾ 7% of bid volume per minute (up and down).

⁽²⁾ Capacity provision is selective and availability-driven; energy provision is broader and more flexible.

⁽³⁾ Both capacity and energy markets are clearly defined and explicitly open to multiple asset types, including demand response.

⁽⁴⁾ Capacity provision remains selective; energy provision is more permissive and closely integrated into the self-dispatching model.

⁽⁵⁾ Participation by loads, storage, or aggregators in aFRR capacity provision is incipient and largely dependent on pilot projects or future regulatory developments.

⁽⁶⁾ The Portuguese framework increasingly recognises the role of aggregation as an enabler for non-traditional resources to participate in balancing energy markets, even if full market opening is still evolving.

European systems use pay-as-bid or marginal pricing for activation energy, depending on national market rules.

From an Energy Community and DER perspective, several design aspects of mFRR are particularly relevant. mFRR typically requires slower but sustained activation, often lasting tens of minutes to several hours, which favours resources with sufficient energy capacity or flexible demand profiles. Procurement structures vary across Europe and include market-based, mandatory, and hybrid models, with mFRR generally procured as both a capacity (availability) and an energy (activation) product. Cost recovery schemes also differ, with capacity and energy costs allocated to grid users, BRPs, or a combination of both [40], [1].

Minimum bid sizes and product time resolution strongly influence DER participation. Lower bid thresholds and explicit aggregation provisions enable Energy Communities and DER aggregators to participate, whereas higher thresholds tend to favour conventional generation. In contrast to FCR and aFRR, mFRR activation profiles are generally compatible with a wider range of distributed assets, including loads, batteries, pumped storage, and mixed portfolios [40].

Table 2.5 summarises the characteristics and limits for mFRR in U2Demo demonstrator countries.

Table 2.5 – Summary of mFRR product design per country.

	Portugal	Belgium	Italy	Netherlands
Procurement schemes for capacity product	Hybrid	Market-based	Market-based	Market-based
Procurement schemes for energy product	Market-based	Market-based	Market-based	Market-based
Minimum bid size requirements (capacity)	1 MW	1 MW	1 MW [47]	1 MW
Minimum bid size requirements (energy)	1 MW	1 MW [7]	1 MW	1 MW [48]
Time-frame (capacity product resolution)	15 min [49]	4 Hours [50]	Hourly / Multi-hour blocks	4 Hours
Time-frame (energy product resolution)	15 min	15 min	15 min	15 min[48]
Activation time (from 0 to full activation)	12.5 min	12.5 min	12.5 min [47]	12.5 min
Capacity Providers	Generators, PHS, loads, batteries, aggregators	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregators	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregators	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregators
Energy Providers	Generators, PHS, loads, batteries, aggregators	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregators	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregators	Generators, loads, batteries, aggregators

RR

RR constitute the highest-time-scale layer of balancing reserves within the European frequency-control hierarchy. Their primary function is to replace previously activated FRR and FCR,

thereby restoring the availability of faster-response reserves and ensuring system preparedness following sustained disturbances. The Reserve Replacement Process (RRP) operates after frequency has been stabilised and addresses longer-lasting system imbalances [1]. RR are characterised by relatively long activation times, typically ranging from approximately 15 minutes to several hours, and are generally activated manually or semi-automatically. They are intended to manage prolonged imbalances where continued reliance on aFRR or mFRR alone could compromise operational security or compliance with the Time to Restore Frequency (TtRF) requirements defined in the European regulatory framework [1], [11].

Historically, the exchange and activation of RR balancing energy at European level were enabled through the TERRE project, implemented under the Electricity Balancing Guideline. The TERRE project operationalised the LIBRA platform, facilitating the exchange of a standardised RR product and supporting cross-border coordination and system security [51], [7]. Recent EU regulatory developments, most notably Regulation (EU) 2019/943 as amended by Regulation (EU) 2024/1747 [52], which introduced a 30-minute cross-zonal intraday gate closure time, have rendered the RR process incompatible with updated market timing constraints. Due to the long Full Activation Time associated with RR products, further adaptation would overlap with mFRR processes and reduce market liquidity. As a result, the TERRE platform ceased operations by the end of 2025, and the reserve replacement process will be progressively discontinued [53].

Following the termination of TERRE, none of the U2Demo demonstrator countries operate a national RR product as a standalone balancing service. The system functions historically fulfilled by RR are instead addressed through a combination of sustained mFRR activation, national dispatching arrangements, and enhanced coordination between balancing and intraday markets. Consequently, while RR remains formally defined within the European balancing architecture, its practical role has been significantly reduced and functionally absorbed by evolving mFRR-based mechanisms rather than maintained as a distinct market product. From an Energy Community perspective, future participation in long-duration balancing is more likely to emerge through evolving mFRR products and aggregation-based mechanisms rather than through the reintroduction of a dedicated RR market layer.

2.4.2 Black Start and System Restoration

Black-start services are essential for re-energising the electricity system following a total or partial blackout, enabling system operators to initiate system restoration without relying on an external electricity supply. In the European framework, black start capability is formally defined as “*the capability of recovery of a power-generating module from a total shutdown through a dedicated auxiliary power source without any electrical energy supply external to the power-generating facility*” [54]. This capability forms a key component of the System Defence and Restoration Plans mandated by the Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/941 on risk preparedness [55]. Traditionally, European TSOs have relied on a transmission-led restoration strategy, in which large synchronous generating units or, in specific cases, interconnectors, provide black-start capability. These units must be able to start without an external power supply, energise adjacent transmission corridors, and form an initial restoration island where load and generation can be balanced. Once a stable island is in operation, the TSO progressively re-energises the wider transmission network to supply other generators, eventually synchronising multiple islands and restoring demand until full system recovery is achieved. System restoration across Europe is carried out in close coordination among TSOs, DSOs, and relevant grid users, as required by Regulation (EU) 2017/2196 [56]. These actors follow predefined roles and

procedures for communication, re-energisation, and load management using resilient and secure channels designed to withstand major system disturbances. The ongoing transformation of the power system, characterised by high shares of inverter-based renewable generation, the deployment of DERs, and advanced digital energy management systems, is driving a strategic shift. This is supported by national analyses, including the National Grid ESO's 2022 study [4] on non-traditional technologies, which indicates that the future European restoration strategy will increasingly depend on distributed, digitalised, and modular resources. This evolution necessitates a more flexible and decentralised approach to black-start and system restoration. In this context, new actors such as distributed storage, grid-forming inverter-based generation, demand-side flexibility, microgrids, and Energy Communities are expected to play an expanding role in supporting resilience and restoration, complementing the capabilities of traditional black-start providers.

Conceptual Role of Energy Communities in System Restoration

ECs aggregate DERs, flexible loads, and local storage systems within the LV distribution grid. While historically not considered as actors in system restoration, their increasing technical sophistication, especially through the deployment of inverter-based generation, distributed storage, and advanced control systems, positions them as potential contributors to local black-start and early-stage restoration processes.

The ability of an EC to provide black-start capability depends on the composition and controllability of its local DER assets. Several types of resources commonly found in ECs may support restoration tasks:

1. **BESS.** BESSs represent the most technically suitable resource for providing black-start capability within ECs. Their instantaneous availability, high power controllability, and ability to operate in grid-forming mode allow them to establish stable voltage and frequency references in a de-energised network. BESS can supply the initial energisation currents required to start local feeders, absorb sudden fluctuations in load pick-up, and stabilise islanded operation during the early phases of restoration. When appropriately sized and equipped with advanced inverter controls, BESS can serve as the foundational element enabling ECs to initiate and sustain local black-start sequences.
2. **PV Installations with Grid-Forming Inverters.** Although PV systems traditionally rely on grid-following inverters that cannot energise a dead network, the deployment of grid-forming inverter technologies significantly expands their role in black-start support. Grid-forming, virtual synchronous machine (VSM), or droop-controlled inverters allow PV installations to operate autonomously in island mode, contribute to setting local voltage and frequency, and coordinate with other DER during load pick-up. While PV generation alone is inherently variable, its combination with BESS provides a stable and sustainable solution for prolonged restoration, particularly in ECs with high solar penetration.
3. **Hybrid Renewable - Storage Systems.** Hybrid systems combining renewable generation, such as PV or wind power, with storage are particularly effective in supporting black-start operations. These systems offer enhanced stability due to the complementary characteristics of renewable generation and fast-responding storage, enabling ride-through support, smoothing of generation variability, and more flexible dispatch. Their ability to maintain continuous operation under fluctuating conditions makes hybrid RES storage configurations an excellent backbone for providing reliable and resilient black-start services within ECs.

4. **Flexible Loads and Demand Response** Flexible loads and demand response mechanisms play a role in supporting black-start sequences by helping to maintain the delicate balance between generation and consumption during the early stages of network re-energisation. By modulating or temporarily reducing demand, these resources enable a staggered and controlled load pick-up strategy, preventing frequency dips or voltage instability. Additionally, demand response systems can prioritise essential services such as hospitals, telecommunications, and community infrastructure ensuring that limited restoration power is directed where it is most needed. This load management flexibility significantly enhances the operability and resilience of EC-led restoration efforts.
5. **Electric Vehicles and V2G-Enabled Chargers** EVs equipped with vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology present an emerging but increasingly promising resource for black-start support. When aggregated within Energy Communities, V2G-capable EVs can act as a dispersed storage network, providing short-term balancing, voltage support, and supplementary energisation capacity during the formation of local restoration islands. Although their deployment for black-start applications is still at an early stage, the rapid growth of EV adoption and smart charging infrastructure suggests that V2G systems may soon become a valuable component of decentralised black-start architectures at the distribution level.

Key Technical Requirements for Black-Start Provision

Providing Black-Start (BS) capability is one of the most technically demanding ancillary services in the power system. Historically delivered by large synchronous power plants, black-start requires a combination of robust operational characteristics, autonomous control capabilities, and the ability to stabilise and energise parts of the grid without any external power supply. BS providers must comply with stringent technical criteria designed to ensure reliable system energisation from a black-grid condition. These requirements typically stem from system operators' restoration plans and cover several essential capabilities. The fundamental procedures [4, 57] of a successful restoration include the self-start of BS resources, the energisation of part of the transmission network, and the restoration of loads. Accordingly, a generation source should meet the following criteria to qualify as a BS provider.

1. **Self-starting.** A generation site is considered self-starting if the power required to start can be met independently of the wider network within a timescale specified by the system operator. The Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/2196 [8] mandates that each TSO must develop a restoration plan, which includes specific timelines for the availability of black start services, tailored to their synchronous area. For instance, in the GB system, BS resources are required to be able to energise part of the national transmission network or the distribution system within 2 hours of receiving the instruction.
2. **Grid-forming.** The grid-forming capability of a BS resource means it can establish a voltage reference and control the voltage and frequency of the section of the system to be restored independently. This is a critical ability that inverter-based resources in ECs must replicate to participate effectively.
3. **Reactive power and voltage control.** A BS resource must be capable of balancing reactive power and regulating voltages in the restored system. This is essential for managing the high reactive power demand when energising long transmission lines. In GB, the minimum absorption capability of a generating plant connected at 400 kV or 275 kV is typically specified in terms of MVar capacity.
4. **Block loading.** The capability to connect a certain amount of demand while maintaining frequency and voltage stability, such as 35–50 MW in GB or 10 MW in Belgium.

5. **Active power and frequency control.** The necessity to rapidly adjust active power output to manage frequency fluctuations. NGESO in GB requires frequency to remain between 47.5–52 Hz during block loading, while Elia specifies 49–52 Hz.
6. **Availability and Duration:** High availability of power is needed for readiness. In GB, backup fuel or energy management is required for availability at least 90% of the year and operation for three to seven days.

DERs Participating in a Black Start

DERs, including converter-connected renewables, battery energy storage systems, and flexible assets such as electric vehicles, present both opportunities and constraints for black-start and early-stage system restoration. Their increasing deployment at the distribution level enables potential contributions to localised restoration and islanded operation.

Converter-connected DERs offer fast activation, rapid ramping, and low auxiliary power requirements, making them suitable for early energisation of local networks. However, their use is limited by weather-dependent availability, predominantly grid-following control strategies, restricted overcurrent capability during energisation, and the need for coordinated control to ensure stable islanded operation and secure resynchronisation. Table 2.6 summarises the relative suitability of Energy Community DER technologies for black-start provision.

Table 2.6 – Qualitative assessment of DER participation in black-start processes [4]

Capability	BESS	PV	EV
Self-starting	Battery storage sites are typically equipped with on-site uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) to energise auxiliaries. Provided sufficient state of charge is available at the time of shutdown, BESS can restore and self-start locally.	During daylight hours, grid-connected solar installations can rapidly self-start once inverter controls are enabled, subject to irradiance availability.	EVs are technically capable of self-starting; however, limited battery capacity per unit and low penetration currently make this infeasible for meaningful grid re-energisation.
Grid forming	Battery storage installations are generally designed for parallel operation and therefore predominantly use grid-following inverters, synchronising to an existing voltage reference rather than forming one.	Most PV installations connect via grid-following inverters that require an external voltage signal and therefore cannot initiate black-start without control upgrades.	EVs are not expected to provide grid-forming capability under current inverter designs.

Capability	BESS	PV	EV
Network energisation and reactive power	BESS can support network energisation by balancing supply and demand and stabilising voltage and frequency. With four-quadrant operation, battery inverters can absorb or supply reactive power rapidly, enabling compensation during islanded operation and formation of power islands.	Network energisation is technically achievable with upgraded control and protection schemes. PV inverters possess reactive power capability and can absorb or inject reactive power once energised.	Given limited deployment and inverter sizing close to battery capacity, EVs are unlikely to energise network sections or provide meaningful reactive power support.
Block loading	Battery storage can energise block loads up to its rated capacity and can modulate output or transition between charging and discharging modes to manage demand.	Restoration based on PV generation requires smaller block loads, as typical PV plant capacities are insufficient to meet conventional restoration block-loading requirements.	EVs with V2G capability could theoretically charge or discharge to support block loading, but current communication and control limitations prevent coordinated system operator interaction.
Frequency control	Battery storage can provide fast frequency response and voltage support through control settings, smoothing large frequency excursions. As BESS can act as both generation and load, coordinated control is required to avoid adverse interactions such as control “hunting”.	PV inverters inherently provide fast active power response and voltage regulation within their control limits.	EVs currently do not provide frequency control, as inverter functionality is not designed or deployed for this purpose due to cost and system complexity.
Availability and intermittency	Availability depends on state of charge; while the energy window may be limited, BESS often act as stabilising assets rather than continuous energy sources, charging and discharging dynamically during restoration. Plant size remains the primary limitation.	Solar output is intermittent and weather-dependent, with limited confidence in availability at the time of restoration despite short-term forecasting.	EV availability remains low due to limited deployment and small individual battery sizes, making aggregate contribution negligible before large-scale adoption.

2.4.3 EC-TSO Operational Validation and Demonstration pilots

This section provides an overview of existing real-life pilots and operational implementations where ECs and DERs have actively contributed to TSO services. It focuses on demonstrated cases of DER participation in balancing services (FCR, FFR, aFRR, mFRR, RR), as well as system restoration and black-start support, highlighting their operational feasibility, scalability, and relevance for future TSO–DSO coordination frameworks. The following examples illustrate operational implementations where energy communities and distributed energy resources have successfully provided balancing, restoration, and resilience services to TSOs, demonstrating both operational feasibility and mutual benefits for system operators and asset owners.

1) Balancing services: Energy-community / local DER pilots providing system services

- **UK - DER participation in FFR and Dynamic Containment (National Grid ESO).** In Great Britain, distributed battery systems and aggregated flexible resources participate in fast-acting frequency response services such as Dynamic Containment and FFR to help maintain system frequency stability. These services are part of National Grid ESO's balancing portfolio, enabling rapid response to frequency deviations and creating market opportunities for DER owners [58].
- **Europe - Aggregated DERs in RR, mFRR and aFRR via TERRE, MARI and PICASSO platforms.** The TERRE (RR), MARI (mFRR) and PICASSO (aFRR) platforms enable aggregated DERs to provide balancing services across multiple European TSOs through standardised, cross-border mechanisms. These platforms demonstrate large-scale DER integration into TSO balancing markets. TSOs gain access to a larger and more diverse flexibility pool and DER owners benefit from cross-border market access and increased asset utilisation [51, 59].
- **Nordic Countries - DERs and demand response for FCR-N and FFR (Finland, Sweden).** Energy communities and industrial DERs participate in Frequency Containment Reserve for Normal operation (FCR-N) through aggregation. It improves frequency stability in low-inertia systems while enabling DER owners to monetise flexibility without compromising local energy objectives [60, 61, 62].
- **Ireland - DS3 System Services enabling participation of new technologies (including fast frequency response) and DER integration work.** DS3 is an operational TSO framework designed to enable new technologies to provide system services and it is widely used by battery projects and DER providers [63, 64].
- **Austria - Community batteries for congestion management and balancing.** Community owned batteries have been tested for combined DSO congestion management and TSO balancing services, demonstrating multi-use operation. TSOs and DSOs reduce grid constraints, while ECs maximise asset value through stacked revenues [65, 66].
- **Germany - Sonnen community batteries providing balancing services via Next Kraftwerke.** Sonnen and Next Kraftwerke implemented a field-operational solution where thousands of residential and community-owned home battery systems are aggregated into reserve groups and actively provide FCR to German TSOs. Sonnen is responsible for aggregation, control, and availability calculation of the batteries, while Next Kraftwerke ensures secure connection to TSO control centres and manages bidding and settlement in the balancing markets. This cooperation demonstrates how small-scale distributed batteries (≤ 25 kW) can be reliably bundled and operated as a virtual power plant to deliver primary frequency control, opening balancing markets to energy communities and enabling TSOs to access large volumes of decentralised flexibility [67].

- **Belgium - LINEAR pilot: Residential DER flexibility for system services.** The LINEAR project was a large-scale real-life pilot in Belgium involving 186 households and 418 smart residential assets, including wet appliances, domestic hot water buffers, and electric vehicles, coordinated to provide measurable and controllable demand response flexibility under real operating conditions. Over multiple years of operation, these aggregated DERs supported system-level applications such as portfolio balancing, real time balancing of wind forecast deviations, voltage control, and reduction of transformer thermal stress, all without compromising user comfort. The results demonstrated that residential flexibility can be reliably quantified and activated at scale, reaching up to 2 GW of load increase and 300 MW of load decrease at the national level, providing strong evidence that energy communities can contribute to future balancing, congestion management, and resilience services within coordinated TSO and DSO operational frameworks [68].

2) Restoration and black-start applications

- **Germany - Adaptation of system defence and restoration requirements [69, 70].** Germany is adapting its system defence and restoration framework to explicitly accommodate distributed generation and battery storage alongside conventional power plants. Under the national implementation of the ENTSO-E Emergency and Restoration framework, black start capability is defined in technology-neutral terms, allowing batteries and other DERs to participate, provided they can energise predefined grid sections without external supply and maintain voltage and frequency within specified limits. The updated approach combines region-based, market-oriented procurement with revised technical and organisational requirements, reflecting the increasing role of decentralised assets and the need for coordinated TSO–DSO restoration strategies in a renewable-dominated power system.
- **UK - Battery-based black-start with adapted technical requirements (National Grid ESO)[71, 4].** National Grid ESO has adapted black-start requirements to enable battery energy storage systems to participate through the Distributed ReStart framework. Battery providers must operate in grid-forming mode, energise a dead network section without external supply, establish stable voltage and frequency, manage inrush currents, and support staged reconnection of loads and generation while coordinating with DSOs. These requirements have been validated through contracted battery projects, demonstrating faster and more resilient restoration compared to conventional black-start approaches.

2.4.4 Challenges & Opportunities for EC/DER Participation in TSO Services

Frequency-related Services. The European regulatory framework increasingly enables DER and EC participation in frequency-control services through technology-neutral procurement and aggregation, notably under the Electricity Balancing Guideline (EBGL), which structures balancing capacity/energy products and European platforms (e.g., PICASSO for aFRR and MARI for mFRR). This creates clear opportunities for ECs to monetise flexibility via aggregators or BSPs, leveraging fast-response assets (BESS, controllable demand, EV charging) to provide FRR/FCR/aFRR/mFRR, particularly as system inertia decreases and the value of fast active power response increases.

In practice, however, EC/DER participation remains constrained by:

- product design and qualification hurdles (minimum bid sizes, symmetric requirements, ramping/accuracy constraints);

- prequalification and monitoring burdens originally designed for centralised units (testing complexity, telemetry, verification, and compliance demonstration), and
- operational coordination issues when distribution-connected flexibility providing TSO services conflicts with local network constraints, requiring stronger TSO–DSO coordination arrangements.

Recent evidence highlights that simplifying and standardising prequalification, enabling smaller aggregation portfolios, and improving coordination mechanisms are “no-regret” steps to unlock demand response and small actors in balancing markets. Overall, the main opportunity lies in scaling EC participation through aggregation + harmonised platforms, while the main challenge is ensuring verifiable technical performance (fast, accurate, observable response) without imposing disproportionate compliance costs on small distributed assets.

Table 2.7 – Barriers and mitigation measures for DER participation in Balancing services

Barrier	Mitigation
Energy-limited activation capability since DERs, particularly batteries and demand response, exhibit limited energy availability, constraining sustained activation for aFRR and mFRR	Alignment with short-duration products, fast and disturbance-oriented services (FFR, FCR) to match DER energy and response characteristics. Design new services oriented to EC/DER and explore their business models
Demand-side DER participation in frequency services is challenged by baseline uncertainty and rebound effects, which complicate performance verification and settlement	Portfolio-level aggregation combined with forecasting and coordinated control mitigates these effects by statistically smoothing individual behaviour and managing recovery phases
Conflicting service priorities since frequency activations may conflict with self-consumption or local grid objectives.	Multi-service optimisation in which coordinated scheduling enables service stacking and constraint-aware activation.
Static unit-centric prequalification and strict requirements	Aggregation is the main enabler for EC participation. EU balancing rules and European platforms are starting to be designed around BSP/BRP roles and standard products, meaning small DERs typically enter via aggregators rather than individually. However, simplified testing and prequalification should be addressed. Short, fast products are DER-friendly only if bid sizes and qualification are DER-friendly: experience from pilots highlights that lowering bid sizes, simplifying testing, and allowing portfolio-based compliance are key to scaling EC participation.
Strong TSO/DSO coordination is required, and field pilots show that without explicit coordination schemes and shared constraints, DER activation can create operational and market inefficiencies	Explicit TSO–DSO coordination frameworks, including constraint-aware activation, shared grid state information, and predefined operational procedures for resolving competing flexibility requests.

Restoration and Black-Start Services. The participation of DERs in black-start services is currently limited by a range of technical, operational, and regulatory barriers that differ across technologies and restoration stages. Although DERs show promising capabilities, their effective contribution is constrained by factors such as auxiliary power dependence, inverter control limitations, communication resilience, and restrictions on islanded operation. Table 2.8 summarises the key barriers affecting solar PV, battery storage, electric vehicles, and DERs in general, along with potential mitigation measures to enable their progressive integration into black-start and system restoration processes.

Table 2.8 – Barriers and mitigation measures for DER participation in Black-Start services

Technology	Barrier	Mitigation
PV	Most PV installations require auxiliary power from the network to energise control, protection, and communication systems and therefore cannot self-start following a total shutdown.	Provision of on-site auxiliary power sources (e.g. batteries or small generators) to energise auxiliary systems and enable self-starting.
	PV sites are predominantly connected via grid-following inverters that cannot form voltage and frequency references and therefore cannot initiate islanded operation.	Deployment of grid-forming inverter technologies and corresponding modifications to inverter control and communication systems.
	Solar generation is intermittent and dependent on irradiance, leading to uncertainty in available power during restoration.	Use of improved forecasting methods and co-location with storage to increase predictability and duration of contribution during restoration.
	PV installations are generally unable to meet conventional block-loading requirements used in transmission-led restoration strategies.	Adaptation of restoration procedures to allow for smaller block loads and reduced reactive power requirements for DER-based restoration.
BESS	Battery storage contribution is limited by installed energy capacity and state of charge at the time of a blackout.	Deployment of larger-capacity storage systems and development of alternative storage technologies with longer discharge durations.
	Many battery storage installations are configured for grid-following operation and cannot independently establish voltage and frequency.	Enabling grid-forming operational modes through inverter upgrades and coordinated control strategies.
	Existing auxiliary power and communication systems typically do not meet extended resilience requirements during prolonged outages.	Enhancement of on-site auxiliary power systems and communication resilience to meet Black Start availability requirements.
EVs	Low current penetration of EVs limits their availability and aggregate impact during Black Start events.	Increased deployment of EVs and aggregation within Energy Communities as adoption grows beyond 2030.

Technology	Barrier	Mitigation
	Lack of resilient communication and control infrastructure prevents EVs from being visible or controllable by system operators during restoration.	Development of resilient communication interfaces and integration of EV charging infrastructure into system operator control frameworks.
	Current EV inverters are not designed to provide grid-forming or frequency control capabilities.	Future development of advanced V2G technologies with enhanced inverter control functionality where system needs justify deployment.
All DERs	DER control and communication systems lack sufficient resilience for extended restoration timelines.	Upgrading communication infrastructure and implementing redundant or fail-safe local control modes.
	Loss-of-mains protection and regulatory requirements prevent intentional islanded operation following a blackout.	Regulatory modifications or exemptions during declared Black Start events to allow controlled islanded operation.
	DERs are not formally integrated into TSO- and DSO-led restoration planning and procedures.	Inclusion of DERs and Energy Communities in predefined restoration plans with clearly defined roles and responsibilities.

2.5 Conclusion

ECs are increasingly positioned as valuable partners for DSOs in delivering system services such as congestion management and voltage control. Across Portugal, Italy, the Netherlands, and Belgium, the regulatory framework clearly enables EC participation through mechanisms including LFMs, tariff-based signals, and FCAs. These tools allow DSOs to defer costly infrastructure reinforcements, improve observability, and manage local grid constraints more efficiently. Pilot projects show that community-level assets, particularly batteries, heat pumps, and EV charging, can reliably contribute to explicit flexibility provision when aggregated and digitally managed. ECs therefore represents a scalable pathway to unlock distributed flexibility in locations where DSO needs are increasing due to electrification and renewable penetration.

At the TSO level, EC participation in frequency-related ancillary services and restoration is technically feasible and increasingly regulated through technology-neutral, market-based European frameworks such as EBGL, PICASSO, MARI, and national pilot schemes. Distributed energy resources aggregated within ECs can support FCR, aFRR, mFRR, and, to a more limited extent, FFR, leveraging fast-acting assets like BESS and controllable loads. While prequalification requirements remain demanding, several international demonstrations confirm the operational viability of aggregated residential and community-owned DERs in providing balancing services. Furthermore, ongoing developments in grid-forming inverter technology, storage-based black-start pilots, and decentralised restoration strategies highlight a future role for ECs in system defense and restoration, especially as power systems evolve toward lower inertia and higher spatial distribution of resources.

Despite these opportunities, EC participation across both DSO and TSO-level services is still constrained by several barriers. Regulatory fragmentation, inconsistent national product definitions, and heterogeneous market rules hinder scale and predictability. Minimum bid sizes, strict technical requirements, and complex prequalification procedures continue to favor traditional

providers. At the distribution level, the lack of observability, limited remote-control capability in LV networks, and strict locational constraints reduce the pool of eligible resources. High upfront costs for advanced metering, telemetry, and automation disproportionately affect small communities. Baseline uncertainty, revenue unpredictability, and fear of operational disruption reduce engagement. For restoration services, the technical limitations of current DERs, particularly grid-following inverters, insufficient auxiliary power resilience, and restrictions on intentional islanding, are still significant obstacles.

This section also identifies several key drivers and recommendations for unlocking EC participation. Aggregation is a central enabler, allowing small DERs to meet bid sizes, smooth behavioral variability, and reduce baseline errors. Dual remuneration structures in LFMs, along with tariff-based incentives and FCA-related network-charge benefits, improve economic viability. Regulatory harmonisation, especially through the forthcoming NC DR, will be essential to scale flexibility markets and standardise baselining, data exchange, and TSO-DSO coordination. Investments in observability, digitisation, and grid-forming capabilities will expand the technical range of services ECs can deliver. Finally, aligning service design with DER characteristics, such as short-duration products for energy-limited assets, flexible activation rules, and portfolio-level performance verification, will ensure that ECs become integral contributors to both local and system-wide operational stability in future decentralised energy systems.

3 Modeling focus and quantitative study

This section serves as a preparatory section for the development and modeling work as well as quantitative analyses that will be presented in this report. This section summarises the energy sharing models and their extensions for flexibility provision mechanisms. Furthermore, it provides the description of the test cases and use cases for the quantitative analyses.

3.1 Summary of Energy sharing models

Four energy sharing model groups that are extensively studied in the U2Demo D2.3 report [2] are illustrated in Figure 3.1 and summarized as follows.

- *Capacity, energy, and revenue allocation models.* Under this model group, the community members share capacity, the generated energy, and/or the revenues from individually and collectively owned assets within the community. A community manager is responsible to operate the collective assets as well as determine the sharing of energy and/or revenues. In [2], two scheduling schemes, namely centralized and decentralized schemes, were investigated, and various allocation mechanisms were studied. In this work, we focus on the centralized scheme [2, Section 4.1] and consider the optimal excess allocation method [2, Section 4.2.2] for revenue allocation of explicit flexibility provision.
- *Internal energy pricing models.* This model group focuses on defining internal community pricing that enable internal energy sharing within the community. Different pricing mechanisms, determined by a community manager, can be considered. In this work, we focus on the Mid-Market Rate (MMR) and Supply-Demand Ratio (SDR) pricing mechanisms [2, Sections 5.1.2 and 5.1.3].
- *Auction-based local energy trading models.* Under this model, a local market is set up by the community manager. Each community member can submit their bid (price and quantity) on the energy that they are willing to exchange internally. The community manager will clear the market taking into account different objectives, such as community social welfare maximisation or redistribution inequality reduction via a lexicographic approach [2, Section 6.1].
- *Pool-based peer-to-peer energy trading models.* In this model [2, Sections 7.1], community members can trade directly with other members, creating peer-to-peer matchings. All trading in the community occurs simultaneously and requires a community manager to clear the market. Differently from the previous model, each member can set a preference regarding the members with which they are willing to trade, defined by their objective function. The community manager will then clear the peer-to-peer market considering the summation of the individual objective functions.

3.2 Extensions for flexibility provision

These energy sharing models specify how energy is shared/traded within the community, and the mathematical coordination algorithms/models therefor, and have been initially explored in [2]. In this report, we expand these models further to explore how different flexibility instruments to deliver different flexibility services can be integrated in these local energy sharing models.

For each energy sharing model group, we develop suitable flexibility provision mechanisms, focusing on two services: (i) congestion management through kW-max service (delivered via U2DEMO - System service provision models based on P2P trading and en- Page 46 of 134
ergy sharing

(a) Capacity, Energy, and Revenue Allocation Models

(b) Internal energy pricing models

(c) Auction-based local energy trading models

(d) Pool-based peer-to-peer energy trading models

Figure 3.1 – Energy sharing and trading models.

rule-based and tariff-based mechanisms), (ii) grid/system services that can be delivered through explicit mechanisms (explicit flexibility markets). The provision of these services defines the use cases considered in this quantitative study.

The kW-max service is essentially limiting the grid offtake and injection of the community to prevent congestion in the distribution system. This can be achieved by implementing a rule-based mechanism, i.e., imposing a strict limit to the community, which must then be taken into account into the energy sharing models. Differently, tariff-based mechanisms can also be imposed to reduce the community peaks or shift them to different period of the day. As discussed in Section 2.2.3, two types of tariffs, namely volumetric ToU and capacity tariffs, have been implemented in practice, and thus we will study how these tariff schemes impact an energy community’s ability to deliver the kW-max service.

For the market-based system services, we assume that the flexibility from the energy community can be aggregated by an aggregator (which can also be the community manager) for participation into a flexibility market. Therefore, the energy community must be able to quantify the available flexibility (both upward and downward) at a certain period of the day, which we

Table 3.1 – Summary of flexibility mechanisms that are developed for different energy sharing models.

Energy-sharing models	Mechanism			
	Rule-based	Tariff	Explicit Quantification	Explicit Activation
Capacity, energy, and revenue allocation	✓	✓	✓	✓
Internal energy pricing		✓	✓	✓
Auction-based local energy trading	✓	✓		✓
Pool-based peer-to-peer energy trading	✓	✓	✓	✓

call the flexibility activation period. Furthermore, the community must also be able to dispatch a flexibility request, i.e., deviating from the operation of the community from its baseline. Note that in this explicit mechanism, the baseline operation of the community is obtained according to the energy sharing model implemented by the energy community, optimizing its costs/revenues when no flexibility delivery is planned in (as such the baseline being the counterfactual energy consumption profile of the community had it not delivered any flexibility service during the considered time period, defined here as a computed energy schedule by the community manager [72]). Furthermore, when the energy community activates their flexibility, they will be remunerated according to certain prices.

The four U2demo energy sharing models might employ different flexibility provision mechanisms for the provision of the previously mentioned services. Table 3.1 summarizes the flexibility mechanisms considered in the four energy sharing models. The mathematical models of the mechanisms are provided in their corresponding sections.

3.3 Test case description and datasets

The quantitative studies conducted in this report are based on the Scheveningen energy community pilot, as described in [2]. The community consists of six members, each of which have inflexible loads and possibly PV generation. Furthermore, there exist some collectively owned assets, namely a battery and a PV generation unit, which is controlled by the community manager and can be used by the members. The overview of the energy community is provided in Figure 3.2.

The datasets collected from this pilot are from summer 2024 until summer 2025 and define the first case considered in the simulation study. Additionally, we created two other cases, which are modifications of the original datasets, i.e., a case with less flexible assets (case 2), and a case with more flexible assets (case 3), while the inflexible consumption profile of each member is kept the same. Specifically, the assets of the community in all cases are defined in Tables 3.2 and 3.3.

The energy community can be exposed to two types of retail prices, namely dynamic (time-varying) and flat-rate prices. As in the numerical study of [2], the dynamic prices are based on the day-ahead electricity prices for the same simulation period. The offtake prices include some transmission network tariffs and taxes [73] while the injection prices are exempt from both. Meanwhile, the flat-rate prices are obtained by averaging the dynamic prices.

3.4 Use case datasets

As discussed in Section 3.2, we consider two use cases, namely:

Figure 3.2 – Configuration of the Scheveningen pilot [2].

- Provision mechanisms for kW-max service (rule-based and tariff-based mechanisms).
- Explicit provision for market-based system services.

In the following, we describe the common datasets used for the numerical simulations of all provision mechanisms.

Rule-based mechanisms

In the rule-based mechanisms, grid limits, i.e., the maximum offtake and injection limits of the community, are imposed. We define two sets of grid limits, namely constant and dynamic grid limits. The constant grid limit is set at 200 kW, while the dynamic grid limits – reflecting the dynamically changing state of the grid – are shown in Figure 3.3. The calculation of these limits are described in Appendix A.

Tariff-based mechanisms

For the tariff-based mechanisms, two types of tariffs, namely capacity and volumetric ToU tariffs, are defined and studied. For the former, the tariff is set at € 3.09668 /kW/month, which is in line with the tariff imposed by Stedin, the DSO to whose network the energy community is connected [74]. Meanwhile, the ToU tariff is defined considering two periods in the day, namely day tariff (between 07:00-22:00), set at 7.57 ¢€/kWh, and night tariff (between 22:00-07:00), set at 4.545 ¢€/kWh. The choice of these tariffs is based on preliminary numerical simulations to ensure the annual cumulative collected DSO revenues from the capacity and volumetric ToU tariffs are equivalent.

Explicit mechanisms

Figure 3.3 – Dynamic and constant grid limits for the three cases. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

Table 3.2 – Solar PV capacity [kWp] for the three cases.

Entity	Type	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
GEMS	Collective	9	45	45
Pavilion 1	Individual	0	9	9
Pavilion 2	Individual	9	9	9
Harbour control	Individual	29	29	29
Beach stadium	Individual	0	0	4.5
Beach stadium Pavilion	Individual	0	0	4.5
Event connection	Individual	0	0	4.5

Table 3.3 – Battery (dis)charging power [kW] and energy capacity [kWh] for the three cases.

Entity	Type	Case 1		Case 2		Case 3	
		Power	Energy	Power	Energy	Power	Energy
GEMS	Collective	200	425	20	42.5	200	425
Pavilion 1	Individual	0	0	22	66	22	66
Pavilion 2	Individual	0.8	1.5	0.8	1.5	15	30
Harbour control	Individual	0	0	0	0	30	70
Beach stadium	Individual	0	0	0	0	2	4
Beach stadium Pavilion	Individual	0	0	0	0	2	4
Event connection	Individual	0	0	0	0	10	20

In the explicit flexibility provision mechanisms, the flexibility remuneration prices are set based on the settlement prices of TenneT, the Dutch TSO, for the simulation period (summer 2024-summer 2025) [75]. Figure 3.4 shows the plots of flexibility remuneration prices and retail prices. According to these plots, we determine the activation period and the direction (either upward or downward flexibility) for each simulated day, shown as gray shaded area in Figure 3.5 – the activation periods being the period during which the system operator is interested in procuring/activating explicit flexibility (via a flexibility request). Furthermore, the quantity of the requested flexibility during these activation periods is set based on the maximum flexibility potential quantification of the energy community, which is further explained in Section 4.3.4. The flexibility requests for all simulated days are shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.4 – Flexibility remuneration prices (upward and downward) as compared to the dynamic retail prices.

Figure 3.5 – The upward and downward flexibility requests for all cases. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

4 Provision mechanisms for capacity, energy, and revenue allocation models

In this section, we present the flexibility provision mechanisms developed for the capacity, energy, and revenue allocation model framework. For the kW-max service, we consider the rule-based and tariff-based mechanisms. For the explicit flexibility mechanism, first, the maximum flexibility potential (upward and downward) of the community is quantified while abiding by the operational constraints of the different flexible assets (individually-owned or collective) within the community. Subsequently, flexibility requests from external flexibility markets are addressed by optimally dispatching the requested flexibility among community members and shared technologies. The revenue from the provided flexibility is then allocated to the members.

These two flexibility services are discussed in more detail in the remainder of this section, where we not only present the mathematical models but also the quantitative analysis based on numerical simulations.

4.1 Energy management and sharing model

As mentioned earlier, the flexibility provision mechanisms are built upon the capacity, energy, and revenue allocation model framework. Under this framework, the operating schedules of all assets, both individual and shared, are optimised by the community manager centrally. Accordingly, the energy management problem is formulated and solved, explicitly accounting for the operational constraints of all assets, as well as the inflexible consumption and generation profiles of all community members. The objective of this optimisation problem is to minimise the total energy cost of the community. The formulation of the proposed energy-sharing scheme is presented as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}^{\text{com}}, \mathbf{P}^{\text{Net}}} \sum_{t \in T} J(P_t^{\text{Net}}) := \lambda_{d,t}^{\text{off}} [P_t^{\text{Net}}]_+ + \lambda_{d,t}^{\text{inj}} [P_t^{\text{Net}}]_- \quad (4.1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } P_{t,i}^{\text{net}} = P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} + \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{u}_{t,i}, \quad \forall t \in T, \quad (4.1b)$$

$$P_t^{\text{Net}} = P_t^{\text{Inflex}} + \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{u}_t^{\text{com}} + \sum_{i \in I} P_{t,i}^{\text{net}}, \quad \forall t \in T, \quad (4.1c)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathcal{U}_i, \quad \mathbf{u}^{\text{com}} \in \mathcal{U}^{\text{com}}, \quad (4.1d)$$

where $P_i^{\text{net}} = \text{col}((P_{t,i}^{\text{net}})_{t \in T})$ is the net energy position of member i over all time periods, i.e., $P_{t,i}^{\text{net}} = P_{t,i}^{\text{off}} - P_{t,i}^{\text{inj}}$, $P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}}$ is the net position of all inflexible assets (loads and generation), where $P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} > 0$ indicates that, aggregatively, the inflexible assets are consuming power, and $P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} < 0$ means that the inflexible assets are injecting power. The vector $\mathbf{u}_i := \text{col}((u_{t,i})_{t \in T})$ denotes the dispatch/scheduling decisions of all flexible assets. The set \mathcal{U}_i in Eq. (4.1d) represents the constraint set for all flexible assets, which includes the operational and technical constraints of the considered assets. For simplicity, we model all constraints of the assets as linear constraints, resulting in a polytopic \mathcal{U}_i . Finally, the operators $[\cdot]_+ = \max(\cdot, 0)$ and $[\cdot]_- = \min(\cdot, 0)$ are projections onto the non-negative and non-positive orthants. By solving the optimisation problem in (4.1), the optimal operating schedules $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$ for all flexible assets, and, hence, the net consumption profiles of all the community members and the shared installations are determined.

4.2 Mechanisms for kW-max Service

Under this energy-sharing model, the kW-max service can be provided through rule-based mechanisms and tariffs. In general, these mechanisms affect the energy-sharing and scheduling of the assets. Specifically, they modify different elements of the optimal energy sharing problem (4.1), which results in different schedules from those originally derived under the optimal solution to Problem (4.1) with no imposed tariffs or kW max limits. An overview of the adapted energy sharing model with these flexibility mechanisms is illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 – Flexibility provision mechanisms for the kW-max service.

4.2.1 Rule-based mechanisms

Rule-based mechanisms typically impose limits on the grid offtake and injection. Such limits can be incorporated directly into the energy-sharing problem (4.1) by adding the following constraints:

$$-\bar{P}_t^{\text{Inj}} \leq P_t^{\text{Net}} \leq \bar{P}_t^{\text{Off}}, \quad \forall t \in T, \quad (4.2)$$

where $\bar{P}_t^{\text{Inj}}, \bar{P}_t^{\text{Off}} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ denotes the grid injection and offtake limits that can vary over time t . Thus, the energy-sharing problem with grid limit constraints can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}^{\text{com}}, \mathbf{P}^{\text{Net}}} \quad & \sum_{t \in T} J(P_t^{\text{Net}}), \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (4.1\text{b}) - (4.1\text{d}), \text{ and } (4.2) \text{ hold.} \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

One can immediately observe that by restricting P_t^{Net} , the optimal value of the restricted problem (4.3) can be higher than the optimal value of the original problem (4.1), implying that rule-based mechanisms, by design, inherently result in a potentially higher energy cost than when no rule-based mechanism is included.

4.2.2 Tariffs

Differently from rule-based mechanisms, the inclusion of a tariff changes the objective function in the energy-sharing problem (4.1). We consider two types of tariffs, namely the time-of-use and the capacity tariffs.

The time-of-use tariff is a volumetric tariff (applied to each kWh of consumption), where the energy volumes offtaken from or injected into the grid are subject to a time-varying tariff [35]. Thus, the additional grid cost function due to this tariff can be represented by:

$$J^{\text{ToU}}(P_t^{\text{Net}}) = \lambda_t^{\text{ToU}} |P_t^{\text{Net}}|, \quad (4.4)$$

where λ_t^{ToU} denotes the tariff at time t . The addition of this tariff results in the following energy-sharing problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}^{\text{com}}, \mathbf{P}^{\text{Net}}} \quad & \sum_{t \in T} (J(P_t^{\text{Net}}) + J^{\text{ToU}}(P_t^{\text{Net}})) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (4.1\text{b}) - (4.1\text{d}) \text{ hold.} \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

Meanwhile, as discussed in Section 2.2.3, the capacity tariff is applied to the offtake peak (i.e., to the maximum kW consumption in a given time period, and not to the total consumed volume of energy). This can be incorporated into the energy-sharing problem by introducing an auxiliary variable that represents the offtake peak, denoted by $P_{\text{peak}}^{\text{Net}}$, and by including the tariff element into the objective function, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{u}_i, \mathbf{u}^{\text{com}}, \mathbf{P}^{\text{Net}}} & \left(\sum_{t \in T} J(P_t^{\text{Net}}) \right) + \lambda^{\text{peak}} P_{\text{peak}}^{\text{Net}} \\ \text{s.t. (4.1b) - (4.1d) hold,} & \\ & P_{\text{peak}}^{\text{Net}} \geq P_t^{\text{Net}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

where λ^{peak} denotes the capacity tariff. Note that in some countries, the capacity tariff is applied to the peak over a certain period of time, e.g., monthly peak [76]. To better integrate this into the daily scheduling problem, one can track the peak of the previous days in the same period (e.g., in the same month) and impose a lower bound on $P_{\text{peak}}^{\text{Net}}$ based on these previous peaks [76]. Similarly to the rule-based mechanism, when the two tariff schemes are introduced, schedules obtained by solving (4.5) or (4.6) are feasible for the original energy-sharing problem (4.1), since all constraints of the latter are included. However, they can indeed be suboptimal, implying a higher energy cost (even without the grid cost elements from the imposed tariff).

4.2.3 Numerical Simulation Results

The simulation results of the proposed mechanisms for kW-max services applied to the considered use cases are presented and discussed in this section. First, the results obtained using the rule-based mechanisms are reported, followed by the results corresponding to the tariff-based mechanisms. The performance of both mechanisms is evaluated under time-varying and flat-rate retail price structures.

Rule-based mechanisms:

To evaluate the performance of the rule-based mechanisms, the grid limits introduced in Section 3.4 are applied to the three considered use cases. Figure 4.2 presents the resulting community offtake and injection under both dynamic and static grid limits for all cases and retail price structures.

Under flat-rate (i.e., non-time-varying) retail prices, it is observed that neither dynamic nor static grid limits constrain the community's offtake or injection in any of the three cases. As a result, the offtake and injection profiles remain similar to the baseline scenario in which no grid limits are imposed.

In contrast, the results under time-varying retail prices exhibit different behavior. For Case 1 and Case 3, both dynamic and static grid limits effectively constrain the community's offtake and injection, leading to noticeable peak-shaving compared to the baseline. However, in Case 2, the baseline offtake and injection levels do not exceed the imposed grid limits; consequently, no peak-shaving is required under either dynamic or static grid limits.

To illustrate the impact of grid limits on the total community cost, the results for the three considered use cases under dynamic and static grid limits are reported in Table 4.4 and compared against the baseline scenario, which is the optimal solution of the energy sharing scheme without any grid limits imposed. As the grid limits do not affect the community's offtake and injection under flat-rate retail prices in any of the three use cases, the results presented in Table 4.4 correspond exclusively to scenarios with time-varying retail prices. For flat-rate retail prices, the cost remains equal to the baseline.

Figure 4.2 – Community offtake and injection with and without capacity limit. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

The results show that since the offtake and injection are curtailed in Case 1 and Case 3 under time-varying retail prices by both dynamic and static grid limits, these constrained operating points deviate from the cost-optimal energy-sharing schedules. Consequently, the imposition of grid limits leads to an increase in the total community cost in these cases. In contrast, for Case 2, where the baseline offtake and injection levels do not violate the imposed grid limits, no curtailment occurs, and the total community cost remains equal to the baseline optimal cost.

Tariff-based mechanism:

The simulation results of the capacity tariff mechanism for the three considered use cases under both time-varying and flat-rate retail price structures are illustrated in Fig. 4.3. The results indicate that, in most cases, the daily peak offtake and injection levels obtained from the baseline energy-sharing scheme, without any tariff constraints, are reduced when the capacity tariff is applied.

Nevertheless, the results also show that, unlike explicit capacity limits, the capacity tariff mechanism is unable to strictly enforce peak constraints for this studied case. As a result, the community’s offtake and injection can still exceed the threshold of 200 kW, indicating that capacity tariffs can mitigate but do not fully eliminate peak demand and injection events in this case study. The reason, thereof, stems from the available volume of flexibility and the insufficient incentives that the capacity tariff would provide to lead users to collectively abide by the grid limit.

Remark: We note here, importantly, that this result is case-dependent on the numerical use case we are exploring (which is inspired by the NL demonstrator in U2Demo, along with applicable tariffs), including the available flexibility volume in the system and the imposed capacity tariff level. Additional flexibility at the users’ level (e.g., additional battery capacity, or shiftable loads) or a higher capacity tariff level will lead to different behaviors/results. Indeed, a capacity tariff’s goal is to flatten the consumption profile as much as possible, granted there is enough incentive (the tariff is high enough) and enough flexibility for the users’ to effectively shift their consumption profiles and reduce their peaks. When these conditions are not met, the capacity tariff may be unable to effectively reduce the collective users’ peaks.

When applying the ToU tariff, periods with lower tariff levels create strong economic incentives for the EC to shift flexible demand and injection to these intervals, leading to increased offtake during low-tariff periods and reduced consumption during high-tariff intervals. This, as a result, highlights the need to design ToU tariffs (in terms of peak vs. off-peak time ranges, and resulting price levels) according to the prevailing price consumption profiles, and the need for system peak reduction. A misaligned ToU tariff can rather increase the system peak. In addition, under time-varying retail prices, the resulting load profile is shaped not only by the ToU tariff structure but also by the relative magnitude of the retail price signal compared to the ToU tariff levels. When low-tariff ToU periods coincide with relatively low retail prices, the combined price signal

Table 4.1 – Community total cost (EUR) under baseline, dynamic, and static grid limit scenarios.

Case	Baseline	Dynamic limits	Static limits
Case 1	70 595	70 718	70 700
Case 2	65 655	65 655	65 655
Case 3	57 086	57 677	57 281

Figure 4.3 – Community daily peak offtake and injection with and without capacity tariffs under time-varying and flat-rate retail prices. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

Figure 4.4 – Community daily peak offtake and injection with and without ToU tariffs under time-varying and flat-rate retail prices. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

reinforces demand shifting and can result in pronounced load peaks. In contrast, when the ToU tariff signal dominates the retail price variation, load shifting is primarily driven by the tariff structure, even during periods in which the underlying retail price would otherwise encourage or discourage consumption.

The simulation results for the ToU tariff are presented in Fig. 4.4. The results are reported for the three considered use cases under both time-varying and flat-rate retail price structures. It is observed that, unlike capacity tariffs, the ToU tariff does not effectively curtail the daily peak offtake or injection. In some instances, it can even lead to a significant increase in peak values. This is due to the misalignment between the ToU definition and the actual consumption profiles, the interplay between the ToU tariff and the (dynamic) retail price as mentioned earlier, and the collective common signal that ToU tariffs give to all participants, which can lead to simultaneous and similar actions. For example, in Case 1, under a flat-rate retail price, the application of the ToU tariff increases the community offtake beyond the 200 kW threshold, which is used as the reference limit for capacity tariff calculations. The peak increase occurs due to the low tariff during the night, which is exploited by the energy community to consume more and activate their flexibility assets (batteries), which can then be used during the high tariff period.

Remark: Similarly to the case of the capacity tariffs, the results shared here are case-dependent. However, in general, the effectiveness of a ToU tariff depends on whether the tariff differential between different time periods provides sufficient incentive for load shifting, and (ii) whether there is enough flexibility at the users' level to shift/flatten their load. If either of these two is not present, the effectiveness of the tariff will significantly decrease. In fact, a fully dynamic volumetric tariff that dynamically changes the tariff over time to reflect the state of the grid has been shown to theoretically resolve/prevent congestions effectively, if sufficient flexibility is available at the users' side [35]. However, a ToU tariff is not a fully dynamic tariff (which would change dynamically over time, having different values at different times), but rather has fixed ToU windows with fixed tariff levels in each. Hence, if the ToU time periods are not perfectly aligned with the peaks, and/or if the price differential between the two time periods (while also accounting for the price differentials created by the dynamic retail price) does not provide enough incentives to shift/flatten the consumption profiles, and/or if the amount of flexibility available is not sufficient to effectively shave the consumption peaks, the effectiveness of the tariff will be significantly limited.

To further illustrate the impact of the ToU tariff on community offtake, Fig. 4.5 presents the results of a single-day simulation for the community under both time-varying and flat-rate retail price structures. As observed in the figure, under the baseline scenario without a ToU tariff, under the baseline scenario without a ToU tariff,

Figure 4.5 – Single-day example of community offtake and retail prices with and without ToU tariff for Case 3.

the community experiences its peak offtake during periods with low retail prices. After applying the ToU tariff, this peak demand is shifted to the time intervals in which the lowest ToU tariff is applied. In the flat-rate scenario, the peak is also shifted to times of low ToU tariff, but this creates a new coincident peak. In both cases, however, the ToU successfully leads to keeping the peak below the target limit. This showcases that the ToU tariff can be effectively used for congestion management under viable conditions.

A similar pattern is observed for the flat-rate retail price case. While the ToU tariff successfully shifts the peak load to the low-tariff periods, it also leads to the formation of a new and significantly higher peak. These results indicate that, although the ToU tariff is effective in shifting demand temporally, it may amplify peak offtake levels, potentially exceeding the original peak demand. This highlights a key limitation of ToU tariffs in managing peak loads when they are not combined with explicit capacity constraints.

4.3 Explicit mechanisms for market-based services

In this section, the explicit mechanism through which the EC provides flexibility is described in detail. For the explicit flexibility mechanism, the optimal schedule obtained by solving Problem (4.1) is considered as a baseline (i.e., set points over the time horizon T) for all prosumers and their associated devices. Building upon this baseline, the explicit flexibility provision mechanism is presented, in which the EC participates as part of the flexibility portfolio of an FSP.

Within this framework, the EC is required to quantify and communicate to the FSP the maximum available upward and downward flexibility through direct provision. Subsequently, upon receiving a flexibility activation request, the EC must be capable of providing the requested flexibility by appropriately adjusting the operating schedules of its members and shared technologies. Finally, the remuneration received by the EC for providing flexibility, together with the associated energy costs, is allocated among the community members. An overview of the explicit flexibility provision mechanism is illustrated in Fig. 4.6.

Figure 4.6 – Market-based explicit flexibility provision mechanism.

Note that to enable the explicit flexibility provision mechanism, the EC receives a flexibility request along with the associated price signal directly from the SO. In this case, the community dispatches the portion of the requested flexibility that lies within its maximum quantified flexibility, taking the received price into account.

In general, this section aims to address the following aspects within the explicit mechanism to provide flexibility:

1. How the EC quantifies its maximum (upward and downward) available flexibility over a certain time range, while (i) respecting the technical constraints (power limits, energy limits, and intertemporal constraints) of all flexible assets (individual and cumulative), (ii) considering the provision of constant flexibility levels over a defined time range or a dynamically

- changing one, and (iii) considering the flexibility remuneration price impacts as well as the impacts of coexistence with different electricity retail price formats (constant vs dynamic);
2. How a flexibility activation request is provided and disaggregated among community members, and shared assets.
 3. How the revenue from the flexibility provision and the cost of energy consumption and sharing are allocated to the community members.

4.3.1 Flexibility quantification

This section presents the methodology used to quantify the maximum upward and downward flexibility that the EC can provide. It is assumed that the EC can either provide upward or downward flexibility per request. Therefore, two separate problems are used to calculate the maximum upward and downward flexibility of the EC.

The maximum upward and downward flexibility is denoted by Δ_t^u and Δ_t^d , respectively, for each defined $t \in T^a \subseteq T^f \subseteq T$. The time set T^a represents the flexibility activation period, during which the community manager is requested to activate flexibility, while T^f denotes the time window over which the community is permitted to deviate from the pre-scheduled baseline \bar{u}_i . Outside this window, the community manager is required to strictly follow the scheduled baseline \bar{u}_i .

Within T^f , individual community members are allowed to deviate from their pre-scheduled baseline \bar{u}_i , provided that the aggregated deviation satisfies the requested flexibility. The flexibility quantification is assumed to be performed on a day-ahead (DA) basis, where the community manager has prior knowledge of the time sets T^a, T^f , and T . To clearly distinguish between the roles of T^a, T^f , and T , (4.7) and (4.8) are introduced.

$$\sum_{i \in I^+} \left(P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} + 1^\top \bar{u}_{t,i} \right) + \Delta_t = \sum_{i \in I^+} \left(P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} + 1^\top u_{t,i} \right), \quad \forall t \in T^a \quad (4.7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I^+} \left(P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} + 1^\top \bar{u}_{t,i} \right) = \sum_{i \in I^+} \left(P_{t,i}^{\text{inflex}} + 1^\top u_{t,i} \right), \quad \forall t \in T \setminus T^f \quad (4.8)$$

where constraint (4.7) represents the power balance during the activation period T^a . Specifically, the aggregated net power of the community can deviate from its aggregated baseline schedule by an amount Δ_t , which is accommodated through adjustments in the new operating schedule variable $u_{t,i}$. During the flexibility window T^f , no additional constraints are imposed by the community manager on the decision variables of individual users. In this period, only constraint (4.1b) limits the adaptation of the new schedule variable $u_{t,i}$. This period, for example, enables shiftable loads to provide flexibility during T^a while still meeting their energy requirements within T^f . In contrast, constraint (4.8) enforces the aggregated updated schedule to coincide with the aggregated baseline outside the flexibility window T^f .

When EC members deviate from their cost-optimal schedules, which serve as the baseline, the provision of flexibility incurs an additional cost during both T^a and T^f . Consequently, in cases where the EC does not set a bidding price and instead receives the flexibility price directly from the FSP, the remuneration for flexibility activation must exceed this additional cost to ensure EC participation. The corresponding flexibility remuneration and incurred costs are defined as follows:

$$J^c = \sum_{t \in T} J(P_t^{\text{Net}}) - J(\bar{P}_t^{\text{Net}}), \quad (4.9)$$

$$J^f = \sum_{t \in T} \lambda^f \cdot |\Delta_{t,i}|, \quad (4.10)$$

where $J(P_t^{\text{Net}})$ and $J(\bar{P}_t^{\text{Net}})$ denote the user cost under the flexibility-activated schedule and the baseline (cost-optimal) schedule, respectively. The cost function $J(\cdot)$ corresponds to the objective function of problem (4.1). The term J^c represents the cost difference, i.e., the total additional cost incurred by rescheduling the community in order to provide flexibility. In contrast, J^f denotes the total remuneration received by EC for delivering flexibility. The parameter $\lambda^f > 0$ represents the flexibility price communicated by the FSP.

As discussed earlier, rescheduling assets to provide flexibility results in additional electricity costs, i.e., $J^c \geq 0$. Consequently, the participation of an EC in the explicit flexibility provision mechanism, without submitting a bid for the flexibility price, is economically attractive only if the flexibility remuneration exceeds the resulting increase in electricity costs. Therefore, when the flexibility price λ^f is known and communicated in advance, a non-negativity constraint on the community profit can be imposed as follows:

$$J^c \leq J^f \quad (4.11)$$

and the quantified flexibility calculated with this constraint can be called profit-constrained flexibility.

Moreover, the quantified maximum upward and downward flexibility can be either *time-varying* or *constant* over the activation period T^a . When it is necessary to make the flexibility volume constant, the following constraint is applied:

$$\Delta_t = \Delta_{t-1} \quad \forall t, t-1 \in T^a. \quad (4.12)$$

Max flexibility quantification:

Given the baseline schedule \bar{u}_i and considering constraints (4.7), (4.8), (4.11), and (4.12), the optimisation problem (4.13) is formulated to compute the maximum upward flexibility available at the EC level:

$$\min_{u_i, P^{\text{Net}}, \Delta} \sum_{t \in T} \Delta_t \quad (4.13a)$$

s.t. (4.1b) - (4.1d) hold,

(4.7), (4.8) hold,

(4.11), (4.12) hold (optional),

$$\Delta_t \leq 0 \quad \forall t \in T^a, \quad (4.13b)$$

$$\Delta_t = 0 \quad \forall t \in T \setminus T^a \quad (4.13c)$$

Similarly, the quantification of maximum downward flexibility is formulated as an optimisation problem in (4.14)

In our convention, upward flexibility is available if there exists a feasible $\Delta_t < 0$, whereas downward flexibility is available if a feasible $\Delta_t > 0$ exists. Notice that the main difference between problems (4.13) and (4.14) is their objective functions, where for the former, we want to find the minimum values of Δ , whereas in the latter, we aim to maximise the values of Δ . The solutions of these two optimisation problems represent the maximum amount of upward and downward flexibility that the energy community is willing to provide. Moreover, when the EC wants to determine the maximum technical flexibility quantity, the constraint on the profit (4.11) is removed from problems (4.13) and (4.14).

$$\max_{u_i, P^{\text{Net}}, \Delta} \sum_{t \in T} \Delta_t \quad (4.14a)$$

s.t. (4.1b) - (4.1d) hold,

(4.7), (4.8) hold,

(4.11), (4.12) hold (optional),

$$\Delta_t \geq 0 \quad \forall t \in T^a, \quad (4.14b)$$

$$\Delta_t = 0 \quad \forall t \in T \setminus T^a \quad (4.14c)$$

4.3.2 Flexibility disaggregation

To provide the requested flexibility and distribute it among community members, two alternative approaches are considered in this section based on (i) the flexibility capacity (capacity-based) and (ii) the cost of providing flexibility (cost-based).

Under the capacity-based dispatch approach, the following optimisation problem is formulated:

$$\min_{u_t, P^{\text{Net}}, \Delta} \sum_{t \in T} |\Delta_t^r - \Delta_t| \quad (4.15a)$$

s.t. (4.1b) - (4.1d) hold,

(4.7), (4.8) hold,

$$\Delta_t^u \leq \Delta_t \leq \Delta_t^d \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4.15b)$$

where Δ_t^r denotes the flexibility request received by the EC. The objective of this problem is to provide the maximum possible amount of flexibility at the community level in order to fully satisfy the request. Consequently, by neglecting flexibility prices, the formulation prioritises community members with higher flexibility provision capacities.

In contrast, the cost-based approach for dispatching flexibility explicitly accounts for the economic benefit of flexibility provision. The benefit obtained from providing flexibility is defined as the difference between the flexibility remuneration and the associated additional cost, expressed as $J^r = J^f - J^c$. Accordingly, the cost-based dispatch formulation is proposed as follows:

$$\max_{u_t, P^{\text{Net}}, \Delta} J^r \quad (4.16a)$$

s.t. (4.1b) - (4.1d) hold,

(4.7), (4.8) hold,

$$[\Delta_t^r]_- \leq \Delta_t \leq [\Delta_t^r]_+ \quad \forall t \in T. \quad (4.16b)$$

By the construction of Problem (4.16), the EC provides flexibility only when it is profitable; i.e., the optimal value of J^r is always non-negative, since the baseline is a feasible solution to Problem (4.16).

In both proposed approaches, the requested flexibility is dispatched among EC members and shared assets by adopting scheduling variables u_i . Therefore, the final operating schedule of all flexible assets, denoted by u_i^* , is obtained as the solution to either problem (4.15) or (4.16).

4.3.3 Revenue allocation from flexibility provision

The activation of flexibility generates a revenue for the community, and this revenue can then be allocated to the community members. In [2], we introduced different cost/benefit allocation methods and evaluated their performances². Based on our conclusion in [2], we consider the optimal excess method as it is the best-performing approach for energy sharing in an energy community. In brief, this allocation method requires solving a linear program where individual rationality and efficiency are incorporated as constraints, and the worst-case excess, i.e., the worst-case difference between the value of a subcoalition (a subset of the community performing the same activity) and the aggregated allocation of all members in that subcoalition, is optimised. This allocation method guarantees individual rationality, i.e., the allocation for each community member is better if not equal to the revenue obtained when each member acts individually, and efficiency, i.e., the total revenue is completely allocated to all members. The full description of this approach can be found in [2, Section 4.2.2], by noting that, for this flexibility provision, the (negative³) value function of a subcoalition is the (optimal) revenue J^r . Additionally, following [2, Section 4.2.4], the allocated revenue from collectively invested assets is redistributed to the community members according to the shares of their investment.

4.3.4 Numerical Simulation Results

In this section, the performance of the proposed flexibility quantification and disaggregation framework, together with revenue allocation, is evaluated through a series of simulations conducted on the three use cases introduced in Section 3. First, the results are presented to quantify the maximum available upward and downward flexibility at the community level for each use case. These results highlight the influence of different retail pricing schemes and flexibility characterisations on the magnitude of the attainable flexibility. Subsequently, the performance of the proposed cost-based and capacity-based mechanisms for providing and dispatching the requested flexibility within the community is assessed. Finally, the impact of these mechanisms on the overall community cost, together with the allocation of the flexibility revenue, is analyzed and discussed.

Flexibility quantification:

The results of the maximum upward and downward flexibility quantification for the three considered use cases are presented in detail in this subsection. Based on the flexibility activation periods and the requested flexibility type illustrated in Figure 3.5, upward and downward flexibility are quantified separately. Specifically, upward flexibility is evaluated for the 21 representative days during which the community is requested to activate upward flexibility, while downward flexibility is quantified for the remaining 9 representative days out of the 30 representative days. Also, note that whenever the total annual flexibility is reported, it refers to the aggregation of the quantified or provided flexibility values of the representative days, which are extrapolated to a full year using the associated weighting factors assigned to each representative day.

The results for the total maximum upward and downward flexibility, quantified at the community level for each case study, are summarised in Table 4.2. These results are obtained under both time-varying and flat-rate retail tariff structures. It is observed that in most cases, the community is able to offer a higher level of total flexibility under the flat-rate tariff. This outcome can be attributed to the fact that time-varying retail prices are often elevated during periods when the community is technically capable of providing flexibility. As a result, the remuneration received

²None of the existing energy allocation methods [2, Section 4.3] is applicable for flexibility provision.

³The energy-sharing formulation in [2, Section 4.2] considers a minimisation problem, while the optimisation problem for flexibility provision is maximising the revenue.

Table 4.2 – Total annual maximum flexibility available at the community level. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

Case study	Total Max Upward Flexibility (kWh)		Total Max Downward Flexibility (kWh)	
	Time-varying retail price	Flat-rate retail price	Time-varying retail price	Flat-rate retail price
Case1	60354.58	75656.11	40952.74	48227.32
Case2	18123.09	21200.56	9458.90	11739.57
Case3	91325.64	90641.63	52572.88	57957.26

Figure 4.7 – Daily upward and downward flexibility quantified at the community level for the representative days. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

for flexibility provision during these periods is insufficient to offset the additional costs incurred by deviating from the optimal operating schedule, as enforced by constraint (4.11). An exception is observed in Case Study 3, where the total annual maximum upward flexibility is slightly higher under the time-varying retail tariff. This outcome can be attributed to the higher level of installed PV capacity in this case, which increases the available potential for providing upward flexibility. The quantified upward and downward flexibility for each representative day used to simulate the three case studies is illustrated in Figure 4.7. The results indicate that, consistent with the annual aggregate flexibility outcomes, the communities in Case Studies 1 and 3 are capable of providing higher levels of flexibility, primarily due to the presence of a large shared battery within the community. In Case Study 3, both upward and downward flexibility are further enhanced as a result of the higher installed capacities of PV generation and energy storage systems. In contrast to the total maximum flexibility values reported in Table 4.2, the cumulative daily upward and downward flexibility under time-varying retail tariffs exceeds that obtained under flat-rate tariffs for certain representative days. This suggests that dynamic price signals can incentivise flexibility provision during specific periods, even when their aggregated annual effect is less pronounced.

To illustrate the impact of time-varying and flat-rate retail prices on the quantification of maximum upward and downward flexibility, the results for two representative days, with hourly simulation time resolution, are presented in Figure 4.8, together with the corresponding remuneration and retail price profiles. The figures on the left-hand side depict the maximum quantified upward flexibility under both time-varying and flat-rate pricing schemes. The shaded regions in each plot indicate the flexibility period T^f , during which community members are allowed to deviate from their optimal schedules to provide flexibility.

For the first representative day, the time-varying retail price is lower than the flat-rate price during the flexibility period T^f , while the remuneration for upward flexibility remains identical under both pricing schemes. Under these conditions, the provision of upward flexibility is economically attractive for the community, resulting in a higher level of quantified flexibility, as ensured by constraint (4.11). In contrast, for the second representative day, the time-varying retail price is higher than the flat-rate price during T^f . Consequently, the community is incentivised to offer less upward flexibility, since deviating from the optimal schedule would violate the non-negative profit condition imposed by constraint (4.11). Note that the baseline corresponds to the

Figure 4.8 – Maximum upward and downward flexibility quantified at the community level under different retail pricing schemes.

optimal community schedule obtained from the energy-sharing scheme under the associated retail price.

The figures on the right-hand side of Figure 4.8 present the results for the maximum downward flexibility quantification. A similar economic rationale applies in this case. Specifically, for the first representative day, when the time-varying retail price is comparable to the flat-rate price during the flexibility period, the quantified downward flexibility is also of similar magnitude under both pricing schemes. However, for the second representative day, the higher time-varying retail price during T^f leads to a reduction in the quantified downward flexibility relative to the flat-rate case.

Overall, these results demonstrate that constraint (4.11) plays a crucial role in determining the amount of flexibility that can be economically provided under different retail pricing structures and must, therefore, be explicitly considered when quantifying community-level flexibility.

Within the proposed flexibility quantification framework, the maximum available upward and downward flexibility at the community level can be evaluated under different flexibility characterisations. In this project, four distinct characterisations of maximum flexibility are considered: 1) *constant-volume & profit-constrained*, 2) *dynamic-volume & profit-constrained*, 3) *constant-volume & non-profit-constrained*, and 4) *dynamic-volume & non-profit-constrained*.

An overview of the four different flexibility categories is provided in Table 4.3. The first distinction relates to the temporal behavior of the quantified flexibility during the activation period T^a . When the maximum quantified flexibility remains constant by using constraint (4.12) throughout T^a , it is referred to as *constant-volume* flexibility. Conversely, when the maximum quantified flexibility varies across time steps within T^a , it is classified as *dynamic-volume* flexibility.

The second distinction concerns the enforcement of the non-negative profit constraint (4.11), which ensures that flexibility provision remains economically viable for the community. When this constraint is enforced, the resulting flexibility is labeled as *profit-constrained*. When the constraint is relaxed, allowing flexibility provision irrespective of profitability, the characterisation is referred to as *non-profit-constrained*.

To illustrate the differences among these flexibility characterisations, Figure 4.9 presents the maximum quantified upward and downward flexibility for a representative day under each of the four considered cases.

Figure 4.9 illustrates the impact of the profit constraint (4.11) on the quantification of maximum upward and downward flexibility. As expected, enforcing this constraint reduces the maximum amount of flexibility that can be economically provided in both directions. Furthermore, imposing the requirement that the flexibility quantity remains constant over the activation period T^a leads to an additional reduction in the quantified flexibility.

Overall, the *constant-volume & profit-constrained* flexibility characterisation yields the lowest

Table 4.3 – Summary of flexibility characterisations considered in the analysis.

Flexibility Type	Constraint (4.12)	Profit Constraint (4.11)	Label in figures
constant-volume & profit-constrained	Enforced	Enforced	Constant/profit
dynamic-volume & profit-constrained	Not enforced	Enforced	Dynamic/profit
constant-volume & non-profit-constrained	Enforced	Not enforced	Constant/No profit
dynamic-volume & non-profit-constrained	Not enforced	Not enforced	Dynamic/No profit

Figure 4.9 – Four different characterisations for maximum upward and downward flexibility quantification.

levels of quantified upward and downward flexibility. In certain cases, such as downward flexibility in Figure 4.9, the results indicate that the community may be unable to provide any flexibility under the *constant-volume & profit-constrained* characterisation.

The results of the total quantified maximum flexibility for the different flexibility types, as reported in Table 4.3, are illustrated in Fig. 4.10. Overall, the *dynamic-volume & non-profit-constrained* type of flexibility yields the highest levels of both upward and downward flexibility across all cases, whereas the *constant-volume & profit-constrained* configuration consistently results in the lowest quantified flexibility. This indicates that allowing dynamic flexibility without imposing a profit constraint enables the system to exploit the full potential of available flexibility.

The results further suggest that the profit constraint has a stronger limiting effect on the maximum achievable flexibility than the choice between dynamic and constant flexibility types. In most cases, introducing a profit requirement significantly reduces both upward and downward flexibility, even when dynamic flexibility is allowed. However, an exception is observed in Case 3, where the *dynamic-volume & profit-constrained* configuration provides higher flexibility than the *constant-volume & non-profit-constrained* configuration for both upward and downward directions. This indicates that, under certain system conditions, the benefits of dynamic flexibility can partially offset the restrictive impact of the profit constraint.

Consequently, it is not possible to identify a single dominant factor that universally limits flexibility. Instead, the relative impact of the flexibility type (dynamic versus constant) and the profit constraint is strongly case-dependent and influenced by the underlying system characteristics and price structures.

Flexibility disaggregation:

This section presents the simulation results of the proposed capacity-based and cost-based approaches for the considered use cases. These mechanisms are referred to as flexibility disaggregation approaches, as they determine how the community responds to external flexibility requests. Following the quantification of the maximum available upward and downward flexibility, the energy community is assumed to actively respond to received flexibility requests by dispatching the available resources accordingly.

In this study, it is assumed that each flexibility request is communicated to the community together with its corresponding activation time, enabling the coordinated and timely activation of flexible resources. The flexibility requests and their associated activation times considered in this section correspond to those illustrated in Fig. 3.5. These predefined requests are used to

Figure 4.10 – Total annual maximum quantified upward and downward flexibility for different flexibility characterisations. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

Figure 4.11 – Total provided flexibility and associated community cost for flexibility disaggregation approaches under different retail price structures. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

evaluate and compare the performance of the proposed flexibility disaggregation approaches. The simulation results of the proposed flexibility disaggregation approaches for the three considered case studies are illustrated in Fig. 4.11. The left-hand side panels present the results for total upward flexibility disaggregation, whereas the right-hand side panels show the corresponding results for total downward flexibility disaggregation. These results provide a comprehensive comparison of how flexibility is allocated across different flexibility requests and disaggregation strategies. To investigate the impact of retail pricing structures on flexibility disaggregation, the results are reported for both time-varying retail prices and flat-rate retail prices. This comparison highlights the influence of price signals on providing the available flexibility. Furthermore, in calculating the total disaggregated flexibility, the weighting factors of the representative days are applied to appropriately scale the results and obtain annualised flexibility values. This ensures that the reported results accurately reflect the relative contribution of each representative operating condition.

The results indicate that, across all case studies, the community receives a higher volume of upward flexibility requests than downward flexibility requests. The blue bars represent the total requested flexibility in each case. For both retail pricing structures, time-varying and flat-rate, it is consistently observed that the capacity-based flexibility disaggregation approach is able to deliver a larger share of the requested flexibility in response to both upward and downward requests. In contrast, the cost-based approach does not fully satisfy the received flexibility requests in any of the considered cases.

Despite this limitation, the cost-based approach proves effective in reducing the total cost of the community in all three case studies by selectively providing upward and downward flexibility only when it is economically advantageous. The gray bars represent the baseline community cost after energy sharing, against which the impact of flexibility activation is evaluated. Compared to this baseline, the cost-based approach consistently lowers total costs, demonstrating its economic efficiency. Note that the cost associated with the disaggregation approaches is calculated as the difference between the baseline community cost and the remuneration received for flexibility provision.

For downward flexibility, the capacity-based approach can, in some cases, lead to an increase in community costs, as it may require higher energy offtake from the grid or a reduction in local energy injection. Although this approach enables the community to respond more effectively to downward flexibility requests by providing a larger volume of flexibility, it does so at the expense of increased costs. As a result, the community lacks sufficient economic incentives to offer downward flexibility under this approach.

Conversely, the cost-based approach ensures that the provision of flexibility is always economically beneficial for the community, even though it may fail to meet the full requested flexibility. This highlights a fundamental trade-off between maximising the volume of delivered flexibility and maintaining economic incentives for community participation.

To evaluate the short-term performance of the proposed methods, Fig. 4.12 presents the results of flexibility disaggregation in terms of daily provided flexibility and the associated community cost under both time-varying and flat-rate retail price structures. The results show that, for all representative days, the capacity-based approach delivers a higher volume of both upward and downward flexibility compared to the cost-based approach. In contrast, the cost-based approach activates flexibility only when it is economically beneficial for the community.

For downward flexibility, the capacity-based approach consistently imposes higher costs on the community under both retail pricing structures. For upward flexibility, the capacity-based approach can be economically beneficial on certain days; however, even in these cases, the cost-based approach achieves a more effective reduction in community costs. These findings further highlight the trade-off between maximising the amount of delivered flexibility and ensuring economically efficient participation by the community.

Figure 4.12 – Daily provided flexibility and community cost for flexibility disaggregation approaches under different retail price structures.

Revenue allocation:

Table 4.4 shows the average annual cost reduction for all community members across all three cases under two different retail prices (time-varying and flat-rate). It is calculated by comparing the allocated cost with flexibility provision remuneration and the allocated cost without flexibility provision (baseline operation), where the allocation for both uses the optimal excess method. From this table, we can observe that explicit flexibility provision benefits all community members, as the average annual cost incurred is reduced when the energy community participates in the service provision activities.

Since the numerical study assumes that all members have an equal share of the collective batteries, the benefits of flexibility provision for members with low consumption (e.g., Beach stadium and Beach stadium pavillion) are relatively high in comparison to their baseline allocated costs (see the normalised columns). Additionally, although Harbour control receives the largest cost reduction (€5248 and €4025 for time-varying and flat-rate prices, respectively), this reduction is relatively low as compared to their baseline allocated costs (10.2% and 7.7%) since it has high energy consumption.

Table 4.4 – The average cost reduction of all community members over all cases by performing flexibility provision

Member	Time-varying price		Flat-rate price	
	Cost reduction	Normalised	Cost reduction	Normalised
Pavillion 1	1962	23.3%	2281	25.2%
Pavillion 2	817	54.8%	1043	45.4%
Harbour control	5248	10.2%	4025	7.7%
Beach stadium	309	61.9%	507	534.1%
Beach stadium pavillion	225	378.5%	485	153%
Event connection	342	10.4%	639	16.1%

4.4 Conclusion

The main conclusions from this section of the study can then be captured as follows.

- The rule-based mechanisms (both dynamic and static capacity limits) effectively curtail the community’s offtake and injection; however, this comes at the expense of an increase in total energy costs.
- For the tariff-based mechanisms, the application of a capacity tariff reduces peak offtake and injection levels; however, these peaks may still exceed the imposed capacity limits if the scale of the tariff and the available amount of flexibility at the users level is insufficient. A similar observation can be also applied to the ToU tariff, as its effectiveness depend on its the alignment of the ToU time periods with the consumption peaks, the levels of incentives it provides for load shifting (price differential between different time periods, when also considering the impact of (dynamic) retail prices). In addition, ToU tariffs can lead to simultaneous shifting of all users to new consumption times creating new peaks. Therefore, careful design and testing are needed to ensure the efficacy of these mechanisms.
- For flexibility quantification, the maximum upward and downward flexibility is obtained under the *dynamic-volume & non-profit-constrained* characterisation, in which neither the

non-negative profit constraint (4.11) nor the constant flexibility constraint (4.12) are enforced in the model. When the non-negative profit constraint (4.11) is imposed, the achievable flexibility becomes highly dependent on both retail electricity prices and flexibility remuneration levels. For the three considered use cases, the quantified upward and downward flexibility is generally higher under flat-rate retail prices than under time-varying retail prices. Furthermore, when both constraints (4.11) and (4.12) are simultaneously enforced, the total quantified upward and downward flexibility reaches its lowest values. For certain activation periods, the quantified flexibility becomes zero under this characterisation, indicating that no economically viable and temporally constant flexibility can be provided.

- When disaggregating flexibility requests, the proposed capacity-based approach provides a higher amount of requested flexibility than the cost-based approach for both upward and downward flexibility. This is because the objective of the cost-based approach is to maximise revenue by considering the remuneration prices and energy prices, whereas the capacity-based approach aims to maximise the amount of provided flexibility regardless of these prices. Consequently, the cost-based approach reduces the community cost for both upward and downward flexibility, while the capacity-based approach may even increase the community cost when providing downward flexibility.
- Overall, the economic benefits of flexibility provision are positive for all community members as the flexibility revenue and energy cost are distributed based on the optimal excess allocation method.

5 Provision mechanisms for internal energy pricing models

This section presents the flexibility provision mechanisms developed within the internal energy pricing model framework. We examine two approaches: an implicit mechanism based on capacity tariffs, and an explicit mechanism that quantifies maximum flexibility potential and activates requested flexibility. The following subsections detail these mechanisms and analyze the simulation outcomes of implementing them within the internal energy pricing model framework.

5.1 Mathematical formulation

This section details the implementation of the two flexibility mechanisms. As previously noted, both mechanisms operate within the internal energy pricing model framework. Since this framework is comprehensively described in Deliverable 2.3 [2], it will not be repeated again here. The focus of this section remains strictly on the implementation of the flexibility mechanisms themselves.

5.1.1 Tariff-based mechanism - Capacity tariff

For the tariff-based mechanism, a capacity tariff is implemented within the modeling framework. The tariff rate is initialised to the reference value described in Section 3.4. This tariff is applied to the individual monthly peak offtake of each individual consumer (€/kW/month). By incentivising consumers to flatten their individual load profiles, this mechanism aims to contribute to lowering the aggregate system peak, thereby supporting grid operation within safe limits.

The implementation of the capacity tariff is integrated into the individual consumer decision-making model (see Deliverable 2.3, Section 5.1.1) by introducing additional constraints and revising the objective function.

To incorporate the capacity tariff into the consumer decision-making model, we introduce an auxiliary decision variable p_m^{peak} , representing the peak power offtake for month m . This variable is governed by an inequality constraint, ensuring it captures the maximum grid offtake within the corresponding billing period. The formulation is defined as follows:

$$p_{d,t}^{off} \leq p_m^{peak} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}_m, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (5.1)$$

where \mathcal{T} denotes the set of time steps in a day, \mathcal{D}_m represents the set of representative days in month m , and \mathcal{M} is the set of all months in the simulation horizon.

Accordingly, the objective function is modified to include the capacity charge. An additional cost term, calculated as the product of the capacity tariff rate CAP and the monthly peak, is added to the original objective:

$$\text{Objective}_{new} = \text{Objective}_{original} + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (CAP \cdot p_m^{peak}) \quad (5.2)$$

5.1.2 Explicit mechanism

This section presents the mathematical formulation of the explicit flexibility mechanism. The mechanism is divided into two sequential optimisation models: **Flexibility Quantification** (calculating technical potential) and **Flexibility Activation** (simulating market response).

Both models are formulated as centralised community optimisation problems. They aggregate the individual consumer decision-making constraints (e.g., energy balance, battery dynamics, and PV generation limits) detailed in Deliverable 2.3. Consequently, these common physical

constraints are not repeated here. The focus remains solely on the aggregated objectives and the specific flexibility constraints introduced in this deliverable.

The implementation relies on a “baseline-deviation” approach. First, the community operation is simulated under standard market conditions using the Internal Energy Pricing Model from Task 2.3. The resulting net-load profiles and local market prices serve as fixed input parameters for the flexibility models. For clarity, the key input parameters derived from the baseline simulation, along with those newly introduced for the flexibility implementation, are defined below:

- **Baseline Inputs (from Deliverable 2.3 Results)**

1. $P_{d,t,i}^{\text{net_base}}$: The baseline net offtake (grid offtake minus injection) for consumer i at time t , taken from the T2.3 simulation outcomes.
2. $\lambda_{d,t}^{\text{off}}, \lambda_{d,t}^{\text{inj}}$: The local energy market prices (offtake and injection) determined in the baseline simulation with the specific internal pricing rules. Simulations are repeated for both pricing rules: the MMR and the SDR.

- **Flexibility Parameters**

1. $I_{d,t}^{\text{req}} \in \{1, -1, 0\}$: A direction indicator parameter. 1 denotes a request for upward regulation (increase injection/reduce offtake), -1 for downward regulation (reduce injection/increase offtake), and 0 for no request.
2. $\text{Flex}_{d,t}^{\text{req}}$: The external flexibility requirement (kW), representing the maximum flexibility the FSP is requesting at that time step.
3. $\lambda_{d,t}^{\text{flex}}$: The remuneration price (€/kWh) offered to activate the requested flexibility.

Flexibility Quantification Model The primary objective of the quantification model is to determine the maximum technical flexibility potential of the community, defined as the maximum possible deviation from the baseline profile given specific flexibility requests. The model maximises the total aggregated flexibility, $\delta_{d,t,i}^{\text{flex}}$, provided by all consumers i :

$$\max \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}} \delta_{d,t,i}^{\text{flex}} \quad (5.3)$$

subject to the following constraints:

1. **Flexibility Definition:** The flexibility provided is defined as the deviation between the baseline net offtake and the new net offtake. This is scaled by the requested direction $I_{d,t}^{\text{req}}$ to ensure the magnitude is always positive and matches the requested service:

$$\delta_{d,t,i}^{\text{flex}} \leq I_{d,t}^{\text{req}} \cdot \left(P_{d,t,i}^{\text{net_base}} - (p_{d,t,i}^{\text{off}} - p_{d,t,i}^{\text{inj}}) \right) \quad \forall d, t, i \quad (5.4)$$

2. **Requirement Cap:** The total flexibility aggregated across the community cannot exceed the external requirement in each time step:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}} \delta_{d,t,i}^{\text{flex}} \leq \text{Flex}_{d,t}^{\text{req}} \quad \forall d, t \quad (5.5)$$

3. **Physical Feasibility:** All physical constraints governing individual consumers (e.g., battery dynamics, PV limits, energy balance) must be satisfied, as defined in the individual consumer decision-making model in Deliverable 2.3. Notably, we require that the state of charge of the batteries be 50% at the beginning and end of the day, similar as in the baseline. Consumers who respond to flexibility requests by discharging or charging their

batteries will therefore have to compensate for it outside of this flexibility provision window. The latter leads to a small rebound through which consumers generally incur additional electricity procurement costs (or obtain fewer injection revenues).

Flexibility Activation Model

The activation model simulates the economic response of the community. It incorporates flexibility revenues into the objective function to determine the optimal flexibility activation volume by consumers given specific remuneration prices. The objective is formulated to maximise the total economic surplus of all consumers, comprising the cost of electricity offtake, revenue from electricity injection, and revenue from flexibility activation. Consumers hence face a trade-off when receiving a flexibility request: they obtain revenues by providing flexibility services, but increase their net electricity procurement cost as they deviate from their (first-best) baseline. As such, consumers will only be willing to provide flexibility when the former component exceeds the latter.

The model treats local energy market prices as exogenous parameters that remain static during flexibility activation. Although minor price deviations could technically occur due to shifts in consumer net-load profiles, this formulation remains a valid approximation for the community manager to estimate the magnitude of flexibility activated by specific price signals.

$$\max \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} w_d \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left(-\lambda_{d,t}^{\text{off}} \cdot p_{d,t,i}^{\text{off}} + \lambda_{d,t}^{\text{inj}} \cdot p_{d,t,i}^{\text{inj}} + \lambda_{d,t}^{\text{flex}} \cdot \delta_{d,t,i}^{\text{flex}} \right) \quad (5.6)$$

subject to the same physical and flexibility constraints as the quantification model.

5.2 Results and analysis of internal energy pricing models

The results for both mechanisms simulated within the internal energy pricing model framework are presented below.

5.2.1 Capacity tariff

The primary objective of the capacity tariff is to reduce the community's peak load, ensuring the grid operates within safe limits. To evaluate its efficacy, we compare the daily peak loads across 30 representative days, both with and without the capacity tariff. The analysis covers three distinct simulation cases under two types of retail contracts: fixed-rate and (dynamic) RTP. The comparison reveals several key insights, particularly regarding grid safety limits. As illustrated in Figure 5.1, under the RTP contract (right column), the baseline scenarios (solid lines) frequently exhibit daily peaks exceeding the static grid limit of 200 kW, particularly in Case 1 and Case 3. However, with the implementation of the capacity tariff (dashed lines), the community peak load is effectively constrained, remaining within safe operating limits. The reduction is consistent across most days, confirming that the capacity tariff is highly effective in mitigating peak stress on the grid.

However, on certain days, the peak load under the capacity tariff is observed to be slightly higher than in the baseline case. This phenomenon occurs because the capacity tariff applies specifically to peak offtake, not injection. In the baseline scenario, consumers might charge batteries or increase consumption during low-price periods, thereby self-consuming local generation and lowering injection peaks. However, the capacity tariff discourages high-power grid offtake. Consequently, consumers become more cautious about offtaking from the grid, which can inadvertently lead to higher net injection peaks during periods of surplus generation, as the battery may be preserved for different intervals or charging power is limited to avoid peak offtake penalties.

Figure 5.1 – Comparison of daily peak loads for 30 representative days, with and without the capacity tariff. The left column displays results for fixed-rate contracts, while the right column displays results for RTP contracts. The rows correspond to Case 1 (original), Case 2 (lower flexibility), and Case 3 (higher flexibility), respectively.

After implementing the capacity tariff, there does not appear to be a significant difference in collective peak consumption between the two local pricing mechanisms (i.e., MMR and SDR). On some days, the MMR yields a higher peak than the SDR, and on other days, the opposite can occur. This depends on the extent to which the pricing mechanisms cause collective peaks on particular days, as well as the interaction between the capacity tariffs and these pricing mechanisms. While these effects are system-specific and must be tested for each case, our results suggest that the difference could be small.

Finally, comparing the two contract types, it is evident that RTP contracts generally induce significantly higher peaks than fixed-rate contracts. This is expected, as hourly variable price signals coordinate consumer behavior, encouraging simultaneous offtake or injection. For instance, extremely low prices may incentivize simultaneous battery charging across the community, exacerbating the system peak. The capacity tariff proves particularly valuable in this context. As shown in the plots, it dampens this synchronized behavior (e.g., limiting aggressive battery charging), resulting in a sharp decrease in the magnitude of the peaks compared to the baseline RTP cases.

While the capacity tariff successfully ensures the system remains within static grid limits, specific instances of dynamic grid limit violations still exist. These violations occur exclusively under the RTP contract in Case 3. Specifically, three violations are recorded under the MMR mechanism and two under the SDR mechanism.

These instances are detailed in Figure 5.2, where the dynamic grid capacity envelope is depicted by the blue shaded area, and the community net offtake is represented by red dots. Any point falling outside the blue shaded region indicates a violation of the dynamic grid limits.

As evident in Figure 5.2, four out of the five recorded violations are driven by peak injection. Only one violation is attributed to peak offtake, where the limit is exceeded by a relatively small amount of approximately 10 kW.

This behavior highlights a limitation of the mechanism: because the capacity tariff is imposed solely on peak offtake, it does not inherently mitigate injection peaks. While applying a capacity tariff to injection could technically resolve this issue, it risks disincentivizing consumer investment in solar PV.

A closer inspection of the retail prices and individual load profiles during these violation moments reveals that the injection peaks coincide with high injection prices (high day-ahead market prices). Driven by these price signals, consumers maximize exports to generate revenue. Notably, the discharge from the community battery contributes significantly to these aggregate injection peaks. Consequently, a more targeted solution, rather than penalizing all PV generation, would be to refine the operational strategy of the collective battery, such as reserving capacity or limiting discharge rates during grid congestion windows.

Finally, we examine the financial impact of the capacity tariff on the community. Figure 5.3 illustrates the relative cost change compared to the baseline scenario, decomposing the total increase into two distinct components: the direct payments made by consumers for the capacity tariff (represented by light shades) and the operational cost difference (represented by dark shades). This operational difference reflects the change in net energy procurement costs, or the loss of surplus, resulting from consumers altering their behavior to minimize peak loads.

As evidenced by the dominance of the lighter-shaded bars in Figure 5.3, the vast majority of the cost increase is attributable to the capacity tariff itself rather than operational inefficiencies. This observation carries significant implications for grid cost recovery. Under a sunk cost assumption where the total revenue requirement of the DSO is fixed, the revenue collected via capacity tariffs would theoretically offset the baseline fixed grid fees. Therefore, from a system perspective, this is not necessarily a net cost increase but rather a reallocation of charges. Furthermore, this reallocation promotes fairness. In the baseline, grid costs were recovered via an equal fixed fee distributed identically across all consumers, regardless of their impact on the

Figure 5.2 – Violations of dynamic grid limits in Case 3 - RTP. The blue shaded area represents the feasible dynamic grid envelope, while red markers indicate the community net offtake.

Figure 5.3 – Relative cost change after the implementation of the capacity tariff. The bars represent the aggregate cost increase, decomposed into the direct capacity tariff payments (light shades) and the operational cost difference caused by behavioral changes (dark shades).

grid. The capacity tariff shifts this burden, ensuring that consumers who impose higher peak demands contribute a proportionally larger share to grid maintenance.

Regarding market efficiency, while capacity tariffs technically introduce a distortion to the pure energy price signal, the results demonstrate that the resulting inefficiency, represented by the dark bars, is small. Under the fixed rate contract, the operational cost difference is negligible across all cases. Under the RTP contract, a visible operational cost penalty exists, particularly in Case 1. However, this inefficiency diminishes significantly in Case 3. This trend suggests that when consumers possess sufficient flexibility assets, such as the batteries available in Case 3, they can manage peak loads without significantly deviating from their optimal energy consumption or sacrificing utility. Consequently, the capacity tariff proves to be a robust instrument that could successfully reduce system peaks and associated grid costs without entailing significant market efficiency losses.

5.2.2 Explicit flexibility

This section evaluates the performance of the explicit flexibility mechanism, focusing on the community's ability to activate flexibility in response to external requests.

We begin by comparing the realized **activated flexibility** (derived from the Flexibility Activation Model) against the **maximum technical potential** (derived from the Flexibility Quantification Model) and the total **flexibility requirement**. These results are illustrated in Figure 5.4. In this figure, the dashed line indicates the total flexibility requirement aggregated over the simulation year. The total height of each bar represents the maximum technical flexibility potential. Within each bar, the colored segments denote the actual activated flexibility contributed by different consumers, while the white portion represents the available potential that remained unactivated under the given remuneration prices.

The results yield several key insights. First, across all cases—regardless of market mechanism or contract type—the community's maximum technical potential is generally sufficient to meet the external flexibility requirements. However, the economic activation rate is notably lower; typically, only 50% to 70% of this technical potential is actually activated given the specific remuneration prices offered. This indicates that while the physical capability exists, the price signals may not always be sufficient to incentivize full activation against the consumers' internal opportunity costs.

Second, the contribution to flexibility is strongly proportional to the battery capacity available to each consumer. This trend is evident across the three simulation cases:

- Case 1: Almost the entire flexibility volume is provided by the collective BESS (425 kWh). Individual contributions are negligible, as only Pavilion 2 possesses a battery, and it is a small 1.5 kWh unit.
- Case 2: The collective BESS (sized at 42.5 kWh in this case) provides approximately 50% of the flexibility. The remaining share is largely contributed by Pavilion 2, which holds a 66 kWh battery.
- Case 3: The contributions are more diversified, reflecting a broader distribution of assets across the community. However, the collective BESS (425 kWh) remains the dominant provider, supplying the majority of the flexibility service.

Finally, comparing the internal pricing mechanisms, flexibility is generally easier to activate under the SDR mechanism than the MMR mechanism. This difference stems from the lower opportunity cost associated with flexibility activation under SDR. For instance, consider a time step where the community has an energy surplus. If a consumer provides downward flexibility (increasing injection), under the MMR mechanism, this additional supply would further decrease

Figure 5.4 – Comparison of activated flexibility versus requirements under Fixed Rate and RTP tariffs across three cases. The dashed line indicates the requirement, colored bars show activated volumes by consumer, and white bars indicate unactivated technical potential. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

the local market price, thereby reducing the revenue earned from energy sales. In contrast, under the SDR mechanism, the local price will not change. Consequently, consumers can provide flexibility without negatively impacting the value of their underlying energy transactions, leading to higher activation rates.

To illustrate the activation dynamics and validate the comparison between the two pricing mechanisms, Figure 5.5 presents a specific instance of flexibility activation from Case 3. In this scenario, the community receives a request for downward regulation (requiring an increase in offtake or a decrease in injection of approximately 25 kW) during the midday window of 11:00 - 14:00.

The figure plots the baseline net offtake (blue circles), the target flexibility profile (red diamonds), and the actual activated profile (blue stars). As observed, the flexibility requirement is successfully met under both market mechanisms on this specific day. However, the operational strategies employed to achieve this activation differ significantly.

Under the MMR mechanism, consumers adopt a strategy of distributing their battery discharge slowly across almost all remaining hours of the day. This behavior is driven by the specific pricing rules of the MMR model: local selling prices are highest when the community remains a net importer (non-negative net offtake). If consumers were to discharge aggressively, the community might switch to a net export state, causing the local selling price to drop. Therefore, consumers choose to trickle-discharge their batteries to try to keep the community net offtake non-negative, ensuring all their injections are settled at the favorable mid-market rate rather than the lower retail injection price.

Conversely, under the SDR mechanism, flexibility provision is achieved through a more distinct operational shift. Consumers aggressively discharge their batteries in a single concentrated interval (visible as the sharp injection spike prior to the event) to deplete storage capacity. This allows them to subsequently increase offtake (recharge) during the requested downward regulation window. This strategy is viable under the SDR because, as noted previously, the price remains stable even during high injection periods. This allows consumers to discharge rapidly to prepare their batteries without crashing the local price, whereas such a move would cause a significant loss of revenue under the MMR mechanism.

Finally, we evaluate the aggregate financial impact of the explicit flexibility mechanism on consumers. Figure 5.6 illustrates the decomposition of the total consumer cost into three distinct components relative to the baseline scenario: the initial consumer bill determined in the baseline simulation, the operational inefficiency caused by altering consumption behaviors, and the financial rewards received for providing flexibility. The operational inefficiency represents the additional cost incurred (or surplus lost) when consumers deviate from their optimal energy profile to satisfy the flexibility request.

The analysis reveals that while the magnitude of flexibility remuneration is roughly proportional to the volume of flexibility offered across the different cases, the associated inefficiency is not. Typically, the magnitude of inefficiency is inversely related to the availability of flexibility assets. With greater battery capacity, flexibility can be easily activated with lower operational disruption than those with limited assets.

Crucially, this operational inefficiency is substantial, significantly exceeding the minor inefficiencies observed under the capacity tariff mechanism (refer to Section 5.2.1). In fact, this cost penalty drastically diminishes the economic gains achieved through P2P energy trading, eroding approximately 50% of the P2P savings in Case 3 and up to 200% in Case 1. However, as indicated by the total cost markers in Figure 5.6, the substantial remuneration from flexibility services generally outweighs these operational losses, ensuring that the mechanism remains economically beneficial for the community overall. This also suggests that when external flexibility rewards are high, the community's operating point is dictated primarily by external price signals rather than local market prices. Since the vast majority of this flexibility is provided by

Figure 5.5 – Example of flexibility activation for a single day in Case 3 under the fixed rate contract. The top panel shows the SDR mechanism, and the bottom panel shows the MMR mechanism. The red line indicates the downward regulation requested by the grid.

the collective battery (Figure 5.4), a centralized strategy utilizing only the community battery could be a preferable alternative. This would safeguard increases in consumers bills while still delivering the required grid services.

5.3 Conclusion

Overall, the results show that internal energy pricing models can effectively address grid security and system-level efficiency when combined with complementary coordination mechanisms. The capacity tariff can be a reliable instrument for reducing collective peaks, especially under RTP when synchronized consumer behavior would otherwise cause severe peaks. There is no clear distinction in performance when comparing both internal pricing mechanisms (i.e. the MMR and the SDR). Its impact on the operational efficiency (i.e. the energy-part of the consumer bill) is furthermore limited, especially in systems with sufficient flexibility. However, the analysis reveals an inherent limitation: the capacity tariff only targets peak offtake and does not fully address injection-driven congestion, especially under strong market price incentives. If the grid is injection-constrained, a more targeted solution could be warranted. For example, one could reserve capacity of the collective battery or limit its discharge rates during congestion windows.

Clearer distinctions between the MMR and the SDR emerge when flexibility is explicitly provided. Although the community consistently has ample technical flexibility to meet external requirements, internal price formation significantly affects the willingness to activate this potential. Under the MMR, flexibility activation is more constrained because changes in individual injections or offtake directly influence the local market price, thereby increasing the opportunity cost of participation. Under SDR, however, prices are decoupled from marginal local actions,

Figure 5.6 – Decomposition of the total consumer cost under the explicit flexibility mechanism. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, and case 3: higher flexibility.

so flexibility is activated more readily. These results suggest that although technical capability is not a limiting factor in our case study, internal prices can partially erode economic incentives for providing flexibility. That said, the community does have an economic incentive to provide flexibility most days.

6 Provision mechanisms for auction-based local energy trading models

6.1 Mechanism formulation

Similarly to previously presented models, the auction-based local energy trading model presented in this section is based on the energy-sharing auction-based model presented in Deliverable 2.3 of U2Demo [2].

The main difference is the explicit introduction of the grid connection into the model, which affects energy sharing within the community through the different flexibility services which it requires. The main model extensions are developed in D2.4 based on the work in D2.3: one for kWmax services and the other one for explicit flexibility activation services. The details of each of these models is outlined below.

6.1.1 kWmax service

The kWmax service is a capacity-based service. It focuses on keeping the community's maximum offtake and injection volumes below a predetermined maximum value, referred to as the kWmax value. For the auction-based local energy trading model, the offtake and injection volumes correspond to the volumes submitted by individual households to the local market, but which were not cleared (due to uncompetitive pricing or lack of supply/demand on the other side).

This kWmax value can be fixed over the entire contract period, in which case we refer to it as a "Constant" kWmax contract, or it can vary over time, in which case we refer to it as a "Dynamic" kWmax contract. The model developed in this section allows to investigate both contract types. To respect this kWmax contract, irrespective of its type, the model gives the possibility to investigate both the rule-based approach and a tariff-based mechanisms presented in Sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3.

The model used to implement both mechanisms is the same, and is presented below.

Assumptions

While the local auction-based market clearing engine developed in Deliverable 2.3 [2] was a two-step lexicographic optimisation including a redistributive objective in the second optimisation step, the market clearing engine developed in this deliverable is a single-step model, only aiming to maximise social welfare. The main reasoning behind this choice is that while Deliverable 2.3 focused on internal energy sharing, thereby bringing the question of internal redistribution of local energy sharing, Deliverable 2.4 focuses more on the interaction of the community with the external system through flexibility services, which is only valued from an economic perspective through the revenue/savings generated by the flexibility service.

The orders (offer orders and demand orders) submitted by the community members to the market represent the net positions of each member after they have run an individual asset optimisation algorithm, which aims to maximise self-consumption. This net position is submitted to the local market as several steps, with each step corresponding to a different price. The size and price of each step depends on the community member's pricing behaviour.

Deliverable 2.3 [2] also showed that the pricing behaviour of the community members strongly affects the market outcome, particularly the volumes cleared in the local market. This pricing behaviour is set by fixing a share of total supply or demand respectively above the retailer's injection price or below the retailer's offtake price. To focus on the impact of external flexibility services on the community's energy sharing, this behavioural aspect which represents the

share of volumes bid at a price below offtake / above injection price is assumed fixed throughout all scenarios. It is set to 20% for all community members, except the collective battery and collective PV assets, for which it is set to 80%, as energy sharing is the main purpose of these assets. The chosen values for the share of over-priced supply and under-priced demand allow to have enough volumes traded at non-retail prices in the local market, while ensuring enough offer (supply) volumes below market clearing price and demand volumes above clearing price. The local market clearing price itself is set to be the marginal offer.

Regarding the grid representation, the community is modelled as a Closed Distribution System (CDS), with a single point of connection to the public grid.

Mathematical formulation

Sets & indexes

- T : Set of timesteps
- O : Set of all orders
- O_t : Set of orders active at timestep $t \in T$
- $S_{o,t}$: Set of price-volume curve steps for order $o \in O$ at timestep $t \in T$
- \mathcal{D} : Set of demand orders, $\mathcal{D} \subseteq O$
- \mathcal{S} : Set of supply/offer orders, $\mathcal{S} \subseteq O$

Parameters

Order parameters

- $p_{o,t,s}$: Price of step s for order o at timestep t (€/kWh)
- $v_{o,t,s}^{\min}$: Minimum volume of step s for order o at timestep t (kWh)
- $v_{o,t,s}^{\max}$: Maximum volume of step s for order o at timestep t (kWh)
- Δt : Timestep duration in hours (default: 1.0)

The *Retailer parameters* and the *Grid parameters* are added to the model formulation in Deliverable 2.4.

Retailer parameters

- $P_{o,t}^{grid}$: retail prices for each community member for offtake / injection to the grid

$$P_{o,t}^{grid} = \begin{cases} P_{m,t}^{offtake} & \text{if order } o \in \mathcal{D} \text{ (demand), where order } o \text{ is submitted by member } m \\ P_{m,t}^{injection} & \text{if order } o \in \mathcal{S} \text{ (supply/offer), where order } o \text{ is submitted by member } m \end{cases}$$

Grid parameters

- $C_{total,t}$: The maximum grid injection / offtake capacity for the community (in kW). Depending on the implemented mechanism, this corresponds either to the physical grid connection point capacity $C_{physical}$ or the contractual grid connection point capacity limit C_t^{kWmax} which the community cannot exceed to respect the kWmax contract .

- $P_t^{grid\ tariff}$: Grid tariff added by the grid operator to retail prices in order to discourage peaks at specific times of the day at timestep t (€/kWh).
- P_t^{LOL} : Price of curtailment for the community as a whole m at timestep t (€/kWh).

Sign convention

$$d_o = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if order } o \in \mathcal{D} \text{ (demand)} \\ -1 & \text{if order } o \in \mathcal{S} \text{ (supply/offer)} \end{cases}$$

Price caps & floors

- P_{\max}^{offer} : Offer price cap, set to 10,000 €/kWh
- P_{\max}^{demand} : Demand price cap, set to $P_{m,t}^{\text{offtake}}$ €/kWh
- P_{\min}^{offer} : Offer price floor set to $P_{m,t}^{\text{injection}}$ €/kWh
- P_{\min}^{demand} : Demand price floor set to 0 €/kWh

Decision Variables

Binary Variables

- $a_{o,t,s}$: Acceptance of step s for order o at timestep t

Continuous Variables

- $v_{o,t,s}$: Cleared volume of step s for order o at timestep t (kWh)
- $V_{o,t}$: Total cleared volume for order o at timestep t (kWh)

kWmax service model formulation

The optimisation is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{v_{o,t,s}, v_{o,t}^{grid}, v_t^{LOL}} \text{Community welfare} = \\ & \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{o \in O_t} d_o \left(\sum_{s \in S_{o,t}} v_{o,t,s} p_{o,t,s} \right) - P_{o,t}^{grid} v_{o,t}^{grid} - P_t^{LOL} v_t^{LOL} \end{aligned} \quad (6.1a)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{s.t. } & v_{o,t,s}^{\min} a_{o,t,s} \leq v_{o,t,s} \leq v_{o,t,s}^{\max} a_{o,t,s} & \forall o \in O, t \in T, s \in S_{o,t} & (6.1b) \\
 & \sum_{o \in O_t} \sum_{s \in S_{o,t}} d_o \cdot v_{o,t,s} = 0 & \forall t \in T & (6.1c) \\
 & V_{o,t} = \sum_{s \in S_{o,t}} v_{o,t,s} & \forall o \in O, t \in T & (6.1d) \\
 & a_{o,t,s} \in \{0, 1\} & \forall o \in O, t \in T, s \in S_{o,t} & (6.1e) \\
 & v_{o,t,s} \geq 0 & \forall o \in O, t \in T, s \in S_{o,t} & (6.1f) \\
 & V_{o,t} \geq 0 & \forall o \in O, t \in T & (6.1g) \\
 & v_{o,t}^{grid} \geq 0 & \forall o \in O, t \in T & (6.1h) \\
 & v_t^{LOL} \geq 0 & \forall t \in T & (6.1i) \\
 & V_{o,t} + v_{o,t}^{grid} \leq \sum_{s \in S_{o,t}} v_{o,t,s}^{\max} & \forall o \in O, t \in T & (6.1j) \\
 & \sum_{o \in O_t} (V_{o,t} + v_{o,t}^{grid}) + v_t^{LOL} = \sum_{o \in O_t} \sum_{s \in S_{o,t}} v_{o,t,s}^{\max} & \forall t \in T & (6.1k) \\
 & \sum_{o \in O_t} v_{o,t}^{grid} \leq C_{total,t} & \forall t \in T \text{ if order } o \in \mathcal{D} \text{ (demand)} & (6.1l) \\
 & \sum_{o \in O_t} v_{o,t}^{grid} \leq C_{total,t} & \forall t \in T \text{ if order } o \in \mathcal{S} \text{ (supply/offer)} & (6.1m)
 \end{aligned}$$

The objective function maximises social welfare for volumes cleared in the local auction and the minimises costs due to interaction with the grid. This second term represents a change from Deliverable 2.3 [2] and thereby creates an arbitrage situation for the community, which must choose between internal price signals and external grid price signals (through the retail prices which participants are exposed to).

Constraints 6.1j and 6.1k indicate that the volume offtaken from or injected to the grid represented the non-cleared share of bid volume $V_{o,t}$, unless there is some LOL (Loss of Load) to prevent physical infeasibilities.

Constraints 6.1l and 6.1m indicate that aggregated offtake and injection volumes from the community members need to be below a certain threshold, which is either physical or contractual.

Rule-based mechanism

In the rule-based mechanism, the kWmax threshold is applied by setting $C_{total,t} = C_t^{kWmax}$. This effectively makes the contractual kWmax value a hard constraint which the community cannot exceed.

Tariff-based mechanism

In the tariff-based mechanism, the kWmax threshold is not applied explicitly. Instead, $C_{total,t} = C_{physical}$, which simply states that the community cannot inject or withdraw more than is physically possible, but no consideration is given to the contractual kWmax limit. Instead, the tariff-based mechanism modifies the value of $P_{o,t}^{grid}$ by adding the value $P_t^{grid tariff}$ to it. The ensuing relative increase in price compared to other timesteps can potentially change the hours where community members prefer to interact with the grid rather than share energy internally.

6.1.2 Explicit flexibility activation

Instead of focusing on limiting the peak withdrawal / injection to the grid over a given timespan, as is the case for the kWmax service, the explicit flexibility activation service consists of up or down deviations from the baseline schedule at specific times, in exchange for a financial compensation. In this case, the service is therefore energy-based, and not capacity based.

This service runs after the energy sharing model outlined in Deliverable 2.3 [2], in order to adjust the volumes offtaken from the grid based on the requirements of the DSO.

The changes in grid withdrawal / injection levels at the community level translate into changes in operational profiles at the household level. Activated flexibility volumes must therefore respect the operational constraints of the assets in each household. Therefore, after the energy sharing auction model has run a first time, the individual optimisation problem for each household is run again, taking into account the operational baseline from the first run, and including the new prices for the flexibility activation services in the objective function. In this second individual optimisation problem, the objective is to maximise the revenues from providing the flexibility activation service, while minimising the additional retail costs due to changes in operational profiles causing less injection to the community/grid and/or more offtake from the community/grid.

A summary of the workflow is provided in 6.1:

Figure 6.1 – Workflow diagram for explicit flexibility activation valorisation

The rest of this section details the specific model which will be used.

Assumptions

The activation price and volume of flexibility activation coming from the DSO is expected to be known in advance. The optimisation horizon is therefore done over the 24 hours of the next day with perfect forecast. While this is an optimistic assumption, it provides an upper bound on the expected profits from providing flexibility activation services.

The planning for flexibility activation is considered to be done for each household individually. This implies that households are not aware of the amount of flexibility which other households

can or want to provide. Households therefore only consider the total flexibility request sent to the community for their flexibility activation scheduling. The total activation demand is not disaggregated to the household level, keeping a decentralised decision making. This uncoordinated flexibility scheduling implies that the total volume submitted by households can exceed the total flexibility activation request to the community. In this case, the flexibility activation revenue for the community is calculated by capping the total provided volume to the requested volume. The disaggregation of the activated volume amongst participants is not considered in this model, but could be done by linearly scaling activation profiles of households based on their weighted contribution to the total volume provided originally.

Mathematical formulation of individual asset optimisation for explicit flexibility services

The individual optimisation problem is formulated as follows:

Flexibility parameters

- $P_{up,t}$: price for upward regulation service at timestep t .
- $P_{down,t}$: price for downward regulation service at timestep t .
- $x_{imb,baseline,t}$: net position of household (energy not self-consumed / self-produced) at timestep t after the first round of individual optimisation for energy sharing auction, before flexibility service provision. This position will either be settled with the market clearing within the community or exchanged with the grid.
- $x_{household,grid,baseline,t}$: volume injected / offtaken from the grid by the household based on the outcome of step 1 (energy sharing), before flexibility activation.
- $x_{flexrequest,t}$: total flexibility activation demand from the DSO at timestep t (in kWh).
- $FlexType_t$: direction of flexibility activation demand from DSO. If $FlexType=UPWARD$, only upward flexibility can be activated, and vice versa for $FlexType=DOWNWARD$, only downward flexibility can be activated. When $FlexType$ is neither $UPWARD$ nor $DOWNWARD$ (no flex), the household can still adjust its baseline up or down, but will receive no remuneration (corresponding $P_{up,t}$ and $P_{down,t}$ values are set to 0).

Decision variables

- $x_{down,t}$: downward deviation from the baseline net position of the household at timestep t (kWh). For net producers, this corresponds to a decrease in production, while for net consumers, this corresponds to an increase in consumption.
- $x_{up,t}$: upward deviation from the baseline net position of the household at timestep t (kWh). For net producers, this corresponds to an increase in production, while for net consumers, this corresponds to a decrease in consumption.
- $x_{current,imb,t}$: imbalance from the current individual optimization (second round). The injected volume is considered as out while the offtake power as in.
- $f_{up,t}$: Flexible upward power provided by the household.
- $f_{down,t}$: Flexible downward power provided by the household.

- $b_{down,t}$: boolean determining whether downward flexibility is activated or not.
- $b_{up,t}$: boolean determining whether upward flexibility is activated or not.

Mathematical formulation

$$\max \quad P_{inj,t} x_{current,imb,t}^{out} - P_{off,t} x_{current,imb,t}^{in} - \text{asset_cost_functions} + \sum_t (P_{up,t} f_{up,t} + P_{down,t} f_{down,t}) \quad (6.2a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad (6.2b)$$

$$\Delta_{imb,t} = x_{current,imb,t}^{out} - x_{current,imb,t}^{in} - x_{imb,baseline,t} \quad (6.2c)$$

$$x_{up,t} - x_{down,t} = \Delta_{imb,t} \quad (6.2d)$$

$$x_{current,imb,t}^{in} \geq x_{imb,baseline,t}^{in} - x_{household,grid,baseline,t} \quad (6.2e)$$

$$x_{current,imb,t}^{out} \geq x_{imb,baseline,t}^{out} - x_{household,grid,baseline,t} \quad (6.2f)$$

$$0 \leq x_{up,t} \leq M b_{up,t}, \quad (6.2g)$$

$$0 \leq x_{down,t} \leq M b_{down,t}, \quad (6.2h)$$

$$b_{up,t} + b_{down,t} \leq 1, \quad (6.2i)$$

$$b_{up,t}, b_{down,t} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (6.2j)$$

$$\text{If flex type is "FlexType.UPWARD": } b_{down,t} = 0, \quad (6.2k)$$

$$\text{If flex type is "FlexType.DOWNWARD": } b_{up,t} = 0, \quad (6.2l)$$

$$0 \leq f_{down,t} \leq x_{flex\ request,t}, \quad (6.2m)$$

$$0 \leq f_{up,t} \leq x_{flex\ request,t}, \quad (6.2n)$$

$$f_{down,t} \leq x_{down,t}, \quad (6.2o)$$

$$f_{up,t} \leq x_{up,t}, \quad (6.2p)$$

$$\text{All operational constraints,} \quad (6.2q)$$

$$\text{Power and activation variables are fixed for all assets except batteries.} \quad (6.2r)$$

6.2 Results and analysis of auction-based energy trading models

The following KPIs are analysed on an aggregated level for the whole community over the entire simulation timespan:

- Exchanged volumes: the energy volumes (in kW) exchanged within the community by the local auction clearing engine. The higher this value, the more autonomous the community is from the grid.
- Community energy bill savings: the bill savings resulting from the implementation of the local auction market, compared to a reference scenario without any local exchanges, where each household pays/gets paid for their excess consumption/production based on retail contracts for offtake/injection.

While the community's social welfare is used in the objective function for clearing the local market, the community's bill savings is chosen instead as the KPI to measure the financial benefit of the implemented mechanism, as it better reflects the real benefits which community members get from implementing the evaluated market mechanism.

Indeed, the social welfare is calculated based on the submitted prices of demand and supply on the market, while the community bills used to calculate the bill savings are calculated based on the cleared prices of demand and supply, which are the prices which community members will benefit from after market clearing. This also makes the KPI more comparable to cost reduction-based KPIs in other models.

The reference value for each of these KPIs is shown in Tables 6.1 and 6.2 for all baseline scenarios. These baseline scenarios correspond to the model results with local auction clearing but without kWmax service, for each case (1,2 and 3) and for each retail contract type (flat or dynamic):

	Flat retail contract	Dynamic retail contract
Case 1	6016.3	2881.8
Case 2	24954.8	15010.0
Case 3	32577.4	21827.7

Table 6.1 – Exchanged volumes (in kW) for each baseline scenario, aggregated over all community members over a year

Without kWmax service, it seems that more volumes are exchanged when applying flat retail contracts than dynamic retail contracts. This can be due to the mismatch between the community’s available volumes for exchange and the dynamic retail pricing.

The total community bill, corresponding to the total volumes purchased minus the total volumes sold (in €), is shown for each baseline in Table 6.2. The community savings for each scenario will be calculated by subtracting the scenario-specific community bill from the baseline community bill.

	Flat retail contract	Dynamic retail contract
Case 1	68715.4	71851.6
Case 2	69629.5	74134.0
Case 3	61482.2	64778.2

Table 6.2 – Total community bill (purchase minus sale, in €) for each baseline scenario, aggregated over all community members over a year

6.2.1 kWmax service

The impact of the kWmax service on each of these metrics is shown below in relative terms:

$$\frac{KPI_{kWmax} - KPI_{baseline}}{KPI_{baseline}} \tag{6.3}$$

The results are presented separately for the rule-based and tariff-based mechanisms.

Rule-based mechanism

Within the rule-based mechanism, the kWmax constraint is applied either as a constant value or as a dynamic value. The performance of each mechanism in the different baselines is shown below.

When kWmax is set to the constant value $kWmax = 200kW$, the following results are obtained.

Figure 6.2 – Impact of CONSTANT kWmax = 200 kW rule-based mechanism on community savings in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

Figure 6.3 – Impact of CONSTANT kWmax = 200 kW rule-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

Setting a constant kWmax constraint barely seems to have any effect on the community’s energy sharing when using the value provided in the dataset. A decreased kWmax value was therefore applied for each case, taking the average of the DYNAMIC kWmax values over all simulated days. This results in a constant kWmax of respectively 178kW, 89KW and 130kW for cases 1, 2, and 3.

Figure 6.4 – Impact of case-dependent CONSTANT kWmax rule-based mechanism on community savings in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

Figure 6.5 – Impact of case-dependent CONSTANT kWmax rule-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

Further decreasing the value of the constant kWmax threshold clearly starts to impact energy sharing within the energy community. However, compared to the baseline, the results do not show a major change in either community savings or exchanged energy volumes. This indicates that most of the time, the community stays below the chosen threshold and only needs to shift its schedule at very few peaks. More aggressive kWmax contracts could have resulted in larger schedule changes.

The community savings are particularly increased when considering dynamic energy tariffs, and particularly in Case 2. Results are therefore dependent on the community’s energy portfolio, and the peaks which this portfolio can cause. Regarding traded volumes, it is interesting to observe that Case 1 with dynamic retail tariffs see a significant increase in traded volumes,

although this does not translate to community savings. In general however, an increase in internally traded volumes is highly correlated with an increase in community benefits. This shows that the grid constraints force the community to exchange more volumes internally, which turns out to be financially beneficial for it, even though this financial benefit was not considered initially by the social welfare maximisation objective in the local market clearing scenario without kWmax constraints.

The results for the dynamic kWmax value are shown below:

Figure 6.6 – Impact of DYNAMIC kWmax rule-based mechanism on community savings in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

Figure 6.7 – Impact of DYNAMIC kWmax rule-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

The results show a very similar pattern to the CONSTANT kWmax mechanism with adjusted case-dependent values. This indicates that the increase in traded energy from kWmax constraint is not very time-sensitive. Volumes are rather increasingly cleared internally instead of

being offtaken or injected to the grid, rather than being shifted across timesteps.

This can be explained by the fact that the bid generation algorithms do not take these grid constraints into account, and therefore the same bid volumes are available on the local market. What changes is the value of clearing a certain volume locally compared to offtaking from or injecting to the grid.

Tariff-based mechanism

The results for the energy grid tariff-based mechanism are shown in Figures 6.8 and 6.9.

Figure 6.8 – Impact of energy grid tariff-based mechanism on community savings in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

Figure 6.9 – Impact of energy grid tariff-based mechanism on total exchanged volumes in different scenarios (in % compared to the relevant baseline)

A clear distinction can be made in this case between the results with flat energy retail tariffs and dynamic energy retail tariffs. For the former, adding the energy grid tariffs has a negligible or even a detrimental impact. On the other hand, for the dynamic tariffs the benefits in terms of community savings are much more considerable compared to the rule-based mechanism. This indicates that grid tariffs can act either with or against retail tariffs, depending on the community's asset portfolio and original operational profile.

In terms of community savings, the energy grid tariff-based mechanism seems to have a higher impact than the rule-based mechanisms analysed above. It seems that the grid tariffs, which are lower from 00:00 to 06:00 and 22:00 to 00:00, are well adapted to the current community's energy portfolio (case 1). As the portfolio changes (more PV but less battery capacity in case 2, more PV and more battery capacity in case 3), the positive impact of grid tariffs decreases, although it stays positive.

As the tariff-based mechanism does not guarantee that the community's net position with regards to the grid stays below the contractual kWmax limit, we also analyse for this mechanism whether the energy grid tariffs have enabled the community to stay below the kWmax threshold or not. To stay concise, we only show the results in Figure 6.10 for case 3, as kWmax constraints are always respected in case 1 and 2.

Figure 6.10 shows the baseline profile (community net position after market clearing without grid tariffs) in black, the community's grid net position after market clearing with grid tariffs in blue, and the implicit offtake and injection kWmax contracts in different shades of red. Four different scenarios are shown, showing different combinations of energy retail tariffs (flat or dynamic) and kWmax contracts (constant or dynamic).

Several observations can be made from these plots:

- The grid tariffs don't necessarily reduce maximum injection / offtake values, but rather shift them to different times of the day.
- Grid tariffs can worsen peaks at particularly timesteps, causing the community to exceed its contractual kWmax threshold, while the baseline case without grid tariffs would have respected this constraint. This is particularly the case for the grid injection volume at the end of the day (23:00), which probably corresponds to battery discharge to reach the required State of Charge of 50% by the end of the day.
- The kWmax contractual limit is exceeded more often with the dynamic retail tariffs than with the flat retail tariffs, irrespective of whether the kWmax contract is constant or dynamic. This implies that the retailer's dynamic tariffs are not aligned with the DSO's grid tariffs.

An important conclusion from the implicit kWmax mechanism is that introducing grid tariffs can incentivize the community to consume slightly more internally, but will not necessarily reduce peak consumption/injection to the grid. Therefore, if a capacity tariff is applied to the community, no or even negative financial benefits would be observed by the community when introducing a kWmax mechanism.

Grid net position (in kW) of community for Case 3, with flat retail contract and CONSTANT implicit kWmax contract

(a) Case 3 with flat retail tariffs and constant kWmax contract

Grid net position (in kW) of community for Case 3, with flat retail contract and DYNAMIC implicit kWmax contract

(b) Case 3 with flat retail tariffs and dynamic kWmax contract

Grid net position (in kW) of community for Case 3, with dynamic retail contract and CONSTANT implicit kWmax contract

(c) Case 3 with dynamic retail tariffs and constant kWmax contract

Grid net position (in kW) of community for Case 3, with dynamic retail contract and DYNAMIC implicit kWmax contract

(d) Case 3 with dynamic retail tariffs and dynamic kWmax contract

Figure 6.10 – Grid net position of community over simulated days for different tariff-based kWmax scenarios in Case 3.

6.2.2 Explicit flexibility activation

The results of the explicit flexibility activation are also analysed for all three cases and the two retail tariffs: flat and dynamic. However, the KPIs are not the same, as the flexibility activation only happens after the internal auction has fixed the baseline schedule within the community. Any deviations, therefore does not affect exchanged volumes within the community, but only volumes exchanged with the grid. The results will therefore only present the overall flexibility revenues (as a percentage of the original community bill with energy sharing but before flexibility activation) and the operational deviation of each household from its baseline schedule (the baseline is taken after the internal auction for energy sharing).

The results shown in Figure 6.11 show that revenues from flexibility activation can be substantial. The observed results should however be considered with care, as the assumptions of perfect foresight provide overly optimistic results. However, this provides a useful upper bound and order of magnitude of expected savings, and provides insights on the mechanism's behaviour across different scenarios.

Figure 6.11 shows that the difference in flexibility activation revenues is much more dependent on the case (and therefore the portfolio mix of the community) than the reference retail tariff. In general, the installed battery capacity is the main driver for flexibility activation revenues. Indeed, in case 2 has reduced capacity for the collective battery capacity, while case 3 has increased battery capacity across all households, and this change in installed capacity is reflected in the received flexibility revenue.

Figure 6.11 – Comparison of flex activation revenues as a share of community bill after energy sharing, across cases and retail tariff scenarios. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, case 3: higher flexibility.

Figure 6.12 shows that the collective battery is the unique contributor to the community’s flexibility deviations in Case 1 (reference case). In Case 2 and 3, other households contribute to flexibility activation as well. In Case 2, the Aloha (Pavilion 1) is particularly notable, as it is assigned additional PV and battery capacities. The level of asset over-dimensioning of each household is therefore essential to determine the amount of flexibility activated. However, in all cases, the load deviation profiles (compared to the baseline) follow a similar pattern across households, with upward deviations at the same time steps across households and downward deviations at other specific time steps across households. The specific operational constraints of each household therefore don’t seem to impact the time steps at which load deviations are optimal.

(a) Household profile deviations in case 1 with dynamic retail tariffs

(b) Household profile deviations in case 2 with dynamic retail tariffs

(c) Household profile deviations in case 3 with dynamic retail tariffs

Figure 6.12 – Household profile deviations across studied cases with dynamic retail tariffs. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, case 3: higher flexibility.

6.3 Conclusion

For the kWmax service, the comparison of results across studies and retail contract scenarios shows that in almost all scenarios, the addition of a kWmax contract (either explicitly through a rule-based mechanism or implicitly through a tariff-based mechanism) increases the exchanged volumes within the community, which thereby also increases community savings. Counter-intuitively, adding constraints improves the performance of the community.

This increase in internally cleared volumes can be explained by two factors: the increase in accepted volumes for given bid curves on one side, and the increase in accepted volumes due to adjusted bid curves (adjusted net positions of community members) on the other side. The former occurs in the rule-based kWmax service, where participants submit the same bidding curves but additional constraints are added to the optimisation problem. The latter occurs in the tariff-based kWmax service, where participants submit adjusted bidding curves. This curve adjustment across time steps is encouraged by the grid tariffs added in the individual optimisation algorithms used to generate the bid volumes.

For the rule-based mechanism, the additional cleared volumes indicate that certain energy sharing bid volumes, which would have been rejected without a kWmax contract, end up being accepted, although they are suboptimal from a community social welfare perspective. Indeed, in the auction mechanism, the exchanged volumes depend on the point of intersection of demand and supply curves. The shape of these curves is determined by the market participation aggressiveness of community members introduced in Deliverable 2.3. Non-cleared volumes represent over-priced supply and under-priced demand bids, which are not acceptable from a social welfare perspective. The increase in cleared volumes indicates those bids are now acceptable, as they allow to avoid facing the kWmax constraints which are even more detrimental. The kWmax constraints thereby unlock some of the internal "price flexibility" within the community, although the net position of each household (volumes cleared at community level + volumes exchanged with the grid) remains the same.

The paradox is that the increased acceptance of over-priced supply and under-priced demand bids ends up increasing community savings, despite decreasing social welfare. This can be linked back to the additional term representing grid costs in the objective function. The utility of consumers' demand curve in the local market does not correspond one-to-one with the utility of buyers in the wholesale market. Indeed, demand volumes that are not cleared in the local market can be provided by the grid. There is therefore an additional arbitrage to make between grid prices, which are necessarily worse than local prices, and accepting over-priced supply and under-priced demand bids in the local market, which end up increasing local market prices.

It could be tempting to maximise community savings by maximising the volumes cleared internally instead of maximising social welfare. However, this could encourage "aggressive" members to set bid prices at cap/floor prices, thereby maximising benefits, as the volumes would be cleared irrespective of submitted prices. This would eventually bring back internal market prices to cap/floor prices (i.e. retail prices), defeating the purpose of energy sharing within the community. Using social welfare maximisation instead of cleared volume maximisation in the objective function is therefore encouraged to avoid abusive bidding behaviour from "aggressive" members.

For the tariff-based mechanism, the combination of dynamic energy retailer tariffs with dynamic grid tariffs brings particularly interesting results. Looking at overall exchanged volumes and community savings, it seems that grid tariffs improve the volumes exchanged within the com-

munity: the net positions of community members are better aligned. However, this increase in internally exchanged volumes simultaneously creates an increase in grid injection peaks. In this case, grid tariffs do not have the hoped effect and worsen grid peaks, showing an unsuited grid tariff mechanism for the given community profile and their retail tariffs. This shows that the interaction between community members' profile, their energy retail tariffs, and the applied grid tariffs must be carefully studied to determine whether impacts will be beneficial or detrimental for the grid.

For the explicit flexibility activation service, in the context of this study, the revenues generated are considerable. While overall revenues are expected to decrease when introducing uncertainty on activated volumes, times, and prices, the magnitude of these upper-bound results found in this study are still encouraging. However, these flexibility activations result in much more peaky household operational profiles, also outside of flexibility activation time windows, as flexibility assets must compensate for the activated energy in the other direction. This could create unintended grid congestion issues at other time steps, if the activation compensations are done at times where the grid is already close to facing congestion. Activation signals from the DSO should therefore carefully be designed depending on the portfolio of assets likely to respond to this activation signal.

These conclusions show how differently the studied flexibility services can impact both grid operations and community financial benefits. While the rule-based kWmax service has undeniable advantages to limit peak loads, its financial incentive depends strongly on the level of congestion already present in the grid and the level of intra-community exchanges. On the other hand, the efficiency of the tariff-based kWmax service to reduce peak loads is not guaranteed and depends strongly on the compatibility of grid tariff signals with retailer tariff signals. Finally, the flexibility services' impact of the community's peak consumption is not considered during activation decision, but the financial benefits of such activations can nonetheless be encouraging enough for community members to participate.

Further work

Regarding the rule-based kWmax service, further work should be done to understand the impact of individual community members' bidding curves on the relative benefit of local exchanges vs. exchanges with the grid. This is particularly true when communities are dominated by an over-dimensioned asset, such as in Case 1, whose operational profile strongly influences the community's peaks, and whose bidding aggressiveness can strongly influence the extent to which volumes are cleared within the community versus exchanged with the grid.

Regarding the tariff-based kWmax service, more contexts need to be analysed to understand the interdependencies between a certain energy community's operational profile, the retailer's price signals that community members subscribe to, and the DSO's grid tariffs, which the community members are exposed to. Depending on the extent of their compatibility, price signals can be beneficial or, on the contrary detrimental to energy sharing within the community.

From the perspective of the flexibility activation service, further work should include stochastic models, with uncertainty on both the activation times, activation volumes, and activation prices, to see how much this reduces revenues. The model should also be run on a rolling horizon to represent real-life decision-making conditions, with activation requests being communicated to the community shortly before the actual flexibility service is provided.

7 Provision mechanisms for peer-to-peer energy trading models

In this section, the flexibility services and mechanisms to be incorporated into the P2P energy trading model of [2, Section 7.1] are presented and tested separately. The flexibility mechanisms considered are the following: (i) a rule-based mechanism to comply with a kWmax service; (ii) two tariff-based mechanisms (ToU and capacity tariffs); and (iii) an explicit flexibility mechanism for the case of flexibility provision for market-based services with known and unknown activation periods.

7.1 Flexibility services and mechanisms modeling

In this section, details on the modeling of each of the flexibility mechanisms used are presented.

7.1.1 Rule-based mechanism for kWmax service

In the following, the kWmax service is modeled using a rule-based mechanism in the P2P energy trading model. This mechanism is modeled by introducing a constraint to the optimisation that limits the net consumption of the EC to a specified limit σ_t .

Finding suitable kWmax limits The net consumption of the EC varies significantly during each day, therefore the kWmax constraint used is set individually for each time step of each day. To set this value, first the P2P trading optimisation is run for a single day, with the energy trades between the EC and the retailer only being constrained by pre-established contractual limits. Based on the result of this optimisation, the net consumption $P_t^{\text{net},r}$ of the EC from the retailer in the unconstrained case is computed as follows:

$$P_t^{\text{net},r} = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} P_{r,l,t}^{\text{sell}} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} P_{r,g,t}^{\text{buy}}. \quad (7.1)$$

where $\sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} P_{r,l,t}^{\text{sell}}$ is the sum of the amount of energy that the retailer entity r sells to each of the EC members and $\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} P_{r,g,t}^{\text{buy}}$ is the sum of the amount of energy that the retailer entity buys from each of the EC members in each time step t . Note that the elements in $P_{r,g,t}^{\text{buy}}$ are by convention negative. Thus, the net consumption of the EC is positive when the retailer entity sells more energy to all EC members together than the retailer entity buys from all EC members together. The P2P energy trading model allows for a load reduction by a given value, resulting in $P_{l,t}^{\text{min,load}}$ as the minimum load of each entity in the model. There exists thus a minimum net interaction $P_t^{\text{net,min}}$ of the EC without batteries under the maximum generation $P_{g,t}^{\text{max,gen}}$ of each generation entity of the EC in each time step. This minimum net interaction is computed through.

$$P_t^{\text{net,min}} = - \left(\sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} P_{l,t}^{\text{min,load}} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} P_{g,t}^{\text{max,gen}} \right). \quad (7.2)$$

In the following, only the time steps with $P_t^{\text{net,min}} > 0$ are analyzed, as these are the time steps in which the EC would consume energy from the retailer, if the batteries were not used and the internal generation was not curtailed. For each of those time steps, the net consumption of the EC in the unconstrained case, $P_t^{\text{net},r}$, is then analyzed. Depending on the values of $P_t^{\text{net},r}$ and $P_t^{\text{net,min}}$, the kWmax limit is set for each time step as shown in Table 7.1.

Table 7.1 – Computation of the kWmax limit.

Description	kWmax limit computation
$P_t^{\text{net},r} > P_t^{\text{net},\text{min}}$	$\sigma_t = 0.5(P_t^{\text{net},r} + P_t^{\text{net},\text{min}})$
$P_t^{\text{net},r} \leq P_t^{\text{net},\text{min}}$ and $P_t^{\text{net},r} \geq 0$	$\sigma_t = P_t^{\text{net},r}$
$P_t^{\text{net},r} < 0$	$\sigma_t = P_t^{\text{net},\text{min}}$

Integration into the P2P energy trading algorithm The kWmax constraint is included into the P2P energy trading algorithm by adding an additional constraint on the net interaction of the EC with the retailer. This constraint is expressed as

$$\sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} P_{0,l,t}^{\text{sell}} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} P_{0,g,t}^{\text{buy}} \leq \sigma_t \forall t \in \bar{\mathcal{T}} \quad (7.3)$$

where $\bar{\mathcal{T}}$ denotes all time steps for which a kWmax constraint was set.

7.1.2 Tariff-based mechanisms

In the following, two tariff-based mechanisms that can influence the net consumption of the EC from the retailer are presented. These two tariffs are investigated separately and serve as input to the optimisation problem of the P2P energy trading scheme.

Time-of-use tariff The time-of-use tariff is implemented by adding this tariff to the retailer off-take price.

Capacity tariff The capacity tariff penalises monthly the peak net consumption of the EC from the retailer. However, as the optimisation horizon of the proposed P2P energy trading scheme is one day, the capacity tariff is understood as a tariff penalising the daily peak net consumption of the EC from the retailer. To include the net peak consumption in the optimisation, the variable P_{peak} denoting the peak net consumption throughout the day is added to the optimisation model. This variable is always positive and is defined through the constraint

$$P_{\text{peak}} \geq \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} P_{r,l,t}^{\text{sell}} + \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} P_{r,g,t}^{\text{buy}} \quad \forall t \quad (7.4)$$

where $\sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} P_{r,l,t}^{\text{sell}}$ is the sum of the amount of energy that the retailer entity (which has the index r in the model) sells to each of the EC members and $\sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} P_{r,g,t}^{\text{buy}}$ is the sum of the amount of energy that the retailer entity (which has the index r in the model) buys from each of the EC members in each time step t . Note that the peak net consumption is independent from the time step, as it denotes the peak net consumption over the full day. The capacity tariff is then included in the objective function by adding the term

$$P_{\text{peak}} \lambda_{\text{peak}} \quad (7.5)$$

to the objective function, where λ_{peak} is the capacity tariff. Since the objective function is minimised, this ensures that the minimum possible value is chosen or P_{peak} even though the value for P_{peak} is only bound below in (7.4). The value of the capacity tariff λ_{peak} is an input to the optimisation problem.

7.1.3 Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with unknown flexibility activation periods

This explicit flexibility mechanism aims at quantifying and disaggregating flexibility from the EC without incurring in a rescheduling when flexibility is activated. The only flexible assets are, thus, the community battery and the batteries of each member. For each of these batteries, the possible deviation from the baseline operation is quantified and then shown how this flexibility is offered over the time steps of each day. Note that flexibility activation periods are assumed to be unknown to the EC, which consequently has a direct impact on the resulting flexibility disaggregation over the time steps of each day. Finally, the chosen mechanism for simulating the activation is described. In this context, downward flexibility is provided by charging the battery (resulting in an increased net consumption of the EC/decreased net injection into the grid), while upward flexibility is provided by discharging the battery (resulting in a decreased net consumption of the EC/increased injection into the grid).

Flexibility quantification for each day To quantify the daily available flexibility, a day-ahead scheduling is performed by solving the P2P optimisation problem with the possibility of reducing the loads by 30 % and the generation by 100 % of the forecast. After obtaining the day-ahead scheduling, the maximum and minimum SOC of each battery over the whole day, $SOC_{max,i}$ and $SOC_{min,i}$, can be determined. These values, together with the technical limits on the SOC, $SOC_{max,i}^{tech}$ and $SOC_{min,i}^{tech}$, and the capacity of each battery, E_i , are used to determine the daily amount of energy which could be charged or discharged without jeopardising the existing scheduling. The amount of flexibility that can be offered is computed by taking into account the charge and discharge efficiencies ν_i of each battery, resulting in

$$(SOC_{max,i}^{tech} - SOC_{max,i})E_i\nu_i = F_i^d \quad (7.6)$$

$$(SOC_{min,i} - SOC_{min,i}^{tech})\frac{E_i}{\nu_i} = F_i^u \quad (7.7)$$

where F_i^d is the daily available downward flexibility and F_i^u is the daily available upward flexibility of each battery i .

Flexibility quantification for each time step This step comprises two parts. First, the time steps are separated for each battery into those where the battery can provide upward or downward flexibility. In each time step only one of the types of flexibility is possible for each battery. Then, the technical limit on additional charging or discharging in each time step is determined. As charging and discharging of the batteries are mutually exclusive actions, downward flexibility can only be offered in time steps in which according to the day-ahead schedule the battery is already charging. Similarly, upward flexibility can only be offered when according to the day-ahead schedule the battery is discharging in this time step. Therefore, only those time steps in which the battery under analysis is charging are selected as time steps in which downward flexibility may be offered, while in all other time steps upward flexibility may be offered. The latter includes time steps in which according to the day-ahead schedule the battery is neither charging nor discharging (as a default). To quantify the technically allowed amount of flexibility in each of the time steps, the amount of energy charged or discharged according to the day-ahead schedule has to be deducted from the technical limit for charging and discharging of each battery. This gives the technical limit to providing flexibility in each time step, independent from the flexibility which can be offered for the whole day.

Flexibility disaggregation over the time steps In the next step, the daily available flexibility is disaggregated over the time steps of the day, with the aim of maximising the EC remuner-

ation. This is done separately for the upward and downward flexibility. As the remuneration for activated flexibility is known for each time step, this information can be used to identify the time steps in which providing flexibility is most profitable. First, only the time steps in which the remuneration for the flexibility is beneficial for the EC are identified. In the case of providing upward flexibility, only the time steps with a positive price for providing flexibility are considered, while for the case of downward flexibility, only the time steps with a negative price for providing flexibility are profitable for the EC. These time steps are then ordered by price. Starting with the time step with the highest reward for flexibility, the minimum between the daily available flexibility and the technically allowed charging/discharging values is set as available flexibility in this time step. The offered flexibility is deducted from the daily available flexibility and the process is repeated for the next time step until all time steps are assigned a flexibility offer value. This is done for both the upward and downward flexibility and for each battery.

Flexibility activation The activation of the flexibility is simulated based on two variables. First, a binary variable indicates whether flexibility in a certain time step is being activated or not. In this analysis, the activation probability is set to 10%. Then, the amount of activated flexibility has to be specified. For this purpose, a random variable with a uniform distribution between 0 and 1 is generated for each time step. A value of 0 in this case denotes activation of 0% of the offered flexibility, while a value of 1 reflects an activation of 100% of the flexibility offered in that time step. Through this process, the amount of activated flexibility in each time step is simulated. Activating flexibility leads to a variation of the SOC at the end of the day. The SOC at the end of the day is thus corrected by the corresponding value and used as the initial SOC for the day-ahead scheduling of the next day. Note that in the day-ahead scheduling, it is enforced that each battery has an SOC of 50% at the end of each day, regardless of the start SOC on that day. The SOC at the start and at the end of a day thus do not necessarily coincide.

Impact on the total bill of the community The total bill of the EC consists of two parts, the energy bill and the remuneration for the flexibility which was activated. For the energy bill, the actual meter readings are used and not the baseline computed in the day-ahead scheduling. The activated flexibility is remunerated according to the data presented in Section 3.4.

7.1.4 Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with known flexibility activation periods

This flexibility mechanism is a variation of the flexibility mechanism described in Section 7.1.3. In this case, the activation periods and the amount of flexibility to be activated are known a-priori. The first two steps of quantifying the daily available flexibility and the available flexibility in each time step are done as described in Section 7.1.3. For the disaggregation over the time steps of each day however, the a-priori information of the activation periods and the flexibility amount to be activated is used.

Flexibility disaggregation over the time steps In a first step, only the time steps in which it is beneficial for the community to offer flexibility are considered from the given activation periods. Thus, only time steps with a negative price for downward flexibility and a positive price for upward flexibility remain from the known activation periods. In a second step, these time steps are ordered by the flexibility price, from the time step with the highest remuneration for the flexibility to the one with the lowest remuneration. For each of the batteries the following steps are then executed.

- Start with the time step with the highest remuneration.

- Compute the minimum between the daily available flexibility of the battery, the available flexibility of the battery in this time step, and the remaining requested amount of flexibility in this time step (which is equal to the amount of flexibility requested by the system operator for the first battery and the updated amount for the subsequent batteries).
- Assign this amount of flexibility to the battery at this time step.
- This amount is then deducted from the remaining requested amount of flexibility in this time step and the daily available flexibility of the battery.
- Repeat this process for all time steps for the battery.
- Proceed to the next battery with the updated remaining amount of requested flexibility in each time step.

Through this process, the daily available flexibility of all batteries is disaggregated over the time steps in which flexibility will be activated, respecting the amount of flexibility requested, the daily available flexibility of each battery and the available flexibility in each time step of each battery. As the activation periods and the amounts to be activated are known a-priori, it is certain that the activation will happen. The SOC of each battery at the end of the day is corrected by the amount of flexibility provided by this battery and used as the start SOC for the day-ahead scheduling of the next day. The impact on the total bill of the community is computed as in Section 7.1.3.

7.2 Results and analysis of peer-to-peer energy trading models

The results obtained when applying the different flexibility mechanisms presented in the previous section under the P2P energy trading model are presented next.

7.2.1 Rule-based mechanism for kWmax service

In the following, the results of a simulation study for the explicit flexibility provision is described. In this study, a kWmax limit was computed and set for the time steps 18 and 19 of the day.

Analysis of the total energy bill First, the annual total energy bill of the community was analyzed for the baseline case with only the contractual limit on the net consumption from the retailer and the case with the kWmax limit acting on the net consumption. Table 7.2 shows the total energy bill of the community for the three cases and the two different pricing schemes in the baseline case and with the kWmax limit set. The negative values show that the EC has to pay the indicated amount to the retailer. The baseline case and the case with the active kWmax

Table 7.2 – Total energy bill of the community [€].

Study Case	Fixed	Dynamic
Case 1 - Baseline	-51984.21	-52597.18
Case 2 - Baseline	-43913.22	-47749.02
Case 3 - Baseline	-43090.90	-45618.16
Case 1 - With kWmax limit	-52060.96	-53216.22
Case 2 - With kWmax limit	-43770.92	-47961.36
Case 3 - With kWmax limit	-43115.41	-46562.67

limit are set into relation to another by computing the increase in the energy bill through

$$\Delta b_l = \frac{100}{b_0} (b_l - b_0) \quad (7.8)$$

where b_0 denotes the bill in the baseline case and b_l the bill in the case with the explicit kWmax limit. A positive value shows that the total energy bill increased, while a negative value indicates that the total energy bill decreased from the baseline case to the case with the active kWmax limit. The resulting values are shown in Table 7.3.

Table 7.3 – Increase of the total energy bill of the community [%].

Study Case	Fixed	Dynamic
Case 1	0.15	1.18
Case 2	-0.32	0.44
Case 3	0.06	2.07

Based on the analysis of the results of Table 7.3, it is verified that with an exception of case 2 with the fixed pricing scheme, the total energy bill of the community increased when setting the kWmax limit in the two time steps. The increase of the total energy bill is higher in the dynamic pricing scheme and highest in case 3, followed by case 1 and lastly case 2. The increase in the total energy bill can be traced to the additional constraint, which enforces a solution of the optimization problem which is suboptimal for optimization without the additional constraint. However, as the optimization problem is non-convex, there may exist local optima. The algorithm may thus find a local optimum and not the global one, wherefore the solution found may not be the solution with the lowest total energy bill. This phenomenon may explain the decrease in the total energy bill in case 2 with the fixed pricing scheme. Here, the solutions found in the baseline case may have been locally optimal solutions, whereas the solutions found in the simulations with the active kWmax constraint may be solutions with a lower total energy bill.

In the next step, the reduction in the net consumption of the EC from the retailer is analyzed. In this analysis, only the net consumption in the time steps 18 and 19 in which the kWmax limit was set are analyzed. In addition, from these time steps, only those in which the EC has a positive net consumption in both the baseline case and the simulation with the active kWmax limit are analyzed.

The net consumption of the EC from the retailer is shown in Figure 7.1 in hour 18 of each day and in Figure 7.2 in hour 19 of each day of the simulation. Both figures show the net consumption in the baseline case, the kWmax limit computed from this baseline case and the minimally required net consumption of the EC without batteries, and the resulting net consumption in the simulation with the active kWmax limit.

Figure 7.1a to Figure 7.1f show the net consumption in hour 18 for each one of the three cases and the two different pricing scheme. In the following, Figure 7.1a is described, highlighting the different types of relations found between the two simulations and the kWmax limit which was computed.

From the relations shown in Table 7.4 the second relation stands out, as the kWmax limit is equal to the net consumption in the baseline case, but the net consumption in the simulation with the kWmax limit active is then lower. The expected net consumption in the simulation with the active kWmax limit would be the baseline net consumption, as the baseline solution is still a valid solution after adding the kWmax limit to the optimization problem. The phenomenon can however be explained by the optimization problem being non-convex, wherefore multiple local minima may exist. Adding an additional constraint can thus lead to finding a different local

Table 7.4 – Comparison between the baseline case, the kWmax limit and the simulation with the active kWmax limit shown in Figure 7.1.

kWmax limit	Simulation with kWmax limit	Example
= baseline case	= baseline case	Days 11 to 21 in Figure 7.1a
= baseline case	< baseline case	Day 1 in Figure 7.1a
< baseline case	= kWmax limit	Day 2 in Figure 7.1c
< baseline case	< kWmax limit	Day 29 in Figure 7.1a

optimum, resulting in a different net consumption of the EC from the retailer. Another interesting behavior that shall be pointed out can be observed in Figure 7.1b on day 15 of the simulations. Here, the net consumption takes on a high negative value, around -150 kW which does not seem plausible. When analysing the net interaction with the retailer on that day, it can be seen that this net injection is due to the community battery charging at an earlier time step of the day and discharging at the time step 18. The behavior is thus plausible.

The types of relations between the baseline case, the kWmax limit and the simulation with the active kWmax limit shown in Figure 7.2, are similar to the ones in hour 18 in 7.1.

Figure 7.1 – Net consumption in the baseline case, the computed kWmax limit and the resulting net consumption with the active kWmax limit of the EC from the retailer in hour 18 over all the days of the simulation. The same legend applies to all plots. Case 1: original, case 2: lower flexibility, case 3: higher flexibility.

Figure 7.2 – Net consumption in the baseline case, the computed kWmax limit and the resulting net consumption with the active kWmax limit of the EC from the retailer in hour 19 over all the days of the simulation. The same legend applies to all plots.

7.2.2 Tariff-based mechanisms

Capacity tariff The introduction of a capacity tariff aims at reducing the peak net consumption of the EC from the retailer. Figure 7.3 shows the net consumption of the EC from the retailer for the three cases under the constant pricing scheme for a baseline case and a simulation with the capacity tariff. In the baseline case, the capacity tariff was set to zero, while in the simulation with the capacity tariff, the provided value $\lambda_c = 3.09668 \text{ €/kW/month}$ was applied as the tariff for the peak consumption.

Figure 7.3 – Peak net consumption for each day for the baseline simulation with and without the capacity tariff.

In case 1, shown in Figure 7.3a, the peak net consumption of the EC was lowered on all of the days by applying the capacity tariff. While on some days there is only a slight decrease, e.g. on day 4; on other days the decrease is more pronounced, e.g. on day 18 with a reduction of 28%.

In case 2, shown in Figure 7.3b, the peak net consumption was always lowered on all days with a positive net peak consumption in the baseline simulation, except for on day 3. Here, the peak net consumption increased slightly. On day 4 on the other hand, the peak net consumption is negative in the baseline case and higher in the simulation with the capacity tariff. This effect is however acceptable, as the capacity tariff was only applied to positive values peak net consumption, and therefore did not penalize the negative net peak consumption.

Figure 7.4 – Daily repeating Time-of-Use tariff used in the simulation.

In case 3, which is shown in Figure 7.3c, the peak net consumption is lowered on all of the days except for the days 2, 11, 14 and 23. On these days the peak net consumption is slightly higher in the simulation with the capacity tariff than in the baseline case, even though the peak net consumption is positive in the baseline case. This effect may be explained by the existence of local optima of the non-convex optimization problem. Because of these local optima, the introduction of the peak tariff into the objective function may lead to a result with a higher peak net consumption.

Time-of-Use tariff Figure 7.4 shows the Time-of-Use tariff added to the offtake retailer price. In the proposed P2P energy trading model, the consumption of the loads can be lowered but not shifted in time. The consumption can thus only be shifted to time steps with a lower energy price by using the batteries. A shift in consumption would thus be observable by studying the charging and discharging values of the batteries and the net consumption of the EC from the retailer. The results of the baseline simulation and the simulation with the ToU tariff are shown in Figure 7.5. The left column shows the sum of the charge and discharge values of all batteries, while the right column shows the net consumption of the EC from the retailer. The simulations were performed for all three cases with the constant pricing scheme for one day (17.08.2024). In case 1, the results show that the batteries are being charged and discharged less in the simulation with the ToU tariff than in the baseline case, with the exception of a higher charge value in time step 14 in the simulation with the ToU tariff. These results indicate that loads are not significantly supplied by the batteries to shift the consumption to time steps with lower energy prices. However, the net consumption of the EC from the retailer shows that the net consumption was lowered in some time steps during the day.

In some time steps in case 2, the battery charging and discharging values are slightly higher in the simulation with the ToU tariff than in the baseline simulation. However, the net consumption of the EC from the retailer is almost equal in both simulations. This indicates that the batteries were not used significantly to reduce the net consumption from the retailer and thus, in this case, the implicit flexibility scheme with the ToU tariff did not have a significant impact on the net consumption of the EC.

In case 3, the battery charging and discharging values in the simulation with the ToU tariff are lower or equal to the values in the baseline simulation. However, the net consumption of the EC from the retailer was lowered significantly in the time steps with a higher ToU tariff. This indicates that the energy was not supplied by the batteries but that the consumption of the loads was probably lowered in time steps with a high ToU tariff.

Figure 7.5 – Sum of the battery charging and discharging values (left) and net consumption of the EC from the retailer (right) over one day (17.08.2024) in all three cases for the constant pricing scheme for the baseline case and the simulation with the Time-of-use tariff for one day.

7.2.3 Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with unknown and known flexibility activation periods

In the following, the results for the explicit flexibility provision, as described in Section 7.1.3 and 7.1.4, are presented. Both the results from the unknown and known activation flexibility activation periods situations are given here to evaluate the influence of the a-priori information on the activation of flexibility and consequently on the remuneration for the ToU.

The total annual bill of the baseline case without flexibility activation and of the scenario with flexibility activation in both the unknown and known activation flexibility activation periods situations are shown in Table 7.5. For all simulations, the three different cases and the two different pricing strategies are evaluated. The negative values in the table show that in all simulations the ToU has to pay the indicated amount.

Table 7.5 – Total bill of the community [€].

Study Case	Fixed	Dynamic
Case 1 - Baseline	-51984.21	-52597.18
Case 2 - Baseline	-43913.22	-47749.02
Case 3 - Baseline	-43090.90	-45618.16
Case 1 - Flexibility (unknown act.)	-51633.78	-51622.96
Case 2 - Flexibility (unknown act.)	-43669.39	-47829.30
Case 3 - Flexibility (unknown act.)	-42078.35	-44149.13
Case 1 - Flexibility (known act.)	-48418.25	-51620.66
Case 2 - Flexibility (known act.)	-43656.12	-48060.38
Case 3 - Flexibility (known act.)	-36653.72	-38560.83

To relate the total annual bill of the baseline case to the total annual bill with flexibility provision, the percentual reduction of the bill in the scenarios with flexibility provision is computed as

$$\Delta b_f = \frac{100}{b_0} (b_0 - b_f) \quad (7.9)$$

where b_0 denotes the bill in the baseline cases and b_f the bill in the cases of flexibility provision. This percentual reduction is computed for all cases and both pricing strategies and shown in Table 7.6. A positive value shows that the total bill was decreased when offering the flexibility service, while a negative value indicates that the bill increased by providing the flexibility service.

Table 7.6 – Percentual reduction of the annual total bill [%].

Study Case	Fixed	Dynamic
Case 1 (unknown act.)	0.67	1.85
Case 2 (unknown act.)	0.56	-0.17
Case 3 (unknown act.)	2.35	3.22
Case 1 (known act.)	6.86	1.86
Case 2 (known act.)	0.59	-0.65
Case 3 (known act.)	14.94	15.47

The values in Table 7.6 show that with the exception of case 2 with the dynamic pricing scheme, the total annual bill of the community decreased under both the unknown and known activation

flexibility activation periods situations. In general, the values are higher in the simulations with the known activation of flexibility. In the simulations with the unknown activation, the decrease is in general higher with the dynamic pricing scheme. Furthermore, the decrease is highest in case 3, reaching a value of 3.22 % in the dynamic pricing scheme, followed by case 1 and lastly case 2. In the simulations with the certain activation, the decrease is highest in case 3 too, with the decrease being significantly higher than in the case of uncertain activation. The highest decrease in the bill is observed in case 3 under the dynamic pricing scheme, reaching a value of 15.47 % w.r.t the baseline case.

As the total annual bill consist of the energy part and the flexibility part, the energy part of the simulation with flexibility activated is compared in the following to the baseline case. Table 7.7 shows the components of the bill in the three cases and both pricing schemes for the unknown activation and the known activation flexibility activation periods. The first component is the energy cost, while the second component shows the remuneration received for providing the flexibility service. In the baseline case, the total annual bill in Table 7.5 corresponds to the energy part of the bill and the flexibility remuneration is equal to zero.

Table 7.7 – Components of the bill in the simulation with flexibility activation [€].

Study Case	Fixed		Dynamic	
	Energy bill	Flexibility remuneration	Energy bill	Flexibility remuneration
Case 1 (unk. act.)	-53358.13	1724.35	-52880.27	1257.30
Case 2 (unk. act.)	-44379.29	709.90	-48402.00	572.70
Case 3 (unk. act.)	-44614.27	2535.92	-46592.20	2443.07
Case 1 (kn. act.)	-56944.57	8526.32	-57436.71	5816.05
Case 2 (kn. act.)	-45309.62	1653.50	-49586.66	1526.28
Case 3 (kn. act.)	-48482.44	11828.72	-50607.13	12046.30

In general, the amount of remuneration received in the simulations with known flexibility activation is significantly higher than with the unknown activation. However, this result does not necessarily stem from the a-priori information on the activation periods and the the amount of flexibility to be activated in the known activation case. As in the unknown activation case, the activation probability in each time is set to 10 % and the amount to be activated is chosen according to a uniform distribution between 0 % and 100 %, the total amount of activated flexibility may be higher in the certain activation simulation than in the uncertain activation simulation. However, from the model it is evident, that in the certain activation simulation, the flexibility to be offered by the EC can be distributed in a more informed way, covering only the time steps in which exactly the requested amount will be activated. It is thus expected, that at least a part of the higher remuneration follows from including the apriori information on the activation periods and the amount to be activated in the process of disaggregating the available flexibility over the correct time steps.

For the simulations with unknown activation, the data in Table 7.7 shows that the remuneration for the flexibility is higher in the fixed pricing scheme than in the dynamic one. Furthermore, the flexibility remuneration is highest in case 3, followed by case 1 and lastly case 2. This can be explained by the different assets in each case. As there are more batteries in case 3 than in case 2 and case 1, more flexibility can be provided in this case. In addition, the battery capacity of the community battery is significantly higher in case 1 compared to case 2, which allows for more flexibility provision. In the simulations with certain activation, the remuneration for flexibility is not generally higher in the fixed pricing scheme. However, as in the simulations with uncertain activity, the remuneration is highest in the simulations of case 3, followed by case

2 and case 1.

To compare the energy part of the total annual bill of the simulation with flexibility provision to the baseline case, the percentual increase of the annual energy part of the bill is computed with (7.9). The results are shown in Table 7.8, with a different convention from before. In this table, a positive value shows that the energy part of the energy bill was increased, while a negative value indicates that when providing flexibility services the energy part of the bill decreased.

Table 7.8 – Percentual increase of the annual bill - only the energy part [%].

Study Case	Fixed	Dynamic
Case 1 (unknown act.)	2.64	0.54
Case 2 (unknown act.)	1.06	1.37
Case 3 (unknown act.)	3.54	2.14
Case 1 (known act.)	9.54	9.20
Case 2 (known act.)	3.18	3.85
Case 3 (known act.)	12.51	10.94

The results obtained show that in all of the cases the annual total energy bill was increased. This increase can be explained by the way the total energy bill was computed. When offering downward flexibility, the consumption of the community is increased, and the additional amount consumed is added to the energy bill of the community. Even though the energy is stored in the battery and can be used the next day, the efficiency of the battery and the consumption at a possibly not optimal time step increase the value of the energy bill. On the other hand, when offering upward flexibility, the battery is discharged additionally resulting in a lower SOC in the beginning of the next day. Even though the amount of energy discharged is respected in the total energy bill, the battery efficiency and selling at a possibly suboptimal time step increase the total energy bill. While in case 1 and case 3, the increase is higher in the simulations with the fixed pricing scheme, the inverse relation is found in case 2. The increase is highest in case 3 and in general, the increase is higher in the simulations with the certain flexibility activation. This may indicate that in case 3 and in the simulations with certain flexibility activation more flexibility was provided.

Shortcomings of both activation schemes In both schemes flexibility is offered by each battery individually but the total bill is calculated for the whole community. This implies that the remuneration for the flexibility service and the possibly additional costs for energy are seen only at the community level. In addition, in the known activation scheme, the order of the batteries which are providing the requested flexibility is set by the order in the model, starting with the community battery and then proceeding with the batteries of the members in a fixed order. By following this pre-determined order of the batteries, flexibility will always be provided by the first batteries if they can provide flexibility in the time step, which may not be fair.

7.3 Conclusions

Rule-based mechanism for kWmax service In the rule-based mechanism for kWmax service an approach to first define a kWmax limit for the net consumption of the EC from the retailer was defined, and it was then shown how the kWmax limit is included in the formulation of the P2P energy trading algorithm. Results obtained show that the optimal solution successfully respects the kWmax limit defined, but the trade-off is a slight increase in the total energy bill for the community in all test cases except for case 2 with a constant pricing scheme. Results

obtained also indicate that local minima may impact the results obtained. In particular it was pointed out that the net consumption in the simulation with the kWmax limit may be significantly below the baseline net consumption, even in cases in which the baseline net consumption was set as the kWmax limit. Nevertheless, in general, it is found that on most days the kWmax limit set on the basis of the baseline net consumption and the minimally needed net consumption of the EC without batteries coincides with the net consumption in the baseline simulation.

Tariff-based mechanisms For the tariff-based mechanisms, two different schemes were tested, the addition of a capacity tariff and the use of a Time-of-Use tariff. In the case of the capacity tariff, the peak net consumption of the EC from the retailer was lowered on most days. A significant decrease of the net peak consumption was for example observed on day 18 of case 1 with a reduction of 28 %. However, on some days, mostly in case 3, the peak net consumption was not lowered but increased. This effect may be due to the existence of local minima in the non-convex optimization problem. In the case of including a Time-of-Use tariff, no significant influence of the tariff on the net consumption of the EC from the retailer was found.

Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with unknown and known flexibility activation periods For this explicit flexibility mechanism, an approach to quantify the daily available flexibility without the need of rescheduling the members consumption and generation was presented. In this approach, the batteries are used to provide flexibility. The available flexibility was successfully disaggregated over the time steps respecting the technical limits of the batteries and the mutually exclusive charging and discharging of the batteries. This flexibility was analyzed under two situations: (i) unknown flexibility activation periods and (ii) known flexibility activation periods. While the unknown flexibility activation periods situation assumed a 10 % probability of flexibility activation and an activation amount reaching from 0% to 100% of the offered flexibility, the known flexibility activation periods situation used a-priori information on the activation periods and the requested amount. In both situations, flexibility was successfully provided by the EC. As a result, the energy bill increased, however with the remuneration received for the activation of the flexibility the total bill for the EC decreased. The remuneration and the decrease of the total bill were more pronounced in the known flexibility activation periods situation, due to the use of the a-priori information to distribute the daily available flexibility over the time steps with known activation.

Further work

Rule-based mechanism for kWmax service The chosen kWmax limit coincides with the baseline result for most days. This shows that in the baseline simulation, the net consumption of the EC from the retailer is lower or equal to the minimally required consumption of the EC without batteries, showing that in the baseline case, the batteries already contribute to the consumption needed by the EC. This observation indicates that further research is needed on how to better define the kWmax limit such that the net consumption of the EC is guaranteed to be lower than in the baseline case, while guaranteeing that the optimisation problem is feasible.

Another relevant research topic is finding the optimisation global minimum. Because of the non-convexity of the optimisation problem, the solution found may be a local optimum and the solution may change significantly when introducing an additional constraint, even though the optimisation problem with the additional constraint may still admit the initial solution.

Additionally, the analysis of the total bill of the EC should take into account a remuneration for lowering the kWmax limit. With this additional source of income for the EC, lowering the kWmax limit may be profitable for the EC even though the total energy bill increases.

Tariff-based mechanisms In the tariff-based mechanisms, the application of other tariff structures is a relevant research topic. In addition, the analysis presented in this report investigated the application of the Time-of-Use tariff and the capacity tariff separately. Future research

should investigate the impact of combining multiple tariff-based mechanisms.

Explicit flexibility mechanism for market-based services with unknown and known flexibility activation periods In both activation situations, the available daily flexibility is quantified in a day-ahead process and then offered in the time steps with the highest remuneration price (unknown flexibility activation situation) or the time steps with the highest remuneration price in which flexibility will be activated (known flexibility activation situation). However, when activating a certain amount of downward (or upward) flexibility, the minimum (or maximum) SOC of the battery over the whole day changes, leading to an increased amount of available downward (or upward) flexibility for the rest of the day. In the case of the unknown flexibility activation, the additional available flexibility could be bid in the market during the day to maximise the amount of flexibility offered. In the case of the known flexibility activation, the additional available flexibility could be offered in other time steps in which this flexibility will be requested.

Another relevant research topic is the estimation of activation probability and activation amount in the case of uncertain activation. Through this estimate, the estimated remuneration in each time step can be computed, leading to a more informed bidding strategy of the EC.

In the case of known flexibility activation, the proposed approach performs the day-ahead P2P energy trading without taking into consideration the known activation periods and corresponding flexibility amounts activated. Future research may investigate possible ways to include the known activation periods and activation amounts directly in the day-ahead P2P energy trading. By including this information on flexibility in the P2P energy trading, the amount of flexibility to be offered may increase, resulting in a greater income through the flexibility services.

In addition, in both the unknown and known flexibility activation periods situations, the time steps are separated into those for providing upward and downward flexibility based on the battery discharging or charging according to the day-ahead P2P energy trading results. This separation of time steps is needed as charging and discharging are mutually exclusive actions for each battery. However, this condition can be relaxed, as in the case that the battery only interacts with the retailer, offering downward flexibility does not necessarily have to be offered by charging more energy, but may also be offered by discharging less energy or to charge instead of discharge. The same follows for the case of offering upward flexibility. Following this reasoning, the condition can be relaxed to only take into account the charging or discharging behavior of each battery with EC members and excluding the interaction with the retailer. This offers the possibility to offer more flexibility in more time steps, maximising the amount of flexibility offered by the EC.

Another future research topic is the analysis of the benefits of including a reserve of the battery capacity for flexibility activation in the P2P energy trading optimisation. When setting the limits of the SOC of the batteries not to the technical limits but to a more narrow region, it would be ensured that the battery can deliver a certain amount of flexibility each day. However, there is a trade-off between the amount of reserved flexibility and using the capacity of the battery for EC internal energy exchange in the P2P energy trading. Investigating the effect of this trade-off is relevant as it provides insights into the scheduling constraints which are most profitable for an EC.

In addition, the shortcomings mentioned in Section 7.1.3 should be investigated in future research. This includes finding a fair distribution of the remuneration and additional costs associated with providing flexibility and investigation of a fair order of assigning flexibility to each battery.

Lastly, it is interesting to investigate the influence of different flexibility service remuneration schemes on the total bill of the community. In the simulations shown in this section, only the remuneration for the amount of activated flexibility was taken into consideration. However, there are other remuneration schemes in which for example the availability for flexibility is remuner-

ated as well.

8 Conclusion and recommendations

8.1 Conclusion

This report has explored how different flexibility instruments can build on different local energy sharing models to deliver a variety of flexibility services, thus allowing Energy Communities not only to engage in local energy exchange, but also to deliver flexibility services, thus supporting the grid while securing additional revenue streams enabling their creation and upscaling.

The main takeaways from the analyses presented in this report are summarised below.

- The participation of ECs in DSO and TSO service provision is supported by regulation. At the DSO level, existing pilot projects indicate that aggregated, digitally managed community assets can provide reliable explicit flexibility, helping DSOs manage constraints and defer grid reinforcements. Meanwhile, at the TSO level, aggregated flexibility assets within ECs can contribute to FCR, aFRR, mFRR, and to a more limited extent FFR, particularly using fast assets like BESS and controllable loads. Demonstrations validate operational viability, and developments such as grid-forming inverters and storage-based black-start pilots point to a growing future role in system defense and restoration.
- The uptake of flexibility provision is still limited by regulatory fragmentation, inconsistent national product definitions, minimum bid sizes, demanding technical/prequalification requirements, and complex procedures. At distribution level, limited observability and controllability, strong locational constraints, and high costs for metering constrain eligibility, especially for small communities. Furthermore, uncertain baselines and revenues reduce engagement. For restoration, limits of current DERs (grid-following inverters, auxiliary power resilience, islanding restrictions) remain significant.
- Overall, the four U2Demo energy sharing and trading models are capable to integrate explicit flexibility mechanisms. For each model, a methodology to quantify the aggregated flexibility potential and that to activate flexibility as a market response have been developed. Furthermore, numerical simulations for all extended models show that an energy community can gain economic benefits by this activity regardless of the sharing and trading framework.
- The capacity, energy, and revenue allocation models can be extended to calculate profitable and technically available aggregated flexibility of an EC. Furthermore, dispatching flexibility can be performed simultaneously with the energy sharing and (re-)scheduling of all assets based on two objectives, namely maximising the quantity of provision and maximising the profit from provision. The latter approach is economically more advantageous than the former for the energy community, and these benefits can be appropriately distributed to all community members through an allocation mechanism and result in total cost reduction for all members.
- When energy is traded under an internal pricing mechanism, the explicit flexibility provision quantity (and consequently revenue) primarily depends on the choice of the pricing mechanism. For instance, flexibility activation is easier under the SDR mechanism as compared to the MMR mechanism. Nevertheless, overall, economic benefits are seen in both internal pricing mechanisms.
- Explicit flexibility provision can also be beneficial under auction-based local energy trading models, as it can generate additional revenue streams for community members by exploiting the remaining flexibility capacity after engaging in local trading.

- Similarly, when an energy community utilises a peer-to-peer energy trading model, explicit flexibility provision can be calculated based on the remaining capacity of flexible assets. The conducted numerical study shows the economic viability of flexibility provision not only when full information of flexibility activation is available but also when some information on the flexibility activation is stochastic.
- Beside explicit flexibility provision, the four energy sharing and trading models have also been extended to allow for kW-max service provision, either through a rule-based mechanism or a tariff-based mechanism. Overall, the rule-based mechanism can strictly limit the aggregated offtake of the community at the expense of an increase in the energy cost as compared to when the community is not restricted and, thus, allowed to fully utilise their flexible assets to optimise their energy bill. On the other hand, the tariff mechanisms can shape the aggregated offtake/injection profile of an EC although they cannot fully enforce the satisfaction of a kW-max limit. When the capacity tariff is integrated into the collective energy-sharing, internal pricing, and pool-based peer-to-peer energy trading models, we observe some level of reduction of the offtake peak. Meanwhile, the time-of-use tariffs that were tested in the collective energy-sharing, auction-based local energy trading, and pool-based peer-to-peer energy trading models simply shifted the peaks but did not necessarily reduce them.
- Although the numerical results are case-dependent, the study considers scenarios spanning different levels of available flexibility. This enables us to illustrate how the various energy sharing and trading models perform across these conditions and to draw a meaningful relative comparison among them.

8.2 Recommendations

Our study results in the following recommendations:

- Regulatory harmonisation is essential to scale EC participation in flexibility provision across both DSO-level services and TSO balancing markets, including aligned product definitions, baselining, measurement/verification, data exchange, and TSO-DSO coordination.
- The feasibility of EC participation in black-start requires an in-depth techno-economic assessment. While BESS can theoretically satisfy technical capability requirements, the required capacity (and associated investment, redundancy, and auxiliary-power resilience) may be prohibitive for many ECs.
- The quantitative analysis indicates that explicit flexibility mechanisms can deliver economic benefits across all tested energy sharing and trading models, and thus enable the delivery of flexibility services to DSOs and TSOs. However, further investigation is needed to address challenges remain therein, in particular with respect to adequate definitions of baselines [72] and ability to effectively control flexibility assets.
- Explicit flexibility procurement and activation schemes should be designed to match the energy sharing and trading framework used in the EC. Adaptations may be needed depending on the community's specific rules, regulatory context, asset portfolio, and operational constraints.
- Further research on explicit mechanisms is needed. On the consumers/ECs/FSPs side, one important direction is to focus on improving the robustness of flexibility estimation and activation against uncertainty, not only due to the variable renewable generation and

imperfect forecasts (of the weather as well as the energy profiles) but also flexibility activation parameters (e.g., requested quantity, activation period), to reduce performance risk. On the grid side, a second direction is to assess grid impacts beyond the activation window, since flexibility provision may shift consumption or generation in ways that create new peaks and potentially trigger unintended congestion. While combining tariff-based or rule-based measures with explicit mechanisms could mitigate such effects, the design and effectiveness of these combined approaches require further investigation. On the flexibility markets design side, these challenges add to other already investigated challenges in the literature including baselining and gaming risks [77].

- To be effective and avoid undesirable results, tariff-based mechanisms should be designed using realistic consumption profiles and explicit service objectives, then validated through controlled pilots before broader roll-out. The ability for a tariff structure to deliver the needed peak reduction or specific load-shifting requires (i) the tariff to provide enough incentive for the users and EC to shift or shave loads during certain defined times or certain grid conditions, (ii) the tariff not to lead to synchronized shifts leading to new peaks, and importantly (iii) that the tariff structure recognizes the available technically-feasible flexibility at the end-users side. If not enough flexibility is available, or if the tariff structure does not give adequate peak-reducing and/or peak-shifting incentives, considering the interplay with other price signals including retail prices, the EC response might deviate from the intended goals of the tariff structure thus reducing its potential effectiveness.

9 References

- [1] ENTSO-E, “Network code on load - frequency control and reserves,” tech. rep., ENTSO-E, 2013.
- [2] Y. Lu, E. Delarue, J. Meus, S. Aubri, N. Fatras, M. Gabay, R. Simon, V. Deichmann, D. P. Ferreira, T. Glória, A. Kostalova, H. Morais, W. Ananduta, H. Fani, A. Sanjab, and J. Vulinovic, “U2DEMO Deliverable D2.3: P2P trading matching and energy sharing models,” tech. rep., U2DEMO, 2025.
- [3] J. Jeriha, A. Gubina, T. Medved, B. Komel, V. Borozan, P. Krstevski, A. Krkoleva, S. Borozan, R. Taleski, and C. Chimirel, “National balancing and wholesale electricity markets structure and principles: Deliverable 10.1,” tech. rep., Crossbow project, 2019.
- [4] National Grid Electricity System Operator, “Black start from non-traditional technologies: Capability and readiness.” Technical Report, 2019.
- [5] THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION, “Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.” Official Journal of the European Union, 2018.
- [6] THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION, “Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU.” Official Journal of the European Union, 2019.
- [7] European Commission, “Commission regulation (eu) 2017/2195 of 23 november 2017 establishing a guideline on electricity balancing (text with eea relevance).” EUR-Lex: Official Journal of the European Union, 2017. OJ L 312, 28.11.2017, pp. 6–53.
- [8] European Commission, “Commission regulation (eu) 2017/2196 of 24 november 2017 establishing a network code on electricity emergency and restoration.” EUR-Lex: Summary of EU legislation, 2017.
- [9] C. Distribution Systems Working Group, “NRAs’ Approach to DSO Flexibility Procurement, Justifications for Derogations from Article 32,” tech. rep., Council of European Energy Regulators (CEER), 2025.
- [10] ENTSO-E, “The harmonised electricity market role model: version 2019-01,” tech. rep., ENTSO-E, 2019.
- [11] European Commission, “Commission regulation (eu) 2017/1485 of 2 august 2017 establishing a guideline on electricity transmission system operation.” EUR-Lex: Official Journal of the European Union, 2017. OJ L 220, 25.8.2017, pp. 1–120.
- [12] H. Holttinen, A. Cutululis, N. A. and Gubina, A. Keane, and F. Van Hulle, “REserviceS: Ancillary services: technical specifications, system needs and costs. Deliverable D 2.2,” tech. rep., DTU, 2012.
- [13] H. Gerard, E. I. Rivero Puente, and D. Six, “Coordination between transmission and distribution system operators in the electricity sector: A conceptual framework,” *Utilities Policy*, vol. 50, pp. 40–48, 2018.

- [14] A. Scrocca, E. Daccò, D. Andreotti, G. Rancilio, F. Bovera, D. Falabretti, and M. Delfanti, “Local flexibility markets in Europe: A critical review of market designs, operational maturity and stakeholder perspectives,” Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, vol. 226, no. Part D, p. 116434, 2026.
- [15] H. Taxt, S. Bjarghov, M. Askeland, P. C. del Granado, A. Morch, M. Z. Degefa, and R. Rana, “Integration of energy communities in distribution grids: Development paths for local energy coordination,” Energy Strategy Reviews, vol. 58, p. 101668, 2025.
- [16] E-Distribuzione, “Impiego dei servizi ancillari forniti da risorse di energia distribuite per l’esercizio della rete di distribuzione,” tech. rep., E-Distribuzione, 2024.
- [17] V. Nutsregulator, “Congestion Avoidance and Unlocking Flexibility,” tech. rep., Vlaamse Nutsregulator, 2025.
- [18] E. Distribuição de Eletricidade S.A., “Regulamento dos Concursos para a Prestação de Serviços de Flexibilidade,” tech. rep., E-REDES - Distribuição de Eletricidade S.A., 2025.
- [19] E-Distribuzione, “Impiego dei servizi ancillari forniti da risorse di energia distribuite per l’esercizio della rete di E-Distribuzione,” tech. rep., E-Distribuzione, 2025.
- [20] E-Distribuzione, “Impiego dei servizi ancillari forniti da risorse di energia distribuite per l’esercizio della rete di E-Distribuzione,” tech. rep., E-Distribuzione, 2024.
- [21] E-Distribuzione, “Impiego dei servizi ancillari forniti da Risorse di energia distribuite per l’esercizio della rete di E-Distribuzione,” tech. rep., E-Distribuzione, 2025.
- [22] A. Sanjab, K. Kessels, L. Marques, Y. Mou, H. Le Cadre, P. Crucifix, and A. García, “Coordinated d6.2 - evaluation of combinations of coordination schemes and products for grid services based on market simulations,” tech. rep., 2022.
- [23] A. Sanjab, L. Marques, W. Ananduta, H. Gerard, B. Shilpa, M. Troncia, et al., “Onenet d3.3 - recommendations for consumer-centric products and efficient market design.,” tech. rep., 2023.
- [24] A. Papavasiliou and I. Mezghani, “Coordination schemes for the integration of transmission and distribution system operations,” in Proceedings of the Power Systems Computation Conference (PSCC), pp. 1–7, 2018.
- [25] L. Marques, A. Sanjab, Y. Mou, H. Le Cadre, and K. Kessels, “Grid impact aware TSO-DSO market models for flexibility procurement: Coordination, pricing efficiency, and information sharing,” IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 1920–1933, 2023.
- [26] A. Sanjab, H. Le Cadre, and Y. Mou, “TSO-DSOs stable cost allocation for the joint procurement of flexibility: A cooperative game approach,” IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 4449–4464, 2022.
- [27] Y. Ruwaida, J. P. Chaves-Avila, N. Etherden, I. Gomez-Arriola, G. Gürses-Tran, K. Kessels, C. Madina, A. Sanjab, M. Santos-Mugica, D. N. Trakas, and M. Troncia, “Tso-dso-customer coordination for purchasing flexibility system services: Challenges and lessons learned from a demonstration in sweden,” IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 1883–1895, 2023.
- [28] A. Sanjab, L. Marques, H. Gerard, and K. Kessels, “Joint and sequential dso-tso flexibility markets: efficiency drivers and key challenges,” in 27th International Conference on Electricity Distribution (CIRED 2023), vol. 2023, pp. 3138–3143, 2023.

- [29] W. Ananduta, J. Vanschoenwinkel, L. Marques, L. Delchambre, A. Kaushal, and A. Sanjab, “Alexander d3.3 - tso-dso coordination for procurement and activation of system services,” tech. rep., 2024.
- [30] W. Ananduta, A. Sanjab, and L. Marques, “Ensuring grid-safe forwarding of distributed flexibility in sequential dso-tso markets,” IEEE Transactions on Energy Markets, Policy and Regulation, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 157–169, 2025.
- [31] S. Bindu, M. Troncia, J. P. C. Ávila, and A. Sanjab, “Bid forwarding as a way to connect sequential markets: Opportunities and barriers,” in 2023 19th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), pp. 1–6, 2023.
- [32] A. Kaushal, W. Ananduta, L. Marques, T. Cuypers, and A. Sanjab, “Operating envelopes for the grid-constrained use of distributed flexibility in balancing markets,” in 2024 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe (ISGT EUROPE), pp. 1–5, 2024.
- [33] L. Marques, W. Ananduta, A. Kaushal, and A. Sanjab, “Embedding operating envelopes in the market design to unlock the flexibility potential of distribution grids,” in CIREN 2024 Vienna Workshop, vol. 2024, pp. 786–789, 2024.
- [34] ACER, “Getting the Signals Right: Electricity Network Tariff Methodologies in Europe,” tech. rep., European Union Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER), 2025.
- [35] S. Cianchi, A. Sanjab, and S. Grammatico, “A two-part pricing mechanism for demand side management,” in 11th International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies (CoDIT), vol. 1, pp. 2245–2250, 2025.
- [36] E. Hillberg, A. Zegers, B. Herndler, S. Wong, J. Pompee, J.-Y. Bourmaud, S. Lehnhoff, G. Migliavacca, K. Uhlen, I. Oleinikova, H. Phil, M. Norström, M. Persson, J. Rossi, and G. Beccuti, “Flexibility needs in the future power system,” 03 2019.
- [37] Next-kraftwerke, “What is frequency containment reserve (fcr)?.” Next-kraftwerke website, 2026.
- [38] TERNA, “Fast reserve.” TERNA website, 2026. <https://www.terna.it/en/electric-system/pilot-projects-pursuant-arera-resolution-300-2017-reel/fast-reserve-pilot-project>, accessed on 2026-02-02.
- [39] Fingrid, “The technical requirements and the prequalification process of fast frequency reserve (ffr),” tech. rep., Fingrid, 2025.
- [40] ENTSO-E WGAS, “Survey on ancillary services procurement, balancing market design,” tech. rep., ENTSO-E, 2019.
- [41] ENTSO-E, “Fcr values full fcr procurement for belgium.” ENTSO-E website.
- [42] Tennet, “Ancillary services.” Tennet web-site. <https://www.tennet.eu/nl-en/markets/ancillary-services>, accessed on 2026-02-02.
- [43] TERNA, “Meccanismo di approvvigionamento della fcr.” TERNA website. https://download.terna.it/terna/Allegato-A.83_8de1e2e9852a056.pdf, accessed on 2026-02-02.
- [44] International Smart Grid Action Network (ISGAN), “An overview of policies and regulations and expansion planning and market analysis for the united states and europe,” tech. rep., International Smart Grid Action Network (ISGAN), 2013.

- [45] DNV KEMA, “Qualitative analysis of cross-border exchange of balancing energy and operational reserves between netherlands and belgium,” tech. rep., DNV KEMA, 2013.
- [46] ERSE, “Manual de procedimentos da gestão global do sistema,” tech. rep., ERSE, 2025.
- [47] Terna, “Procedura per la selezione delle risorse per mb e per la conversione delle offerte ai fini della partecipazione del gestore della rete alle piattaforme di bilanciamento,” tech. rep., Terna, 2026.
- [48] Tennet, “Manual / Product Information standard mFRR product (MARI product) for BSPs,” tech. rep., Tennet, 2025. <https://tennet-drupal.s3.eu-central-1.amazonaws.com/default/2025-12/Handbook%20mFRR%20standard%20product%20%28MARI%20product%29%20for%20BSPs%20-%20v1.0.pdf>.
- [49] ERSE, “Implementação do mercado de banda de reserva de restabelecimento da frequência com ativação manual.” Diário da República, 2023. pp 158-176.
- [50] Elia, “Individual mfr capacity bids.” OpenDataElia. <https://opendata.elia.be/explore/dataset/ods055/table/?sort=deliverydate>, accessed on 2026-02-03.
- [51] ENTSO-E, “Terre – trans-european replacement reserves exchange.” ENTSO-E Network Codes: Electricity Balancing.
- [52] European Commission, “Regulation (eu) 2024/1747 of the european parliament and of the council of 13 june 2024 amending regulations (eu) 2019/942 and (eu) 2019/943 as regards improving the union’s electricity market design.” EUR-Lex: Summary of EU legislation, 2024.
- [53] ENTSO-E, “Announcement from replacement reserve tsos.” ENTSO-E web-site.
- [54] European Commission, “Commission regulation (eu) 2016/631 of 14 april 2016 establishing a network code on requirements for grid connection of generators (text with eea relevance).” EUR-Lex: Official Journal of the European Union, 2016. OJ L 112, 27.4.2016, pp. 1–68.
- [55] European Commission, “Commission regulation (eu) 2019/941 of the council of 5 june 2019 on risk-preparedness in the electricity sector and repealing directive 2005/89/ec (text with eea relevance).” EUR-Lex: Official Journal of the European Union, 2019. OJ L 158, 14.6.2019, pp. 1–21.
- [56] European Commission, “Commission regulation (eu) 2017/2196 of 24 november 2017 establishing a network code on electricity emergency and restoration (text with eea relevance).” EUR-Lex: Official Journal of the European Union, 2017. OJ L 312, 28.11.2017, pp. 54–...
- [57] Z. Pan, N. Jenkins, and J. Wu, “Black start from renewable energy resources: Review and a case study of great britain,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 209, p. 115143, 2025.
- [58] National Energy System Operator, “National grid eso – frequency response services; project terre / eso dynamic services.” National Energy System Operator (NESO) Industry Information, 2026.
- [59] ENTSO-E, “Picasso – platform for the international coordination of automated frequency restoration and stable system operation.” ENTSO-E Network Codes: Electricity Balancing. https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/picasso/, accessed on 2026-02-02.

- [60] Fingrid Oyj, “The technical requirements and the prequalification process of frequency containment reserves (fcr).” Appendix 2 to the Market Agreement for FCR, Fingrid, 2025.
- [61] Fingrid Oyj, “Frequency containment reserves (fcr) – reserve products.” Fingrid electricity market information.
- [62] Fingrid Oyj, “Frequency containment reserves (fcr_n, fcr_u and fcr_d), transactions in the yearly and hourly markets.” Fingrid Reserve Market Information.
- [63] ESB Networks, “Facilitation of fast ds3 system services: Innovation strategy close-out report.” ESB Networks Innovation Strategy Publication, 2018.
- [64] EirGrid and SONI, “Ds3 system services: Current system services volume requirements information paper.” EirGrid / SONI Information Paper, July 2024.
- [65] OSMOSE Consortium, “Osmose (optimal system mix of flexibility solutions for european electricity).” Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission, 2018–2022. Grant Agreement No. 773406.
- [66] INTERFACE Consortium, “Interrface (tso-dso-consumer interface to provide innovative grid services).” Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission, 2019–2022. Grant Agreement No. 824330.
- [67] sonnen GmbH and Next Kraftwerke GmbH, “sonnen and next kraftwerke cooperate to supply primary control reserve.” Press release, sonnen GmbH, September 21 2020.
- [68] R. D’hulst, W. Labeeuw, B. Beusen, S. Claessens, G. Deconinck, and K. Vanthournout, “Demand response flexibility and flexibility potential of residential smart appliances: Experiences from large pilot test in belgium,” *Applied Energy*, vol. 155, pp. 79–90, 2015.
- [69] Netztransparenz.de, “Market-based procurement of black start capability.” Netztransparenz – German TSOs ancillary services information.
- [70] Bundesnetzagentur, “Go ahead for additional system stability measures.” Press release, Bundesnetzagentur, July 2025.
- [71] L. Colaluce, “Distributed black start: Uk’s strategy for a system without central backup.” Strategic Energy Europe, May 2025.
- [72] L. Lind, J. P. Chaves-Ávila, O. Valarezo, A. Sanjab, and L. Olmos, “Baseline methods for distributed flexibility in power systems considering resource, market, and product characteristics,” *Utilities Policy*, vol. 86, p. 101688, 2024.
- [73] Statistics Netherlands, “Prices of natural gas and electricity,” Sep 2025.
- [74] Stedin, “Electriciteit tarieven 2025,” tech. rep., 2025. <https://www.stedin.net/over-stedin/pers-en-media/persberichten/netbeheertarieven-stedin-stijgen-in-2025>.
- [75] Tennet, “Tennet transparency data.” <https://www.tennet.eu/nl-en/node/3479>. Accessed: 2025-11-20.
- [76] A. Sanjab, A. Kaushal, and T. Cuypers, “End users flexibility potential estimation under differing prosumers’ characteristics and constraints,” *IET Conference Proceedings*, vol. 2025, pp. 643–647, 2025.
- [77] L. Marques and A. Sanjab, “Strategic behavior in TSO-DSO coordinated flexibility markets: A nash equilibrium and efficiency analysis,” *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, vol. 39, p. 101476, 2024.

APPENDIX A: Grid limit calculation

In reality, the actual grid limit imposed on the Dutch demo case studies is set at 600 kW. Based on the offtake and injection outcomes of the centralised energy-sharing schemes presented in Deliverable D2.3, it is observed that this limit is excessively high, making the evaluation of the rule-based mechanisms under this constraint impractical. Therefore, to enable a meaningful assessment of the proposed mechanisms, new grid limits are derived using the outcomes of the energy-sharing schemes as a baseline.

To determine the grid limits, the load duration curve (LDC) of the optimal community offtake resulting from the energy-sharing scheme is employed. Figure A.1 illustrates the LDC of the optimal offtake for Case Study 1. An LDC represents electrical demand over a specified time horizon by ranking load values in descending order of magnitude. Unlike a conventional load curve, which preserves the chronological sequence of demand, the LDC reorganises the data to indicate the proportion of time during which specific load levels are met or exceeded.

Figure A.1 – Example of the LDC of community offtake in Case 1.

To enable a meaningful evaluation of the rule-based mechanisms, the derived grid limits must actively constrain the community's electrical offtake rather than remain non-binding. To this end, a LDC-driven approach is adopted to define the grid limits. Specifically, the 95th percentile of the LDC of the community offtake is used, which represents the load level that is exceeded during only 5% of the evaluated time horizon and therefore captures near-peak operating conditions. This percentile value is then added to the maximum community offtake observed at each time step to account for temporal variations and ensure that the resulting grid limit remains sufficiently restrictive. The resulting grid limit is then defined as

$$P^{\text{grid}}(t) = p_{\text{comm}}^{\text{max}}(t) + p_{\text{LDC}}^{95\%}, \quad \forall t = 1, \dots, T. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $p_{\text{comm}}^{\text{max}}(t)$ denotes the maximum community offtake at time step $t = 1, \dots, T$, and $p_{\text{LDC}}^{95\%}$ denotes the 95th percentile of the load duration curve of the community offtake.

The maximum community offtake at each time step is computed as follows. Let \mathcal{H} denote the set of households, with $|\mathcal{H}| = H$, and let $p_{h,t}$ represent the offtake of household $h \in \mathcal{H}$ at time step $t = 1, \dots, T$. The maximum community offtake at each time step is defined as

$$p_{\text{comm}}^{\text{max}}(t) = \max_{h \in \mathcal{H}} p_{h,t}, \quad \forall t = 1, \dots, T. \quad (\text{A.2})$$